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Application of Optimisation Strategies to Shallow Water Flow Simulation

Master thesis

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Declaration of Authorship

I declare that this thesis was composed by myself and that the work contained herein is my own except where explicitly stated otherwise by reference or acknowledgment.

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Abstract

Numerical surface water flow models are often used by decision makers to design flood protection measures, because they offer crucial information about the flow field and temporal characteristics of potential inundations. Large scale simulations, taking multiple days to complete, may offer detailed insights, whereas a smaller scale may be necessary to create quick forecastings. This is why the computational performance and an efficient use of given resources by the numerical model must not be neglected.

Steffen et al. (2020) introduced a new open-source C++ framework for explicit FVM solvers called `hms++`. The framework includes a performance-oriented rewrite of a robust Godunov-type solver for the depth-averaged shallow water equations, originally implemented in the Java framework *Hydroinformatics Modeling Systems*. In this thesis, the solver is verified, a number of new traversal strategies for the edge-based flux calculation are introduced and investigated for parallel performance and scalability on shared-memory systems. Since some of the introduced patterns are based on the principle of cache blocking, a preliminary study concerning the tile size is carried out as well. The test platform was a compute node containing two sockets, each equipped with an Intel Xeon Platinum 9242, totaling 96 physical cores and 192 hardware threads.

The preliminary study reveals load balancing issues in the seamless block-wise traversal patterns, leading to a redesign of the approaches. Increasing the block size slightly improved the performance of the flux calculation on a large mesh set, although in total, the speed-up is somewhat diminished when summing up all computational steps involved. The study also finds that an increase of the block size does not result in any performance benefits for smaller meshes, probably due to the large amount of cache memory that is available on the test platform. In the future, more elaborate tests, involving a wider range of mesh sizes and varying numbers of utilised threads, should be carried out.

The parallel performance investigation shows that the introduced traversal patterns scale well, obtaining maximum speed-ups ranging between $57.52\times$ and $67.41\times$ for a large mesh without the use of simultaneous multithreading (SMT). On a small mesh, higher speed-ups are obtained, ranging between $77.52\times$ and $84.09\times$, except for row-wise traversal patterns. These patterns exhibit signs of increasing communication overhead when increasing the core count. Enabling SMT further speeds up all patterns for up to 32 cores. SMT mitigates performance for some patterns when more cores were utilised. Overall, the fastest or next to fastest computation times were obtained with the seamless block-wise traversal pattern. The pattern also showed good scalability on all meshes, regardless of SMT.

Lastly, a comparative study between `hms++` and the Java version is carried out. The study includes a surface runoff simulation for a rainfall event in the Alps in Austria. Results show that `hms++` is up to $1.26\times$ faster than the Java version. Nevertheless, the Java version performs better than expected, which suggests that a more encapsulated approach for the computational steps may further improve the performance of `hms++`.

Kurzzusammenfassung

Numerische Strömungsmodelle können aufschlussreiche Informationen über den räumlichen und zeitlichen Verlauf von möglichen Überflutungen bieten, weshalb sie häufig im Bereich des Hochwasserschutzes eingesetzt werden. Dabei kann die Größenordnung und Rechenzeit solcher Modelle stark variieren. Modelle von großem Ausmaß können detaillierte Erkenntnisse liefern, was jedoch oftmals mit einem Rechenaufwand von mehreren Tagen oder Wochen verbunden ist. Kleinere Größendimensionen werden beispielsweise genutzt, um schnelle Voraussagen zu fundieren. Dies sind Gründe, weshalb die Rechenzeit und effiziente Nutzung der gegebenen Ressourcen wichtige Aspekte sind, die im Entwurf eines numerischen Modells berücksichtigt werden müssen.

In Steffen et al. (2020) wird ein neues Open-Source Framework vorgestellt, in welchem explizite Löser für die Finite-Volumen Methode implementiert werden können. Das Framework trägt den Namen `hms++` und beinhaltet u. a. eine Performance-orientierte Neuaufsetzung eines Godunov-Lösers für die tiefengemittelten Flachwassergleichungen, der ursprünglich im Java Framework *Hydroinformatics Modeling Systems* implementiert wurde. In dieser Arbeit wird der Löser validiert und es werden eine Reihe von Traversierungsverfahren für die kantenbasierte Flussberechnung vorgestellt und auf ihre parallele Rechenleistung und Skalierbarkeit getestet. Da manche der vorgestellten Traversierungsverfahren das Cache-Blocking Prinzip nutzen, wird eine vorläufige Parameterstudie zur Blockgröße durchgeführt. Alle Studien nutzen eine Maschine mit zwei Prozessorfassungen, die jeweils mit einem Intel Xeon Platinum 9242 ausgestattet sind, sodass insgesamt 96 Rechenkerne und 192 Hardware Threads zur Verfügung stehen.

Die vorläufige Studie zur Blockgröße deckt die schlechte Lastenverteilung der ursprünglich entworfenen Strategien auf, was zu einem Neuentwurf der Verfahren geführt hat. Die Blockgröße betreffend hat die Studie gezeigt, dass eine Vergrößerung die Flussberechnung auf einem großen Testgitter beschleunigt, jedoch wird die gewonnene Zeit durch das Aufsummieren mit den anderen Rechenschritten ausgeglichen. Auf einem kleineren Rechengitter konnte die Rechenleistung durch eine Blockvergrößerung nicht verbessert werden, was möglicherweise auf die große Menge des verfügbaren Cache-Speichers der Testmaschine zurückzuführen ist. Die Ergebnisse zeigen, dass weitere Untersuchungen auf einer größeren Anzahl von Gittern und genutzten Threads durchgeführt werden sollten. In der Untersuchung zur parallelen Rechenleistung zeigen die Traversierungsverfahren eine gute Skalierbarkeit und erzielen Beschleunigungsfaktoren von $57.52\times$ bis $67.41\times$ auf dem großen Testgitter, ohne den Einsatz von simultanem Multithreading (SMT). Für das kleine Gitter können alle Verfahren, bis auf die Row-wise-Traversierungsverfahren, sogar

Faktoren zwischen $77.52\times$ und $84.09\times$ erzielen. Für höhere Kernanzahlen zeigen die Row-wise-Verfahren jedoch Anzeichen für einen erhöhten Kommunikations-Overhead, weshalb geringere Beschleunigungsfaktoren erzielt werden. SMT erzielt weitere Verbesserungen der Rechenleistung, solange weniger als 32 Rechenkerne genutzt werden. Wenn mehr Kerne genutzt werden, verringert SMT die Rechenleistung mancher Traversierungsverfahren. Insgesamt erzielt das Seamless Block-wise-Traversierungsverfahren die schnellsten bis zweitschnellsten Rechenzeiten und demonstriert durchweg gute Skalierbarkeit, unabhängig vom Einsatz von SMT.

Zuletzt wird eine Vergleichsstudie zwischen **hms++** und der Java-Version durchgeführt. In der Studie wird ein Oberflächenabfluss simuliert, der auf einem realen Niederschlagsereignis basiert, das in den österreichischen Alpen im Jahr 2007 stattgefunden hat. Die Ergebnisse zeigen, dass **hms++** bis zu $1.26\times$ schneller als die Java-Version ist, sofern das Seamless Block-wise-Traversierungsverfahren genutzt wird.

In Zukunft sollte ein Berechnungsansatz für **hms++** untersucht werden, in dem die einzelnen Berechnungsschritte stärker gekapselt sind. Als Ausgangspunkt dieser Anregung steht die Rechenleistung der Java-Version, welche höher als erwartet ist.

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List of Symbols

Symbol	- Description	Unit
c_w	- gravity wave speed	[m/s]
d	- water depth	[m]
e_p	- parallel efficieny	[-]
f_l, f_r	- connecting functions for Riemann states	
\mathbf{f}	- vector of advective fluxes in x-direction	
f_x	- external forces in x-direction	[m ² /s ²]
f_y	- external forces in y-direction	[m ² /s ²]
g	- gravitational acceleration	[m/s ²]
\mathbf{g}	- vector of advective fluxes in y-direction	
h	- water elevation	[m]
h_p	- height of hydrostatic pressure area	[m]
i	- infiltration	[m/s]
k_{Str}	- Strickler's roughness coefficient	[m ^{1/3} /s]
l	- edge length	[m]
m	- smoothness monitor	[-]
n	- Manning's roughness coefficient	[s/m ^{-1/3}]
\mathbf{n}	- unit vector normal to cell surface	
\mathbf{p}	- vector of hydrostatic pressure	
\mathbf{q}	- vector of conserved state variables	
r	- mass source/sink	[m/s]
\mathbf{s}	- vector of sources and sinks	
\mathbf{s}_m	- vector of mass sources and sinks and external forces	
\mathbf{s}_B	- vector of bed slope sources	
\mathbf{s}_f	- vector of friction sources	
t	- time	[s]
u	- depth-averaged flow velocity in x-direction	[m/s]
v	- depth-averaged flow velocity in y-direction	[m/s]
x	- spatial dimension	[m]

y	- spatial dimension	[m]
z	- spatial dimension	[m]
z_B	- bottom elevation	[m]
A	- cell area	[m ²]
C	- Chézy coefficient	[m ^{1/2} /s]
Cr	- Courant number	[-]
D	- discretised equation	
\mathbf{D}	- coefficient derived for full implicit scheme	
\mathbf{F}	- vector of advective fluxes	
P	- partial differential equation	
R	- limiter function	[-]
S	- wave speed	[m/s]
T	- execution time	[s]
TV	- total variation	
δ	- discretisation error	
η	- slope of variables	
η_p	- parallel speed-up function	[-]
ν	- kinematic viscosity	[m ² /s]
ϕ	- value of a reconstructed variable at an edge	
ρ	- density	[kg/m ³]
τ_{Bx}	- bed shear stress in x-direction	[N/m ²]
τ_{By}	- bed shear stress in y-direction	[N/m ²]
Δs	- characteristic cell length	[m]

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	-	Meaning
API	-	Application programming interface
AVX	-	Advanced vector extensions
C	-	General purpose programming language
C++	-	Extension to the programming language C
CCFVM	-	Cell-centered Finite-Volume-Method
CFD	-	Computational fluid dynamics
CPU	-	Central processing unit
ENO	-	Essentially non-oscillatory
FDM	-	Finite-Difference-Method
FEM	-	Finite-Element-Method
FVM	-	Finite-Volume-Method
GNU	-	"GNU's not Unix!", collection of free software
gcc	-	GNU compiler collection
HLL	-	Harten-Lax-van Leer Riemann solver
HLLC	-	Harten-Lax-van Leer-Contact Riemann solver
hms	-	Hydroinformatics modeling systems
hms-java	-	Java version of hms
hms++	-	C++ version of hms
I/O	-	Input/Output
L1	-	Level 1 cache memory
L2	-	Level 2 cache memory
L3	-	Level 3 cache memory
MIMD	-	Multiple instruction multiple data
MISD	-	Multiple instruction single data
MPI	-	Message passing interface
MPP	-	Massive parallel processing
NUMA	-	Non-uniform memory access
OMP	-	OpenMP

OpenMP	-	Open multi-processing
RAM	-	Random access memory
SIMD	-	Single instruction multiple data
SISD	-	Single instruction single data
SMP	-	Symmetric multiprocessing
SMT	-	Simultaneous multithreading
SRAM	-	Static random access memory
SSE	-	Streaming SIMD extensions
SWE	-	Shallow water equations
TVD	-	Total variation diminishing
UMA	-	Uniform memory access

1. Introduction

1.1. Motivation

Hazardous occurrences caused by hydrological events like flooding due to heavy rainfall have risen in recent years. A wide range of reasons can be given for this development, amongst them is the human interference with nature (Rainey et al., 2021). An increase in surface sealing, the introduction of drainage systems in urban areas and restructuring of natural water bodies has altering effects on the hydrological cycle. Missing green areas and other nonexistent natural retention opportunities reduce evapotranspiration and infiltration and lead to a higher surface runoff after rainfall (Konrad, 2003). In consequence, this raises the risk of inundations due to heavy precipitation events, which in turn can lead to severe economic damage and even loss of human lives (Loster, 1999). One example of such an event was the 2015 flooding at the French Riviera (dpa, 2015). Flash floods caused by torrential lead to the deaths of 17 people as well as massive amounts of damage caused to the infrastructure and properties in the area, the latter as seen in Fig. 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Aftermath of flash floods that occurred in Nizza, France in 2015 (Photograph: Valery Hache / AFP).

This is why the European Union passed the Flood Risk Management Directive in 2007, which advises flood protection on a communal level (European Parliament, 2007).

Flash floods and inundations, especially in urban areas, feature complex spatial and temporal characteristics, which is why they must be analysed and studied in order to understand their damage potential and to evaluate potential counter-measures. To assist the process of decision making, surface water flow models can be taken into consideration, as they may offer critical temporal and spatial information about the flow field of potential floods.

Many prominent models, e.g. TELEMAC-2D (Hervouet & Ata, 2017), take a physical modeling approach by utilising the full two-dimensional shallow water equations (SWEs), a system of non-linear, hyperbolic partial differential equations obtained by combining the continuity equation with a special case of the Navier-Stokes equations. Analytical solutions to these equations only exist for a few special cases, hence a numerical approach is taken, often utilising a *Finite-Difference* (FDM), a *Finite-Element* (FEM) or a *Finite-Volume-Method* (FVM). The latter is widely spread in surface water flow modeling because of its inherent conservation properties and handling of shocks. Using the FVM, the domain of interest is discretised into a number of cells over which the solution is averaged, resulting in piecewise constant data for each cell. The SWEs are then solved in each cell for a specified time interval (Hinkelmann, 2006).

A rather complex part of the solution is the computation of fluxes between cells. A modern approach to do this would be to employ a Godunov-type method, e.g. a *Harten-Lax-van Leer-Contact* (HLLC) approximate Riemann solver (Toro et al., 1994) extended by a Total Variation Diminishing (TVD) high-order reconstruction scheme, like the *Monotonic Upstream-centered Scheme for Conservation Laws* (MUSCL) (Leer, 1979), flux-corrected-transport schemes (Boris & Book, 1973) or essentially non-oscillatory (ENO) schemes (Harten et al., 1997). These methods may feature a lot of computational steps and conditional branches. This is why the technological progress in computational and graphical processing units of recent years proved to be beneficial in running surface water flow simulations, as computation times were decreased drastically (Ginting, 2019). But with increasing computing power, new opportunities and challenges arise. Since surface water systems are multiscale systems, the spectrum for space and time scales is vast. Domains may range from micrometres to a hundred kilometres, while simulation times can range from milliseconds to multiple days (Hinkelmann, 2006). On the one hand, the advent of better hardware gave rise to large scale simulations with a substantial number of cells and long real-time computation times, e.g. dam-breaks (Ginting, 2019), on the other hand, decision makers need forecastings as part of the disaster management,

therefore requiring smaller and faster simulations (Özgen, 2017). In order to achieve reasonable computation times for large scale scenarios and to facilitate quick results for smaller simulations, an efficient use of software and hardware is necessary.

1.2. Purpose

Hydroinformatics Modeling System (referenced as `hms-java` throughout this work), developed at the Chair of Water Resources Management and Modeling of Hydrosystems, Technische Universität Berlin, is a software framework that is capable of simulating physical processes in the context of water and environmental related problems, ranging from surface water flow and transport to sediment transport. As these processes may interact with each other, `hms-java` encapsulates them in independent components, which can be employed in singular fashion or in conjunction with one another to allow for more complex simulations. Since `hms-java` is developed in the Java programming language and its focus lies on the aforementioned flexibility, extendibility and portability, it allows for rapid prototyping but accepts a trade-off in performance. An aspect which can be improved upon (Simons, 2020).

This is why Steffen et al. (2020) introduce a new open-source software framework for explicit FVM solvers called `hms++`, with a robust solver for the depth-averaged SWEs already implemented. Written in C++, its focus lies on improving the computational performance for surface water flow simulations through an efficient use of hardware and software. Strategies to achieve this range from utilizing parallel computing, vectorisation and optimising memory layout and access patterns.

The aim of this work is to verify and benchmark an explicit FVM solver on a structured grid, utilising a second-order accurate MUSCL reconstruction scheme in combination with an HLLC approximate Riemann solver for solve the SWEs. The new framework incorporates *Eigen* (Guennebaud, Jacob, et al., 2010), a C++ template library for linear algebra. Many subroutines and traversal strategies are parallelised via the use of preprocessor directives, provided by the shared-memory multiprocessing application programming interface (API) *OpenMP* (Dagum and Menon, 1998).

Computational steps are broken up into edge-based and cell-based calculations. Overall, five different traversal techniques for the edge-based flux calculation, along with one cell-based approach, are introduced. Traversal techniques are arranged in a way such that parallelisation locks and conditional branches, which are known to be poor for the performance, are avoided as much as possible (Intel Corporation, 2021).

Along with conceptual optimisations, the framework utilises auto-optimisations, provided

by the *GNU Compiler Collection*.

1.3. Related literature

There are many strategies to achieve a more efficient use of software and hardware when running surface water flow simulations. These range from modifying numerical schemes, to utilizing different forms of parallel computing, and optimising memory access in regard to the memory hierarchy.

Özgen (2017) developed numerical schemes to account for high-resolution topographic data produced by modern survey technology. This data is an important factor in urban surface water simulations since small features like pavements can have a large impact on flow field characteristics. Instead of explicitly discretizing small topographic features, by employing a substantial amount of cells, they are accounted for through an artificial friction coefficient or through porosity-based parameters. A reduction of up to three orders of magnitude in simulation wall-time could be achieved if the developed models were used.

To accelerate performance in a more hardware-oriented way, one may utilise parallel programming techniques by incorporating shared-memory multithreading interfaces like OpenMP or the message passing standard *MPI* for distributed-memory systems (Message Passing Interface Forum, 1994). This way, modern computer architectures with their multiple processors can be utilised to speed up the numerical computations. To further exploit the hardware of large compute clusters, a hybrid of the two mentioned interfaces can be used in which the problem is decomposed into a number of processes that are assigned to compute nodes, communicating with each other via *MPI*. On these nodes, the problem is solved in parallel via OpenMP or a similar standard. Such a hybrid model was developed in Ceder (2015) in order to solve the three-dimensional Burger's equation via a Finite-Difference-Method.

hms-java exploits modern architectures to some extent by enabling parallel computing through the built-in multithreading capabilities of Java. This way, all available CPU cores of a symmetric multiprocessing system can be used to speed up the performance. In a case study, a good parallel efficiency for up to 16 cores was obtained (Simons, 2020). But parallel simulations are susceptible to load imbalances, negatively impacting performance. During inundations, a common occurrence are wet-dry phenomena, with wet cells demanding significantly more computation time than dry ones, leading to an imbalanced workload for utilised threads/nodes. Ginting (2019) proposed *weighted-dynamic load balancing*, a suitable strategy to avoid load imbalancing, leading to better parallel efficiency.

Ginting (2019) also made extensive use of vectorisation, which is another known avenue for optimising computing performance. If vectorisation is utilised, scalar operations inside a loop are not computed in a serial manner but in groups. This means, that a whole batch of scalar operations is computed at once through a single instruction (Intel Corporation, 2021). The auto-vectorisation of an HLLC solver code in Ginting (2019), utilising the SIMD instruction sets AVX, AVX2 and AVX-512 led to speed-ups of $5.5\times$, $4.5\times$ and $16.68\times$, respectively, when compared to a non-vectorised version, for a single utilised CPU core.

1.4. Scope

The mathematical and numerical foundations are discussed in Secs. 2 and 3, followed by an introduction to modern computer architecture in Sec. 4. Subsequently, the utilised libraries, data structures, the implementation of the numerical scheme as well as the traversal approaches are described in Sec. 5, followed by the verification of the implementation in Sec. 6. Afterwards, the parallel performance benchmark and performance metrics are explained in Sec. 7. Then, a preliminary study is carried out in Sec. 8, followed by the parallel performance investigations of the traversal patterns in Sec. 9 and, lastly, the performance comparison between `hms++` and `hms-java` in Sec. 10. The results of the investigations are analysed and discussed. A conclusive summary as well as an outlook and recommendations for future research are given in Sec. 11.

2. Governing equations

This section covers the mathematical principles of this work. First, the general form of the balance equation that is used to express the conservation laws for mass, momentum and energy, is described in Sec. 2.1. Then, the shallow water equations, which are used to model the physical process of surface water flow, are presented in Sec. 2.2.

2.1. General form of balance equation

Figure 2.1: Square Eulerian control volume, after Hinkelmann (2006), modified by the author.

Physical processes in fluid mechanics are represented by conservation laws for mass, momentum and energy. These processes include subsurface two-phase / multicomponent flow and transport as well as flow and transport processes in surface waters. Conservation laws can be viewed as balance equations for a preserved quantity in a fixed *Eulerian* control volume, resulting in a system of differential equations. Euler introduced the control volume, illustrated in Fig. 2.1, as an approach to observe physical quantities inside of a fixed volume of arbitrary size at a steady state, instead of assigning them to a specific particle that flows through the space-time-continuum. This way, a field-like observation of physical quantities at a specific point in time is possible. To observe these

physical quantities, the general form of the balance equation is used:

$$\int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{q}}{\partial t} + \text{div}(\mathbf{f} + \mathbf{g}) - \mathbf{s} \right) d\Omega = 0 \quad (2.1)$$

Eq. 2.1 implies that the volume integral of the temporal change of conserved variables plus the spatial derivatives of their fluxes minus sources and sinks inside the control volume Ω is zero. Since the numerical schemes in this work are based on the Finite-Volume-Method, the *Green-Gauss Integral theorem* must be applied to the volume integral of the flux derivatives to transform them into a surface integral:

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \mathbf{q}}{\partial t} d\Omega + \oint_{\Gamma} (\mathbf{f}n_x + \mathbf{g}n_y) d\Gamma - \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{s} d\Omega = 0 \quad (2.2)$$

with Ω denoting the control volume and Γ its surface. \mathbf{q} denotes the vector of conserved state variables, \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{g} denote the advective fluxes in x- and y-direction, n_x and n_y are components of the normal vector $\mathbf{n} = (n_x, n_y)^T$ and \mathbf{s} stands for a vector of sources and/or sinks (Hinkelmann, 2006).

2.2. Shallow water equations

2.2.1. Physical background

The SWEs are part of surface water model concepts that exist under the umbrella term *far-field problems* in which dominant processes occur on large scales in relation to their counterpart, the *near-field problems*. The former feature processes found in the sea and coastal waters or in inland waters like rivers or estuaries. Within *far-field problems*, an important distinction between model concepts is made based on the length of occurring waves and their contextual time scales. Surface water systems that feature short waves often use *wave models* while long waves are featured in *flow models*. The difference between these waves is their ratio of wave length to water depth. A wave is categorised as a long wave if its length is $20\times$ larger than the water depth, whereas short waves feature smaller ratios. This also leads to these surface waters being characterised as *shallow* since the horizontal dimensions are much larger than the vertical one. This allows for the utilisation of the *shallow-water equations* (Hinkelmann, 2006).

2.2.2. Mathematical background

The two-dimensional depth-averaged SWEs are obtained by combining the continuity equation for mass balance with a special case of the Navier-Stokes equations for the momentum balance as well as making further simplifications. The density is constant and can be neglected since the fluid is assumed to be incompressible. Since the horizontal dimensions of flow models are in general much larger than the vertical dimension, including relatively high horizontal flow velocities and a high wave-length-to-water-depth-ratio, further assumptions can be made. These include a hydrostatic pressure distribution and a negligible vertical flow velocity.

Assuming a free surface, the equations are then integrated over the water depth to obtain the two-dimensional depth-averaged SWEs (described in detail in Malcherek (2004)):

$$\mathbf{q} = \begin{bmatrix} d \\ ud \\ vd \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{f} = \begin{bmatrix} ud \\ uud + \frac{1}{2}gd^2 \\ uvd \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{g} = \begin{bmatrix} vd \\ vud \\ vvd + \frac{1}{2}gd^2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2.3)$$

$$\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{s}_m + \mathbf{s}_B + \mathbf{s}_f$$

with

$$\mathbf{s}_m = \begin{bmatrix} r \\ f_x \\ f_y \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{s}_B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ gd \frac{\partial z_B}{\partial x} \\ gd \frac{\partial z_B}{\partial y} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{s}_f = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{\tau_{Bx}}{\rho} \\ \frac{\tau_{By}}{\rho} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.4)$$

The formulation fulfills the *C-Property* and is therefore a *well-balanced* form of the equations: If the equations are well-balanced, a motionless water body will be preserved on an uneven bed, as long as no forces act on it (Liang & Marche, 2009).

If the first row of components of Eq. (2.3) is put in Eq. (2.2), the continuity equation, describing the mass balance, is obtained. The second and third row lead to the momentum balance equation in x- and y-direction, respectively.

The vector \mathbf{q} is the storage vector, with d denoting the water depth and u and v denoting

 Figure 2.2: Water elevation h , water depth d and bottom elevation z_B .

the depth-averaged flow velocity in x- and y-direction. Flow velocities multiplied with the water depth result in the specific discharges ud in x-direction and vd in y-direction. Vectors \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{g} are flux vectors in x- and y-direction. The first components consider the mass flux. The advective momentum fluxes in x- and y-direction are given by uud, uvd and vud, vvd . Momentum is also transported due to differences in hydrostatic pressure, expressed by the term $\frac{1}{2}gd^2$. If viscous fluxes are to be taken into account, the second and third components of \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{g} are appended by $-\nu\frac{\partial ud}{\partial x}$, $-\nu\frac{\partial vd}{\partial x}$ and $-\nu\frac{\partial ud}{\partial y}$, $-\nu\frac{\partial vd}{\partial y}$, respectively. Viscous terms consist of the kinematic viscosity ν multiplied with the gradient of the specific discharge. The kinematic viscosity can serve as a way to introduce turbulence models into the equation, e.g. *Prandtl's mixing length model*. Turbulence and diffusive fluxes and therefore viscous fluxes are neglected in this work.

The sources/sinks in the vector \mathbf{s} comprise the mass and external momentum sources in \mathbf{s}_m , the slope source terms \mathbf{s}_B and the friction source terms \mathbf{s}_f . Mass sources or sinks are denoted by r , often used to consider an influx of mass by precipitation or a decrease through infiltration. The friction momentum source is expressed by $\frac{\tau_{Bx}}{\rho}$ in x-direction and $\frac{\tau_{By}}{\rho}$ in y-direction, with τ_B denoting the bed shear stress and ρ standing for the fluid density. *Chézy's* formula can be utilised to calculate the friction source term:

$$\frac{\tau_{Bx}}{\rho} = \frac{g}{C^2} u|\mathbf{v}| \quad (2.5)$$

$$\frac{\tau_{By}}{\rho} = \frac{g}{C^2} v|\mathbf{v}| \quad (2.6)$$

C can either be a constant to apply the original Chézy's law or can be used to introduce other approaches. In this work, an approach after Gauckler-Manning-Strickler is utilised:

$$C = \frac{d^{1/6}}{n} \quad (2.7)$$

with n denoting the Manning roughness coefficient. A Strickler roughness coefficient k_{Str}

can also be used:

$$k_{Str} = \frac{1}{n}. \quad (2.8)$$

The slope source term is denoted by $gd\frac{\partial z_B}{\partial x}$ and $gd\frac{\partial z_B}{\partial y}$ for the x- and y-direction, respectively, with z_B denoting the bottom elevation (Simons, 2020). The relation between water elevation, water depth and bottom elevation can be observed in Fig. 2.2, with the water elevation computed as

$$h = z_B + d. \quad (2.9)$$

External forces on the momentum balance, e.g. wind shear or Coriolis forces, is taken into account by f_x, f_y .

Classification of conservation laws In order to apply some of the numerical methods described in section 3.3, the mathematical properties of the system of conservation laws have to be analysed. A system of non-linear partial differential equations can be classified as either elliptic, parabolic or hyperbolic by determining the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the Jacobian matrix. The two-dimensional depth-averaged SWEs have two Jacobian matrices, one for each direction, with each having three real eigenvalues and three independent eigenvectors. This classifies the system as hyperbolic. Such a system allows the propagation of discontinuities, which in fluid simulations often occur in the form of shock waves (LeVeque, 2002). This property is an important requirement to treat the advective flux as a Riemann problem, further explained in section 3.3.2.

3. Numerical model concepts

The depth-averaged SWEs are a set of partial differential equations which can be solved analytically only for a few specific cases. This is why most models use numerical methods to approximate the solution, which requires a temporal and spatial discretisation of the derivatives in the balance equations. In general, a discretisation method must be *consistent*, *convergent* and *stable*. The first requirement describes how the difference between the partial differential equation P and the discretised equation D tends to zero for ever decreasing time step and cell sizes. The difference between the equations is called the discretisation error δ :

$$\delta = \lim_{\Delta t, \Delta x \rightarrow 0} |P - D| = 0 \quad (3.1)$$

The discretised equation has an order of consistency, which serves as a measure of accuracy, further explained in Sec. 3.1. Additionally, convergence is required. For decreasing time step and cell size the solution of D should converge to the actual solution given by P . Unfortunately, this is not always possible since the exact solution is rarely known. In this case the solution given by D can be observed for a fixed point in time or place. If D is converging to a specific value for decreasing time step and cell sizes, the requirement is fulfilled. Discretisation methods have to be stable, i.e. oscillations in the numerical solution must not increase. To keep small disruptions from becoming increasingly larger, stabilisation measures are employed. A common practice is the addition of numerical diffusion, although this often smears the solution over multiple cells and therefore results in a loss of accuracy (Hinkelmann, 2006).

In this work, the temporal derivative of the SWEs is discretised by employing a *Forward-Euler Method*, described in Sec. 3.1. The spatial terms are discretised via a *Cell-Centered Finite-Volume Method*, approximating the solution with piecewise constant data, more specifically cell averages, detailed in Sec. 3.2. Two different approaches to determine the flux over an edge are implemented. The first is a simple Fully-Upwind Method and the second is the *Harten-Lax-van Leer-Contact* solver, an approximate Riemann solver introduced in Toro et al. (1994), see Sec. 3.3 for more details. The modern high-resolution shock-capturing method *Monotonic Upwind-centered Scheme for Conservation Laws* (MUSCL) is implemented and further described in Sec. 3.3.5. In Sec. 3.5 the treatment of the bed friction term is described, which utilises a splitting point-implicit method. The slope source term is formulated so that a well balanced scheme is obtained, as seen in Sec. 3.4.

Solving the depth-averaged shallow-water equations numerically requires initial values for the conserved variables in the field. Additionally, it must be known how the numerical model handles flux calculations concerning cells and edges located at the boundary of the domain. Approaches that specify what should happen at boundaries are called boundary conditions, further explained in Sec. 3.6.

3.1. Temporal discretisation

The first term of Eq. (2.2) accounts for the temporal change of a conserved variable. This temporal derivative is discretised by utilising a *Taylor-series expansion*:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{q}}{\partial t} = \frac{\mathbf{q}^{n+1} - \mathbf{q}^n}{\Delta t} - \underbrace{\left(\frac{\Delta t}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{q}}{\partial t^2} + \frac{\Delta t^2}{6} \frac{\partial^3 \mathbf{q}}{\partial t^3} + \frac{\Delta t^3}{24} \frac{\partial^4 \mathbf{q}}{\partial t^4} \right)}_{\text{discretisation error}} - O(\Delta t^5) \quad (3.2)$$

The terms of higher order are skipped to obtain the *Forward-Euler Method*:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{q}}{\partial t} \approx \frac{\mathbf{q}^{n+1} - \mathbf{q}^n}{\Delta t} \quad (3.3)$$

n and $n + 1$ stand for the old and new time level, respectively. The time step is denoted by Δt . The discretisation error is made up of higher terms and describes the consistency of the method. The Forward-Euler Method is of first order of consistency, indicated by the minimal power of the time step in the discretisation error.

It is categorised as an *explicit one-step method*, i.e. the calculation only takes one value of the old time level into account. So called *multi-step methods* consider the values of more time levels, but require more steps to determine the solution. The word *explicit* refers to the fact that the computation of conserved variables on the new time level \mathbf{q}^{n+1} is solely dependent on the values of the old time level, which are already known. This results in a low computational effort per time step when compared to *implicit* methods in which the values of the new time level depend on each other leading to a system of equations that has to be solved for each time step computation.

A downside of explicit methods is the constraint on the time step size. Spatially, the unknown variables of a cell on the new time level are depending on values from directly neighbouring cells. This leads to a maximum propagation distance of one neighbouring cell. If the information propagates further, the simulation will become unstable. To prevent this, the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) condition has to be fulfilled. The

condition is a ratio of the maximum propagation distance and the cell distance:

$$Cr = \frac{(|\mathbf{v}| + \sqrt{gd})\Delta t}{\Delta s} \leq 1 \quad (3.4)$$

with Cr denoting the *Courant* number. The maximum propagation velocity consists of the absolute value of the flow velocity and the wave, which is the square root of the gravity multiplied with the water depth, denoted by d . The cell distance, denoted by Δs , is a characteristic length, that can be computed in different ways. In this work, the diameter of the incircle of the triangular cell was chosen. For rectangular cells, this equates to the shorter side of the rectangle:

$$\Delta s = \frac{4A}{C} \quad (3.5)$$

with C denoting the cell circumference.

If a time step size is not given, the Courant number can be used to compute it adaptively for each iteration of the time marching algorithm. Eq. (3.4) is rearranged to

$$\Delta t = \frac{Cr \Delta s}{(|\mathbf{v}| + \sqrt{gd})}. \quad (3.6)$$

In order to prevent oscillations, the Courant condition has to be fulfilled in every cell, which is achieved by choosing the smallest time step in the field for all cells (Hinkelmann, 2006).

3.2. Spatial discretisation

3.2.1. Computational domain

Finite-Volume-Methods require the subdivision of the computational domain into control volumes of finite sizes. The resulting structure is called grid or mesh, an often but not necessarily seamless arrangement of control volumes, also called cells, discretising the domain of interest. The cell size is crucial for accuracy and performance and must be given special care when conceptualising a surface water model. If a topographical feature is of sub-cell size, its influence on the flow field gets neglected as it is not discretised explicitly. A possible solution is a more detailed discretisation by choosing a higher spatial resolution, therefore increasing the cell count substantially, which in turn has an impact on computing performance. A modeler must know her or his way around the accuracy/performance trade-off. Meshes can be constructed in a structured or unstructured manner. Using

triangular cells results in an unstructured mesh, enabling the reproduction of complex boundaries and inner structures. While `hms++` supports unstructured meshes, this work focuses solely on structured meshes, comprising quadrilateral cells for which further classification is introduced, described in detail in Sec. 5.2.1. The arrangement of cells is the basis for data storage and therefore memory layout, rendering the indexing of said cells, as well as their edges, a crucial part in terms of performance improvements. Indexing strategies are explained in detail in Sec. 5.2.2.

Another name for the Finite-Volume-Method applied to a structured mesh is *Integral-Finite-Difference-Method* (Hinkelmann, 2006).

3.2.2. Cell-Centered Finite-Volume-Method

Figure 3.1: Different ways to construct a control volume for a Finite-Volume-Method (Hinkelmann, 2006).

In general, there are multiple ways to construct control volumes for a Finite-Volume-Method. If the *Node-Centered Finite-Volume-Method* is employed, a node or vertex of the mesh is used as centre point of a control volume, which can be constructed around the centre in two different ways, illustrated in Fig. 3.1b and 3.1c. In this work, the construction of control volumes is done via the *Cell-Centered Finite-Volume-Method*, which uses the element or cell as control volume, as seen in 3.1a, and evaluates a cell average for the solution determined at the cell centre, which results in piecewise constant approximations.

Finite-Volume-Methods are locally and therefore globally conservative, i.e. mass, momentum and energy are directly balanced between adjacent control volumes (Hinkelmann, 2006). Conservative schemes are known to be more accurate than non-conservative schemes if the flow involves shocks, which is common in free-surface flow (Toro, 2009). To serve as a basis for a Finite-Volume-Method, the general form of the balance equation

has to be formulated in a conservative way. Considering only the advective flux vector of the equation, the integration over the surface integral yields the product of the flux over an edge and its respective length summed up over all edges of the control volume:

$$\oint_{\Gamma} (\mathbf{f}n_x + \mathbf{g}n_y) d\Gamma = \sum_{k=1}^{n_B} ((\mathbf{f}_k n_{k_x} + \mathbf{g}_k n_{k_y}) l_k) \quad (3.7)$$

with k denoting the current edge and n_B denoting the number of edges of the cell. For a two-dimensional cell, the integration over the surface integral is equal to the multiplication with the length of the edge, denoted by l . The advective flux components may also be written as:

$$\mathbf{f}_k n_{k_x} + \mathbf{g}_k n_{k_y} = \mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_k} \mathbf{n}_k \quad (3.8)$$

The Eq. 3.8 is substituted into Eq. (3.7), followed by the substitution of the result and Eq. (3.3) into Eq. (2.2). The temporal derivative and source term of the resulting equation are integrated over the control volume, which yields:

$$\frac{\mathbf{q}^{n+1} - \mathbf{q}^n}{\Delta t} A + \sum_{k=1}^{n_B} (\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_k}^n \mathbf{n}_k l_k) - \mathbf{s}^n A = 0 \quad (3.9)$$

Analogously to the integral over the surface, the integral over the control volume is equal to the area of the cell, denoted by A . To solve Eq. (3.9) for the unknown variables on the new time level, it can be rewritten as:

$$\mathbf{q}^{n+1} = \mathbf{q}^n - \frac{\Delta t}{A} \sum_{k=1}^{n_B} (\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_k}^n \mathbf{n}_k l_k) + \Delta t \mathbf{s}^n \quad (3.10)$$

The obtained numerical method is a *semidiscrete method*, i.e. a Finite-Difference-Method is used to discretise the temporal term while a Finite-Volume-Method discretises the spatial component of the equations (Simons, 2020).

3.3. Advective flux term treatment

The advective flux is determined for each edge, however, since an edge interfaces two cells and the flux term is a function of the conserved variables of the interfacing cells, as seen in Eq. 3.11 for the edge $k = i + 1/2$, it is not clearly defined which information is

taken into account when computing the flux:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_k} = f(\mathbf{q}_i, \mathbf{q}_{i+1}) \quad (3.11)$$

Eq. 3.11 can be solved by many different methods and approaches, all varying in their accuracy, robustness, complexity and computational effort. Two of these approaches are implemented in `hms++`. The first is the *Fully Upwind Method*, a simple and robust approach that uses a one-sided approximation for the flux, described in detail in Sec. 3.3.1. The second method implemented is an approximate HLLC solver, based on Godunov's scheme, which equates the flux computation at an edge with solving a local Riemann problem, detailed in Sec. 3.3.3. In order to fully comprehend the approximate solver, a brief explanation of the exact Riemann solution is given in Sec. 3.3.2.

3.3.1. Fully Upwind Method

The Fully Upwind Method determines the advective flux by splitting each component of the flux vectors of Eq. 2.3 into its transporting variable, represented by the flow velocity u , and its transported variable, expressed by the conserved variables \mathbf{q} , as well as into the hydrostatic pressure term \mathbf{p} , exemplarily shown in Eq. 3.12 for the flux vector \mathbf{f} :

$$\mathbf{f} = \begin{bmatrix} ud \\ uud + \frac{1}{2}gd^2 \\ uvd \end{bmatrix} = u \begin{bmatrix} d \\ ud \\ vd \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}gd^2 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = u\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{p} \quad (3.12)$$

Subsequently, mean transporting velocity between the interfacing cells is determined as

$$u_{i+1/2} = \frac{u_i + u_{i+1}}{2} \quad (3.13)$$

A one-sided approach is used to determine the advective flux, i.e. the direction of the computed mean transporting velocity dictates if the upstream or downstream cell provides the conserved variables involved in the advective flux computation. This can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_{i+1/2}} = \begin{cases} u_{i+1/2}\mathbf{q}_i + \mathbf{p} & \text{if } u_{i+1/2} \geq 0 \\ u_{i+1/2}\mathbf{q}_{i+1} + \mathbf{p} & \text{if } u_{i+1/2} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.14)$$

The hydrostatic pressure component \mathbf{p} is unaffected by the upwinding of the advective

flux. It is computed for the cells on either side of the edge, incorporating the locally residing water depth d_{cell} and an adjusted pressure height h_p :

$$h_p = \begin{cases} 0.5 \cdot (h_i + h_{i+1}) & \text{if } d_i, d_{i+1} \geq d_{\min} \text{ or } d_i, d_{i+1} < d_{\min} \\ 0.5 \cdot (h_i + \min(h_i, z_{i+1})) & \text{if } d_i \geq d_{\min} \text{ and } d_{i+1} < d_{\min} \\ 0.5 \cdot (h_{i+1} + \min(h_{i+1}, z_i)) & \text{if } d_{i+1} \geq d_{\min} \text{ and } d_i < d_{\min} \end{cases} \quad (3.15)$$

$$\mathbf{p} = g d_{\text{cell}} h_p \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.16)$$

The Fully Upwind Method is a simple and robust approach that stays stable if the CFL-condition in Eq. 3.4 is fulfilled and delivers respectable results for smooth solutions. However, the method is not suitable to capture discontinuities like shock waves as it introduces numerical diffusion and spurious oscillations, often leading to poor agreement with exact solutions and delivering inaccurate results (Simons, 2020).

3.3.2. Godunov's scheme

Figure 3.2: Godunov's scheme applied to finite volumes in a 1D example (Simons, 2020).

A more sophisticated method to treat the advective flux is Godunov's scheme (Godunov & Bohachevsky, 1959). The scheme takes advantage of the mathematical properties of the SWEs and the discretised solution profile, provided by the Finite-Volume-Method.

The scheme essentially solves a Riemann problem for a hyperbolic conservation law. This is applicable to the SWEs, since they are a system of non-linear hyperbolic partial differential equations. In combination with the piecewise constant distribution of data for the conserved variables in each cell, which leads to discontinuities between interfacing cells, a local Riemann problem can be formulated for each edge, illustrated in Fig. 3.2. Godunov's scheme then determines the flux between cells by solving the local Riemann problem at each edge, either exactly or approximately. This procedure is encapsulated in the *REA-algorithm* (reconstruct-evolve-average), a three-step algorithm to determine the advective flux, proposed by LeVeque (2002):

Reconstruct: Determine the left and right values of the Riemann problem. Choosing midpoint values of interfacing cells, i.e. the values given by the piecewise constant data, as left and right edge values, respectively, results in a first-order accurate reconstruction. Accuracy can be improved by employing modern higher-order reconstruction methods, described in section 3.3.5. A hydrostatic reconstruction of water depths is necessary if variations in bottom topography are to be taken into account, detailed in section 3.3.4

Evolve: Determine the advective flux by solving the local Riemann problem, which is based on the reconstructed values. In this work, the Riemann problem is solved approximately by utilising an HLLC solver, described in section 3.3.3. A brief description of the exact solution to the Riemann problem is given in the paragraphs in this section.

Average: Obtain new average values for the cells by updating conserved variables of the interfacing cells with the sum of the fluxes multiplied with the respective edge length, time step and normal vector.

Riemann problem The Riemann problem is referring to an initial value problem for hyperbolic partial differential equations involving a single discontinuity in its initial data (LeVeque, 2002), as it can be seen in Fig. 3.3a. Initial Riemann data represents piecewise constant states left and right of the discontinuity and is expressed as

$$\mathbf{q}(x,0) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{q}_l & \text{if } x < 0 \\ \mathbf{q}_r & \text{if } x > 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.17)$$

Since Riemann problems are inherently one-dimensional, they are formulated perpendicular to an edge, which requires the transformation of the two-dimensional flow velocity direction into normal and tangential direction of the respective edge.

Figure 3.3: Riemann problem (Simons (2020), modified by the author).

Exact solution to the Riemann problem Hyperbolic systems are known to allow the propagation of a discontinuity, like the one described in Eq. (3.17). Obtaining information on the behavior of the propagation is necessary in order to determine the conserved variables that are required for the computation of the flux between two interfacing cells. With the evolution in time, a set of waves will propagate through the system, starting at the discontinuity, illustrated in Fig. 3.3b. The number of waves is equal to the number of equations in the system and since the one-dimensional SWEs consist of two equations, there will be two waves propagating from the discontinuity. Between these waves a new intermediate state emerges. The conserved variables in the intermediate state \mathbf{q}_m are unknown and must be determined. This is done by constructing the functions f_l , connecting the left and intermediate state, and f_r , connecting right state with the intermediate state. Since the propagating waves can either be rarefaction or shock waves, the construction of these functions is based on different relations.

If the left or right state is connected with the intermediate state via a shock wave, then the connecting function is based on the *Rankine-Hugoniot condition*. The connecting function over rarefaction waves can be constructed using the *Riemann invariants*. But these solutions are only weak solutions to the Riemann problem. The physically correct solution can be determined via the *Lax Entropy Condition*. A more detailed derivation of the functions and information on the three mentioned relations can be found in LeVeque (2002). These three relations can be combined in a general Riemann solver for the SWEs with

$$f_l = \begin{cases} u_l + 2(\sqrt{gd_l} - \sqrt{gd_m}) & \text{if } d_m < d_l \text{ (left wave is raref. wave)} \\ u_l - (d_m - d_l)\sqrt{\frac{g}{2}\left(\frac{1}{d_m} + \frac{1}{d_l}\right)} & \text{if } d_m > d_l \text{ (left wave is shock wave)} \end{cases} \quad (3.18)$$

and with

$$f_r = \begin{cases} u_r - 2(\sqrt{gd_r} - \sqrt{gd_m}) & \text{if } d_m < d_r \text{ (right wave is raref. wave)} \\ u_r + (d_m - d_l)\sqrt{\frac{g}{2}\left(\frac{1}{d_m} + \frac{1}{d_r}\right)} & \text{if } d_m > d_r \text{ (right wave is shock wave)} \end{cases} \quad (3.19)$$

with d_l , u_l and d_r , u_r denoting the water depth and normal flow velocity in the left and right state respectively. Both functions return a value for u_m , the normal flow velocity in the intermediate state. This allows for equating Eq. (3.18) and Eq. (3.19):

$$0 = f_l(d_m) - f_r(d_m) \quad (3.20)$$

Now, the intermediate water depth d_m , the only unknown in Eq. 3.20, can be determined by rearranging Eq. (3.20) and solving it iteratively via a Newton-Raphson method. When d_m is obtained, u_m is computed via:

$$u_m = \frac{1}{2}(f_r(d_m) + f_l(d_m)) \quad (3.21)$$

With this information it is easy to sample an exact solution for any point in space-time. Further explanations on how this is done for different wave combinations is described in Simons (2020).

3.3.3. Approximate Riemann solver

The exact solution to the Riemann problem consists of a wealth of information that exceeds what is actually required for practical computations. The exact solution can be sampled at any point in space-time, although only the conserved variables at $x/t = 0$ need to be determined for the flux computation. Additionally, the exact solution comes with a high computational cost, since the Newton-Raphson iteration scheme is used on every edge for each time step. For these reasons, so called *approximate Riemann solvers* have been developed. The application of these solvers in *Godunov-type* methods is much cheaper than exact Riemann solvers, while at the same time achieving highly accurate results, even rivaling those of the exact solution, especially in combination with high-resolution schemes (LeVeque, 2002).

In `hms++`, the prominent *Harten-Lax-van Leer-Contact* (HLLC) Riemann solver is implemented (Toro et al., 1994). The HLLC solver is an approximate Riemann solver that serves as an extension to the *Harten-Lax-van Leer* (HLL) Riemann solver (Harten et al., 1983). The latter approximates the Riemann solution with two waves resulting in a

constant intermediate state that emerges between the left and right fixed state. This is a correct solution for a system of two equations, e.g. the one-dimensional SWEs, yet for two-dimensional problems this introduces a strong numerical diffusion, as the HLL Riemann solver does not take the change of the tangential momentum in the intermediate state into account.

Figure 3.4: Approximated solution structure of the HLLC solver (Simons (2020), modified by the author).

The HLLC Riemann solver modifies the HLL Riemann solver in that it introduces a third wave separating the intermediate state into two states, illustrated in Fig. 3.4. The third wave is called contact discontinuity or shear wave.

With the help of wave speed estimations, the flux in x-direction at an edge k that is part of a structured mesh with rectangular cells is determined as

$$\mathbf{f}_k^{\text{hllc}} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{f}_l & \text{if } S_l > 0 \\ \mathbf{f}_{ml} & \text{if } S_l \leq 0 \leq S_m \\ \mathbf{f}_{mr} & \text{if } S_m \leq 0 \leq S_r \\ \mathbf{f}_r & \text{if } S_r \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.22)$$

with S_l and S_r denoting the wave speed estimations for the waves connecting the left state with the left intermediate state, and right state with the right intermediate state, respectively. S_m stands for the estimated propagation velocity of the shear wave.

In order to determine the correct flux, the wave speeds have to be estimated beforehand. The left and right celerities are approximations of rarefaction waves and can be expressed

as

$$S_l = \begin{cases} u_r - 2c_{w,r} & \text{if } d_l = 0 \\ \min(u_l - c_{w,l}, u_m - c_{w,m}) & \text{if } d_l > 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.23)$$

$$S_r = \begin{cases} u_l + 2c_{w,l} & \text{if } d_r = 0 \\ \max(u_r + c_{w,r}, u_m + c_{w,m}) & \text{if } d_r > 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.24)$$

with $c_{w,l}$ and $c_{w,r}$ denoting the wave speeds in the left and right state, respectively, and $c_{w,m}$ representing an estimated wave speed in the intermediate region:

$$\begin{aligned} c_{w,l} &= \sqrt{gd_l} \\ c_{w,r} &= \sqrt{gd_r} \\ c_{w,m} &= \sqrt{gd_m} \end{aligned} \quad (3.25)$$

The estimated wave speed in the intermediate state is based on an estimated water depth, which is obtained via:

$$d_m = \frac{1}{g} \left(\frac{1}{2}(c_{w,l} + c_{w,r}) + \frac{1}{4}(u_l - u_r) \right)^2 \quad (3.26)$$

Eqs. 3.23 and 3.24 require estimations of the flow velocity in normal direction in the intermediate state, which is given by:

$$u_m = \frac{1}{2}(u_l + u_r) + c_{w,l} - c_{w,r} \quad (3.27)$$

The estimated celerity of the shear wave is computed by:

$$S_m = \frac{S_l d_r (u_r - S_r) - S_r d_l (u_l - S_l)}{d_r (u_r - S_r) - d_l (u_l - S_l)} \quad (3.28)$$

Eq. (3.22) states that if the wave speed of the left wave is estimated to be greater than zero, then the flux determination is based on the conserved variables of the left state, which in the Finite-Volume framework would be the left cell. Analogously, if the wave speed estimation of the right wave is below zero, the computation solely relies on the

right state, therefore the right cell:

$$\mathbf{f}_l = \begin{bmatrix} u_l d_l \\ u_l^2 d_l + \frac{1}{2} g d_l^2 \\ u_l v_l d_l \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{f}_r = \begin{bmatrix} u_r d_r \\ u_r^2 d_r + \frac{1}{2} g d_r^2 \\ u_r v_r d_r \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.29)$$

The flux computation is based on the intermediate state, when the left wave has a negative propagation speed and the right wave has a positive one. It is given by:

$$\mathbf{f}_m = \frac{S_r \mathbf{f}_l - S_l \mathbf{f}_r + S_r S_l (\mathbf{q}_r - \mathbf{q}_l)}{S_r - S_l} \quad (3.30)$$

The HLLC Riemann solver introduces a shear wave, separating the intermediate state over which the mass flux and momentum flux in normal direction stay constant, although there is jump occurring in the momentum flux in tangential direction. Therefore, the flux computation for the intermediate state is separated into a left and right state (Liang et al., 2004):

$$\mathbf{f}_{ml} = \begin{bmatrix} f_{m,1} \\ f_{m,2} \\ v_l f_{m,1} \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{f}_{mr} = \begin{bmatrix} f_{m,1} \\ f_{m,2} \\ v_r f_{m,1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.31)$$

$f_{m,1}$ and $f_{m,2}$ are the first and second components of \mathbf{f}_m , which is obtained by solving Eq. 3.29.

3.3.4. Bottom topography variations treatment

Neither the exact solution to the Riemann problem in section 3.3.2 nor the approximate Riemann solver in section 3.3.3 take changes in bottom topography into account and they are therefore only applicable to neighbouring cells that share the same bed elevation. In order to consider changes in bed elevation in the computation, the water depths of the left and right cells have to be hydrostatically reconstructed at the edge (Hou et al., 2013). This is done by computing a bed elevation for the discontinuity at edge k :

$$z_{B,k} = \max(z_{B,l}, z_{B,r}) \quad (3.32)$$

Now the left and right water depths are reconstructed with respect to the new bottom

elevation:

$$d_r = \max(0, h_r - z_{B,k}) \quad (3.33)$$

$$d_l = \max(0, h_l - z_{B,k})$$

Eq. (3.33) derives the water depths used for the solution of the Riemann problem in sections 3.3.2 and 3.3.3. The Riemann problem can now be solved as usual, with an even bed elevation shared by both states. The implemented hydrostatic reconstruction method is quite robust as it can manage wet and dry fronts. In case of the former, the left and right water depths are higher than the difference in bottom elevation, simply resulting in a reconstruction of the water depth in the cell with the lower bottom elevation, as seen in Fig. 3.5. If the variation in bottom topography is higher than the water depth in the lower positioned cell, then this cell is artificially dried. If in this case the cell that has the higher ground is physically dry, there will be no flow whatsoever between the interfacing cells, illustrated in Fig. 3.6.

Figure 3.5: Hydrostatic reconstruction at an interface with higher water depths than the difference of bottom elevations (Simons, 2020).

However this form of reconstruction has disadvantages when it comes to shallow water flow with continuously small water depths on inclined bottom topography, also called sheet-like flow. In this scenario, the difference in bottom elevation can be continuously higher than the water depth in the lower cell, leading to the artificial drying of a cell on the incline for each computation in that context. This will lead to inaccurate results for the incline, resulting in a wrong flow field. If a higher-order reconstruction scheme is utilised, the second neighbours, which are neighbour cells to the cells that interface at a given edge, are involved in the reconstruction, leading to a linear approximation, which allows for an inclined free surface and bottom topography, therefore better representing

Figure 3.6: Hydrostatic reconstruction at a wet and dry interface (Simons, 2020).

(c) Hydrostatic reconstruction with higher-order accurate scheme.

Figure 3.7: Hydrostatic reconstruction of sheet-like flow (Simons, 2020).

the sheet-like flow on the incline, viewed in Fig. 3.7 (Simons, 2020).

3.3.5. High-resolution scheme

The numerical methods presented in section 3.3.1 to 3.3.3 are spatially first-order accurate. Toro (2009) states that first-order methods lack the accuracy to be of any practical interest, as these methods, although monotonous and robust, introduce numerical diffusion. Methods of higher order, like the *Central Method* or the *Lax-Wendroff Method*, prove to be more accurate for smooth solutions, however the monotonicity of the solution is amiss, as they introduce spurious oscillations, especially at discontinuities. This lead to Godunov's theorem stating that there are no linear numerical schemes of second or higher solving partial differential equations that are monotone. *High-resolution* schemes were developed to circumvent Godunov's theorem. In order to be described as having high-resolution, a scheme must be second order or higher in smooth parts of the solution, but must not produce spurious oscillations. The scheme must also resolve discontinuities on less cells than first-order methods (Harten, 1983).

An approach that satisfies these properties is the monotonic upwind-centered scheme for conservation laws (MUSCL) approach for non-linear conservation laws, introduced in Leer (1979). The MUSCL approach extends the Godunov scheme to achieve a higher order of spatial accuracy by modifying the first step of the REA-algorithm. Instead of using the piecewise constant data distribution, provided by the finite-volume framework, the MUSCL approach reconstructs the data in piecewise linear fashion. Additionally, the method is a total variation diminishing scheme, i.e. oscillations are monitored so that they do not increase with time. This information is the basis for slope limiter methods, that will limit the slope in higher-order computations so that no over- or undershooting of the solution occurs, preventing oscillations in the process. The mentioned techniques are described in the following paragraphs.

Total variation diminishing The total variation is a tool that allows to measure oscillations that might occur in numerical solutions regarding the approximation of discontinuities. These oscillations are produced by utilising high-order numerical schemes like the *Lax-Wendroff scheme* or the *Beam-and-Warming scheme*. The former is known to produce oscillations ahead of the discontinuity while the latter produces them after the wave. The behavior of oscillations can be monitored with the total variation TV , which

is expressed as:

$$TV(\mathbf{q}) = \sum_{i=-\infty}^{\infty} |\mathbf{q}_i - \mathbf{q}_{i+1}| \quad (3.34)$$

To prevent spurious oscillations, the total variation must diminish or at least not increase over time. Respecting the discretisation of time, this means that the total variation on the new time level must not be greater than the total variation on the old time level:

$$TV(\mathbf{q}^{n+1}) \leq TV(\mathbf{q}^n) \quad (3.35)$$

Unlike higher-order schemes, first-order schemes always fulfill Eq. (3.35) as they are monotone and therefore total variation diminishing (Toro, 2009).

Slope limiter The Riemann problem described in Eq. (3.17) is based on the conserved variables of a left and a right state connected by a discontinuity. Instead of choosing the piecewise constant data of the midpoints i and $i + 1$ of the interfacing cells, the conserved variables, as well as the bottom elevation and the water elevation, are interpolated beforehand, thus reconstructed directly at left and right side of the edge $i + 1/2$:

$$\phi_{i+1/2_L} = \phi_i + \frac{1}{2}R(m_{i+1/2_L})(\phi_{i+1} - \phi_i) \quad (3.36)$$

$$\phi_{i+1/2_R} = \phi_{i+1} + \frac{1}{2}R(m_{i+1/2_R})(\phi_i - \phi_{i+1}) \quad (3.37)$$

ϕ is substituted with components of $\mathbf{q} = (d, ud, vd)^T$, the water elevation h or bottom elevation z_B . The limiter function is denoted by R and in order to prevent the occurrence of spurious oscillations, the function must be total variation diminishing. This is achieved if

$$0 \leq R(m) \leq \max(0, \min(2, 2m)) \quad (3.38)$$

is satisfied. The limitation is a function of the smoothness monitor, which compares the slopes of the neighbouring cells. The left and right smoothness monitors are computed

as:

$$m_{i+1/2_L} = \frac{\eta_{i-1/2}}{\eta_{i+1/2}} \quad (3.39)$$

$$m_{i+1/2_R} = \frac{\eta_{i+3/2}}{\eta_{i+1/2}} \quad (3.40)$$

with η denoting the slope, computed as:

$$\eta_{i-1/2} = \frac{\phi_i - \phi_{i-1}}{\Delta x_{i-1/2}} \quad \eta_{i+1/2} = \frac{\phi_{i+1} - \phi_i}{\Delta x_{i+1/2}} \quad \eta_{i+3/2} = \frac{\phi_{i+1} - \phi_{i+2}}{\Delta x_{i+3/2}} \quad (3.41)$$

Figure 3.8: Cells and values involved in the reconstruction of a variable at the edge $i+1/2$.

Fig. 3.8 depicts the cells involved in the reconstruction process. For meshes with uniformly spaced cells, Δx cancels out when Eq. (3.41) is substituted into Eq. (3.39) and Eq. (3.40) (Özgen, 2011).

The condition in Eq. (3.38) ensures that the solution is always anti-diffusive by enforcing R being greater than or equal to zero. If the smoothness monitor is less than zero, the compared slopes have different signs, which indicates a local extremum. In this case, the limiter function will be zero to enforce a first order reconstruction, fully limiting the local extreme value. This is also done for gradients equal to zero. In the case of very sharp gradients, indicated by large smoothness monitors, the limiter function may be equal to two, which also results in a first order reconstruction. If the slopes are equal, then the smoothness monitor as well as the limiter function will be equal to one, ensuring a full second order reconstruction. The following limiter functions subscribe to the described behavior and are implemented in `hms++`:

Figure 3.9: Slope limiter functions inside the Sweby region of second-order accurate TVD methods (Simons (2020), modified by the author).

- minmod (Roe, 1985):

$$R(m) = \max(0, \min(m, 1)) \quad (3.42)$$

- van Albada:

$$R(m) = \max\left(0, \frac{m + m^2}{1 + m^2}\right) \quad (3.43)$$

- van Leer (Leer, 1979):

$$R(m) = \frac{m + |m|}{1 + m} \quad (3.44)$$

- Superbee (Roe, 1985):

$$R(m) = \max(0, \min(2m, 1), \min(m, 2)) \quad (3.45)$$

- UMIST:

$$R(m) = \max\left(0, \min\left(2, 2m, \frac{3 + m}{4}, \frac{1 + 3m}{4}\right)\right) \quad (3.46)$$

- QUICK:

$$R(m) = \max\left(0, \min\left(2, 2m, \frac{3 + m}{4}\right)\right) \quad (3.47)$$

- Monotonised central-difference (Leer, 1979):

$$R(m) = \max \left(0, \min \left(2, 2m, \frac{1+m}{2} \right) \right) \quad (3.48)$$

Fig. 3.9 shows the Sweby diagram, visualising the limiter functions in dependence of the smoothness monitor. The Sweby region marks an area in which the functions are total variation diminishing and are second-order accurate in space (Sweby, 1984). If a limiter function would be located above the Sweby region, then its total variation would be increasing and spurious oscillations would occur. If it is below, then it is only first-order accurate. The higher the function values of a limiter function are, the higher is the order of accuracy and the less it is limiting the slope (Özgen, 2011).

3.4. Slope source term treatment

In order to treat the slope source term, further reconstruction of the bed elevation is necessary. Eq. (3.32) results in the reconstructed bed elevation for the edge k . For the slope source term treatment, the lower value between the reconstructed water elevation of the currently observed cell and the bed elevation at the edge is chosen as new bed elevation at the edge:

$$z_{B,k} = \min(h_{\text{cell}}, z_{B,k}) \quad (3.49)$$

In the finite-volume framework, the slope source term of Eq. (2.3) is integrated over the control volume, but the solution can be simplified by transforming the term into an integral over the surface. The result acts as fluxes across the edges of the control volume, leading to the summation of fluxes:

$$\int_{\Omega} \mathbf{s}_B d\Omega = \oint_{\Gamma} (\mathbf{f}_B n_x + \mathbf{g}_B n_y) d\Gamma = \sum_{k=1}^{n_B} (\mathbf{F}_{B_k} \mathbf{n}_k l_k) \quad (3.50)$$

Just as with the advective fluxes, the directional components can be combined to:

$$\mathbf{f}_{B,k} n_{k_x} + \mathbf{g}_{B,k} n_{k_y} = \mathbf{F}_{B_k} \mathbf{n}_k \quad (3.51)$$

The now transformed slope source is computed as:

$$\mathbf{F}_{B_k} \mathbf{n}_k = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -n_{k_x} \frac{1}{2} g (d_k + d_{\text{cell}}) (z_{B,k} - z_{\text{cell}}) \\ -n_{k_y} \frac{1}{2} g (d_k + d_{\text{cell}}) (z_{B,k} - z_{\text{cell}}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.52)$$

with d_{cell} denoting the original piecewise constant water depth in the currently observed cell and d_k denoting the reconstructed water depth Eq. (3.33) at the edge. $z_{B,k}$ stands for the newly reconstructed bottom elevation at the edge, obtained by Eq. (3.49), and z_{cell} stands for the unreconstructed piecewise constant bottom elevation of the observed cell. Substituting Eq. (3.51) in Eq. (3.50) and then into Eq. (3.10) modifies the time-marching equation into:

$$\mathbf{q}^{n+1} = \mathbf{q}^n - \frac{\Delta t}{A} \sum_{k=1}^{n_B} ((\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_k}^n + \mathbf{F}_{B_k}^n) \mathbf{n}_k l_k) + \Delta t (\mathbf{s}_m^n + \mathbf{s}_f^n) \quad (3.53)$$

This treatment produces a well-balanced solution fulfilling the C-Property (Hou et al., 2013).

3.5. Friction source term treatment

Liang and Marche (2009) state that in cases involving wetting and drying of cells, the friction term plays an important role in simulation stability. Eq. (2.5) and Eq. (2.7) show that the water depth is part of the denominator of the friction term. Due to this circumstance, very small water depths may lead to great forces, generated by friction, that are physically incorrect. In order to ensure stability of the numerical scheme, the friction term is discretised in an implicit way by utilising a splitting point-implicit method. Since the friction has no influence on the mass balance, only the momentum balance equations are considered for the following computations. Using the splitting method, the friction source term is calculated for the new time level and Eq. (3.53) is rewritten as:

$$\mathbf{q}^{n+1} = \mathbf{q}^n - \frac{\Delta t}{A} \sum_{k=1}^{n_B} ((\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_k}^n + \mathbf{F}_{B_k}^n) \mathbf{n}_k l_k) + \Delta t \mathbf{s}_m^n + \Delta t \mathbf{s}_f^{n+1} \quad (3.54)$$

The friction source term \mathbf{s}_f^{n+1} on the new time level can be expressed through a Taylor

series expansion:

$$\mathbf{s}_f^{n+1} = \mathbf{s}_f^n + \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{s}_f}{\partial \mathbf{q}}\right)^n (\mathbf{q}^{n+1} - \mathbf{q}^n) + O(\Delta \mathbf{q}^2) \quad (3.55)$$

Eq. (3.55) is substituted into Eq. (3.54) while the higher order terms are dropped. This yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{q}^{n+1} &= \mathbf{q}^n - \frac{\Delta t}{A} \sum_{k=1}^{n_B} ((\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_k}^n + \mathbf{F}_{\text{B}_k}^n) \mathbf{n}_k l_k) + \Delta t \mathbf{s}_m^n \\ &\quad + \Delta t (\mathbf{s}_f^n + \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{s}_f}{\partial \mathbf{q}}\right)^n (\mathbf{q}^{n+1} - \mathbf{q}^n)) \\ \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{q}^{n+1} - \Delta t \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{s}_f}{\partial \mathbf{q}}\right)^n (\mathbf{q}^{n+1} - \mathbf{q}^n) &= \mathbf{q}^n - \frac{\Delta t}{A} \sum_{k=1}^{n_B} ((\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_k}^n + \mathbf{F}_{\text{B}_k}^n) \mathbf{n}_k l_k) \\ &\quad + \Delta t \mathbf{s}_m^n + \Delta t \mathbf{s}_f^n \\ \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{q}^{n+1} (1 - \Delta t \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{s}_f}{\partial \mathbf{q}}\right)^n) &= \mathbf{q}^n (1 - \Delta t \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{s}_f}{\partial \mathbf{q}}\right)^n) - \frac{\Delta t}{A} \sum_{k=1}^{n_B} ((\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_k}^n + \mathbf{F}_{\text{B}_k}^n) \mathbf{n}_k l_k) \\ &\quad + \Delta t \mathbf{s}_m^n + \Delta t \mathbf{s}_f^n \\ \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{q}^{n+1} &= \mathbf{q}^n + \frac{1}{1 - \Delta t \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{s}_f}{\partial \mathbf{q}}\right)^n} \left(-\frac{\Delta t}{A} \sum_{k=1}^{n_B} ((\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_k}^n + \mathbf{F}_{\text{B}_k}^n) \mathbf{n}_k l_k) + \Delta t \mathbf{s}_m^n + \Delta t \mathbf{s}_f^n \right) \\ \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{q}^{n+1} &= \mathbf{q}^n + \frac{1}{\mathbf{D}} \left(-\frac{\Delta t}{A} \sum_{k=1}^{n_B} ((\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_k}^n + \mathbf{F}_{\text{B}_k}^n) \mathbf{n}_k l_k) + \Delta t \mathbf{s}_m^n + \Delta t \mathbf{s}_f^n \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3.56)$$

in which \mathbf{D} is the coefficient that is derived for a fully implicit scheme (Liang & Marche, 2009). It can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{D} = 1 - \Delta t \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{s}_f}{\partial \mathbf{q}}\right)^n = 1 + C \frac{\Delta t}{d} (|\mathbf{v}| + \frac{\mathbf{v}^2}{|\mathbf{v}|}) \quad (3.57)$$

Eq. (3.56) is the actual equation that is evolved in time with the implemented algorithm, detailed in Sec. 5.4.

3.6. Boundary and initial conditions

The numerical methods described in prior sections are operational under the assumption that cells are neighbouring other cells. However, this is not the case for cells located at the boundary of the computational domain. In order to apply the implemented schemes to boundary adjacent cells, the computational domain is extended by so called *ghost cells*. These are fictitious cells that interface domain cells located at the boundary. Ghost cells contain values for the primitive variables or conserved variables that are set according to boundary conditions at the beginning of each time step. Furthermore, initial values for the primitive variables are required to compute the first iteration of the time-marching algorithm. These values are called the initial conditions and are given by the user.

In `hms++`, a few common sets of boundary conditions for the SWEs, given in Simons (2020), have been implemented and will be described in the following.

3.6.1. Walls

The ghost cell value of the water depth for the representation of a wall is equal to the domain cell value. The tangential flow velocity in the ghost cell mirrors the domain cell value. This way, they cancel each other out so no flux occurs at the edge:

$$d_{\text{ghost}} = d_{\text{domain}} \quad (3.58)$$

$$v_{\perp\text{ghost}} = -v_{\perp\text{domain}} \quad (3.59)$$

Walls can either have a slip or a no-slip condition. This depends on whether wall friction should be taken into account or not. If friction is considered, the tangential velocity in the ghost cell is equal to the negative domain cell value:

$$v_{\parallel\text{ghost}} = -v_{\parallel\text{domain}} \quad (3.60)$$

If friction has no influence, then the ghost cell value is equal to the domain cell value:

$$v_{\parallel\text{ghost}} = v_{\parallel\text{domain}} \quad (3.61)$$

3.6.2. Free outflow

If a free outflow condition is prescribed to a boundary, the flow velocity and water depth in the ghost cell are set to the corresponding values in the neighbouring domain cell:

$$v_{\parallel\text{ghost}} = v_{\parallel\text{domain}} \quad (3.62)$$

$$v_{\perp\text{ghost}} = v_{\perp\text{domain}} \quad (3.63)$$

$$d_{\text{ghost}} = d_{\text{domain}} \quad (3.64)$$

In case an influx instead of an outflux occurs at the boundary due to changes in the flow field, the boundary condition is changed to represent a solid boundary, i.e. the normal flow velocity in the ghost cell mirrors the normal flow velocity in the adjacent domain cell:

$$v_{\perp\text{ghost}} = -v_{\perp\text{domain}} \quad (3.65)$$

It should be noted that when this boundary condition is prescribed and the flow field in proximity of the boundary is in subcritical flow condition, it will tend to become supercritical. This is due to the influence of the upstream traveling wave of the Riemann problem at that edge. This behaviour is unwanted, especially for simulations trying to achieve a steady state. Simons (2020) proposes a threshold to limit the water depth, which increases convergence speed:

$$d_{\text{ghost}} = \max(d_{\text{domain}}, d_{\text{threshold}}) \quad (3.66)$$

3.6.3. Constant water depth

A constant water depth can be prescribed for a boundary by settings the water depth in the ghost cell to the desired value:

$$d_{\text{ghost}} = d_{\text{boundary}} \quad (3.67)$$

If flow conditions in the field are subcritical, a rarefaction wave from the Riemann problem is influencing the upstream. One can take advantage of this circumstance and compute the normal flow velocity in the ghost cell with the rarefaction case of Eq. (3.18):

$$v_{\perp\text{ghost}} = v_{\perp\text{domain}} + 2(\sqrt{gd_{\text{domain}}} - \sqrt{gd_{\text{ghost}}}) \quad (3.68)$$

The tangential flow velocity in the ghost cell is equal to the domain cell value:

$$v_{\parallel\text{ghost}} = v_{\parallel\text{domain}} \quad (3.69)$$

3.6.4. Constant normal flow velocity

The normal flow velocity in the ghost cell is set to a fixed value while the tangential flow velocity is equal to the domain cell value:

$$v_{\perp\text{ghost}} = v_{\perp\text{boundary}} \quad (3.70)$$

$$v_{\parallel\text{ghost}} = v_{\parallel\text{domain}} \quad (3.71)$$

For subcritical flow conditions, the water depth in the ghost cell is computed via the rarefaction wave that influences the upstream. Again, Eq. (3.18) is used, but now rearranged for the water depth in the ghost cell:

$$d_{\text{ghost}} = \frac{1}{4g} (v_{\text{ghost}} - v_{\text{domain}} - 2\sqrt{gd_{\text{domain}}})^2 \quad (3.72)$$

4. Modern computer architecture

Since the algorithms implemented in `hms++` are designed to make use of modern parallel computers, a summary of important concepts of computer architecture and its components is given in this section. The *von Neumann model* is the most common computer architecture and is briefly described in Sec. 4.1, followed by a description of cache memory in Sec. 4.2. Afterwards, parallel computing concepts, such as simultaneous multithreading, vectorisation and cache coherence, are presented in Sec. 4.3.

4.1. Von Neumann model

Most computer architectures today are based on the von Neumann model, which was published in 1945. The model describes the architecture with four components: An input unit, an output unit, a main memory unit and a central processing unit (CPU), which comprises a control unit and an execution unit. In the context of computational performance, the CPU and memory unit are of particular interest as the CPU is doing the fundamental computational work and is reading and writing data to its register and eventually to the main memory unit. Data transfer between the two components is happening over a connecting component called bus. This bus is introducing a latency into the system as the main memory has to be accessed, an operation that is relatively slow compared to register access or the computation itself. Over the course of technological progress, computation times of the CPU became much faster than memory access times, which led to the connecting bus inhibiting performance, since its bandwidth could not uphold the CPU's request for data, resulting in the so-called *von Neumann bottleneck* (Häfliger et al., 2014).

4.2. Cache memory

To reduce the effect of the bottleneck, the architecture was amended by introducing multiple levels of cache memory in addition to the main memory. Cache memory offers considerably faster access times than the main memory, as it employs *static random access memory* (SRAM), a type of random access memory that is faster than *dynamic random access memory* (DRAM), which is used for the main memory unit. Due to the relatively high cost of SRAM, cache memory is substantially smaller than the main memory. Additionally, the cache memory unit is directly located on the CPU die, further impacting size and costs. CPU die size and therefore cache memory size is linked to the manufacturing process of integrated circuits. Dies are manufactured in batches, located

on a wafer. During the manufacturing process, the wafer and dies can be damaged, rendering the affected dies defective. As a consequence, these dies are discarded, reducing the yield per wafer, i.e. the fraction of good dies on the wafer. In order to minimise the cost per integrated circuit, the number of chips per wafer, therefore the proportion of good chips, is maximised. This entails that chip sizes and their space for cache memory units have to be relatively small (May, 2006).

In Tab. 4.1 the access times and sizes for different memory units are listed (Häfliger et al., 2014).

Memory unit	Access time	Size
L1 cache	$\gtrsim 1$ ns	$\sim 10 - 100$ kB/core
L2, L3 cache	$\sim 2 - 10$ ns	~ 1 MB/core
Main memory	$\sim 20 - 100$ ns	$\gtrsim 1$ GB
SSD / Flash memory	~ 100 ns - 1 μ s	$\gtrsim 128$ GB
HDD	~ 1 ms	$\gtrsim 500$ GB

Table 4.1: Access times and sizes for different memory units.

Cache memory acts on the principle of locality, which assumes that accessed data is in temporal and spatial proximity of one another. In the main memory, each byte is indexed by a memory address. A byte is part of a block of contiguous bytes, a so-called cache line, which begins on the first memory address that precedes the initially accessed byte and is divisible by 64. The test platform that was frequently used throughout this work has a cache line size of 64 bytes (Intel Corporation, 2021). When a byte is accessed, the whole cache line is loaded into cache memory instead just the targeted address under the assumption that its entries will be accessed soon. When the CPU is instructed to fetch data, it will start searching for it in the cache memory. If the data is found, a so-called *cache hit* is scored, resulting in a fast memory access. If not, a *cache miss* occurs and main memory has to be accessed to retrieve the data, a significantly slower operation. Therefore, a high ratio of cache hits to cache misses benefits performance.

Since cache memory is of rather small size in comparison to main memory, the replacement of cache lines needs to be managed. Many modern CPUs follow a *least recently used* (LRU) replacement policy or variants of it to replace cache lines, i.e. when a new cache line has to be loaded into cache but the latter is already full, the least recently used cache line gets evicted from cache to make space for the new cache line. Cache line placement and replacement also depends on the cache mapping strategy of the CPU.

Modern computers employ one of three following policies:

When utilising direct mapped cache, each cache line in main memory is mapped to exactly one cache line of the cache memory unit, identified by a part of the memory address called 'tag'. On the one hand, this speeds up hit-checking, since the potential location of the sought after memory in cache is known. On the other hand, the benefits obtained by caching are diminished if the program uses memory that is mapped to the same cache line slot, which leads to conflict misses due to contention and reduces the cache hit rate.

The fully associative cache maps a cache line of the main memory to every slot of the cache memory unit. This alleviates memory contention and increases the cache hit rate, however, hit-checking is slower since the desired data is only found by iterating through the lines of the cache memory unit.

Set-associative cache combines both policies. Cache line slots in the cache memory are divided into sets to which the cache lines of the main memory are mapped. These sets behave like direct mapped cache, whereas their cache line slots are fully associative. This limits hit-checking to the cache line slots inside a set (Häfliger et al., 2014).

4.3. Parallel computing

Solving computational problems can be accelerated by decomposing a problem into parts that are then solved in parallel, utilising more resources, namely parallel computers. There are different categories of parallelism in computers, usually classified after *Flynn's taxonomy* (Flynn, 2011), as shown in Fig. 4.1. In regards to Flynn's taxonomy, parallel computers can be classified as either *single instruction multiple data* (SIMD) or *multiple instruction multiple data* (MIMD), while traditional non-parallel computers fit into the category *single instruction single data* (SISD), as their CPU is capable of handling only one instruction on a single data stream per clock cycle. Parallel computers with SIMD capabilities are able to supply all processing units with a single instruction that gets carried out on different data elements. This form of parallelism often is applied to problems featuring a high degree of regularity, such as vector/matrix transformations. But the most common type of parallel computers, including the ones utilised in this work, are classified as MIMD. These computers often feature multiple CPU cores or chips. Processors have their own instructions and operate on their own data independently. To exploit parallelism on multiple avenues, MIMD computers often also feature SIMD subcomponents. The last quadrant of Flynn's taxonomy is *single input multiple data* (MISD), a mostly irrelevant classification as these computer have no real use in scientific

	Single Data	Multiple Data
Single Instruction	Single Instruction Single Data SISD	Single Instruction Multiple Data SIMD
Multiple Instructions	Multiple Instructions Single Data MISD	Multiple Instructions Multiple Data MIMD

Figure 4.1: Flynn's taxonomy of computer architectures.

or personal computing.

Further categorisation is necessary when it comes to hardware architecture, specifically the layout of CPUs and memory units. Parallel design traits appear on multiple levels of computer architecture. Single processor chips may feature multiple CPU cores that share access to a global memory unit, often seen in common retail products like laptops. Computers with more than one CPU socket may feature multiple chips each featuring multiple cores, usually employed by servers and workstations. Another possibility is a network of computers, working in isolation and waiting for parallelisation coordinated by the programmer, a common practice for high-performance computers. In general, modern parallel computers can be categorised as either shared-memory systems, distributed-memory systems or hybrid systems (Hennessy, 2003).

4.3.1. Shared-memory systems

The computational work in this thesis was carried out on so-called *shared-memory systems*, which may have a single or multiple processor chips each featuring a single or multiple CPU cores. In shared-memory systems, also known as *symmetric multiprocessing* (SMP), the CPU cores have direct access to the main memory via a memory controller. The scheduling of an application does not depend on the cores, i.e. the program can run on different cores at different times without altering the output of the program since all cores work on the same memory unit. Shared-memory systems can be further divided into *uniform-memory-access* (UMA) systems and *non-uniform-memory-access* (NUMA)

systems.

Figure 4.2: Overview of a shared-memory system with uniform memory access.

In UMA systems, all cores on a chip access the same physical memory via a memory switch, often a system bus, allowing identical access times for each core. The limited bandwidth of bus-based systems is a disadvantage in terms of the scalability of such systems. With an increasing number of cores, the available bandwidth decreases and latency increases. Fig. 4.2 illustrates an exemplary shared-memory UMA system with a single multiprocessor chip featuring four CPU cores, each with a private L1 and L2 cache memory unit as well as a shared L3 cache memory unit.

NUMA systems avoid this by moving away from a single centralized memory pool and employing physically distributed local memory for each chip, forming a unit that is called a node. The nodes are interconnected, as shown in Fig. 4.3, enabling the utilisation of the same memory access API for all CPUs and therefore creating a global address space. This entails that each CPU core is able to access its own as well as remote memory units of other chips. On the upside, this takes some of the workload off of the local bandwidth, therefore reducing the bottleneck effect seen in UMA systems, however remote memory accesses are slower than accessing the local memory unit, therefore introducing a new form of overhead. In order to keep the cache of all CPUs coherent, all processors are

Figure 4.3: Overview of a shared-memory system with non-uniform memory access.

notified if a location in the shared-memory is updated, introducing further overhead. More on cache coherence in Sec. 4.3.4.

While NUMA systems generally scale better than UMA systems, as the memory bandwidth is increased and the latency to local memory decreases, the scalability is also limited. Increasing the number of nodes may lead to more traffic on the remote memory path, which already operates on higher latencies, and may also lead to an increased overhead caused by memory management (Hennessy, 2003).

A common programming interface often used in conjunction with shared-memory systems is *OpenMP*. See Sec. 5.1.1 for detailed explanations on how *OpenMP* is used in `hms++`.

4.3.2. Vectorisation

Vectorisation is categorised as a SIMD principle. It is a special program transformation that allows to perform the same operation on multiple data elements simultaneously. However, hardware must support these operations, which is done through the use of instruction set extensions.

Generally, vectorisation can be used in three different ways, each representing a trade-off

between the portability of the source code and its performance. The first and easiest approach is auto-vectorisation. One advantage of auto-vectorisation is its simple usage, since the compiler automatically determines which pieces of code it will vectorise. The user merely has to set specific flags when compiling the source code. Another advantage is that the code is portable, since no changes to the source code are necessary when moving to different platform. However, the performance portability suffers, as different platforms may support different instruction sets. This entails that a piece of code, e.g. a loop, might be vectorised for a certain supported instruction set, whereas on a different platform, the same code might be vectorised for a separate instruction set. Possible consequences are significantly different computation times. Furthermore, some pieces of source code might be too complex for the compiler to vectorise (Pohl et al., 2016).

If the compiler is not able to vectorise a piece of code, guided vectorisation can be used. This method requires more effort on source code level than auto-vectorisation since every loop or function that needs vectorisation has to be preceded by a preprocessor directive. Compilers also have to support the chosen multiprocessing interface. Using an API like *OpenMP SIMD*, one is able to advise the compiler how to vectorise a piece of code. The simplest way to do this is by employing the preprocessor directive `#pragma omp simd`, an instruction for the compiler to vectorise subsequent code that can be extended by various clauses (OpenMP Architecture Review Board, 2015).

The third and most difficult way to employ vectorisation is to use vector intrinsics. These are data types for vectors specific to certain instruction sets and therefore completely dependent on the used processor. This method is the most difficult one out of the three vectorisation techniques as it requires low-level work on the source code, downgrading its portability. On the other hand, the trade-off in source code portability improves the performance portability since it stays more or less similar on different processors, if they are compatible with the chosen instruction sets (Intel Corporation, 2021).

4.3.3. Simultaneous multithreading

Modern operating systems (OS) are *multithreading*, i.e. they support running small, independent pieces of programs called *threads* or *software threads*. This allows the OS to process a thread while another thread waits for a memory operation or I/O from the user, therefore facilitating work to be processed in parallel. Traditionally, a system with a single CPU executes these threads sequentially and switches between them rapidly, creating a seemingly simultaneous processing of the threads.

While the introduction of symmetric multiprocessing allowed for the actual parallel

processing of threads, another technique to improve performance, namely *simultaneous multithreading* (SMT), gained in popularity at the beginning of this century. CPU cores capable of SMT consist of two logical processors, also called hardware threads, both sharing the execution resources and cache memory of the CPU core. The OS engages each hardware thread as an independent processor, which means that a system with two physical cores is represented in the OS as a system with 4 processors. Each logical processor of a CPU core is able to track a software thread. When the first logical processor handles its assigned software thread and does not utilise all available execution resources, the second logical processor is able to use these idle resources to handle its own software thread. This way the utilisation of the execution resources of the CPU core as well as the instruction throughput increases (Intel Corporation, 2003).

However, since the logical processors of a CPU core share the cache memory, SMT can also have performance degrading effects, as the contention for cache memory rises. This entails that SMT is only beneficial to the computational performance if the time saved by the utilisation of idle execution resources is greater than the time accrued by cache memory contention. Consider highly vectorised applications in which the execution of a single thread uses up almost all execution resources of the CPU core. In this case, SMT may only save an insignificant amount of time on the execution part but still strain the memory bandwidth by utilising the second logical processor, leading to a performance degradation (Saini et al., 2011).

The performance benefits obtained by SMT for compute-intensive workloads vary. Intel benchmarked a CFD code, threaded with OpenMP, on a single-processor SMT system and obtained a speed-up of 23% (Magro & Shah, 2002). In an investigation by the *NASA Advanced Supercomputing Division*, a range of different CFD codes has been tested with obtained speed-ups ranging between -15% and 45% (Saini et al., 2011).

The utilised test platforms, detailed in Sec. 7.2, make use of Intel's implementation of SMT, called *Hyperthreading Technology*. Its impact on the computational performance of the simulations in this work is subject to analysis.

To avoid confusion, the term "thread" always refers to a software thread in future mentions, unless it is explicitly mentioned as a hardware thread.

4.3.4. Cache coherence

When writing algorithms for modern parallel machines, cache coherence is an aspect that needs consideration, as it can have detrimental effects on performance should it be neglected. State-of-the-art processors feature CPU cores that have private cache memory

units. As described in Sec. 4.2, when data is accessed, the corresponding cache lines will be loaded into the cache. If, for example, two different processors read the same or two different memory addresses that reside on the same cache line, the latter will be loaded into both private cache memories. Should one of the CPUs perform write operations on a memory location on this cache line, it is inconsistent with its copy in the other CPU's cache. If this second CPU accesses the cache line, via read or write operation, the cached copy of the cache line in the first processor has to be written back into main memory and reloaded into cache memory of the second processor, to keep the cache line copies coherent. How this procedure actually works is encapsulated in so-called *cache coherence protocols* that are implemented by shared-memory systems. Even though these cache coherence mechanisms ensure that inconsistent cache lines will not falsify computations, it introduces an overhead, as each write operation on the cache line, followed by a read or write operation on the same line by another processor, is forcing processors to reload the affected cache line, inhibiting the performance benefits originally expected by the usage of cache memory. This performance problem is also known as *false sharing* (Sorin et al., 2011).

5. Implementation in hms++

`hms++` is an open-source C++ software framework, introduced in Steffen et al. (2020) and is licensed under the GNU General Public License v3.0. The main motivation behind the development of `hms++` is to create a framework for explicit FVM solvers that utilises industry standard high-performance parallelisation libraries for modern parallel computers as well as mature linear algebra libraries in order to improve the computational performance of numerical simulations. Furthermore, `hms++` is extendible, as it provides an expressive interface to develop new solvers for arbitrary meshes.

The framework already features a built-in Godunov-type solver for the depth-averaged SWEs. The solver is based on a robust solver implemented in `hms-java`. Both versions are in development and being maintained independently from each other at the Chair of Water Resources Management and Modeling of Hydrosystems, Technische Universität Berlin.

The fundamental libraries that are implemented in `hms++`, along with some of their used subroutines, are presented in Sec. 5.1. This is followed by a description of the representation of computational meshes and their indexing schemes in Sec. 5.2. Afterwards, the memory layout and storage components are presented in Sec. 5.3, followed by a detailed description of how the utilised numerical schemes are implemented, see Sec. 5.4. Lastly, the traversal strategies for flux calculation are introduced in Sec. 5.5.

5.1. Libraries

In order to exploit shared-memory multiprocessing computers, `hms++` uses the open-source API *OpenMP*. Further, the framework deeply integrates the expression template library *Eigen* for its data structures and its linear algebra operations.

5.1.1. OpenMP

OpenMP is a library and API which offers a set of compiler directives, functions and environment variables enabling parallel computing on shared-memory systems (Dagum & Menon, 1998). OpenMP is available in the FORTRAN, C and C++ programming languages, supports multi-platform shared-memory parallel programming on many architectures and is based on the programming model of so called *software threads*, also called *OpenMP threads*. In this context, a thread is a single unit of execution that can be run individually. Using OpenMP, an initial thread is running the desired application

in a serial manner. If the workload is parallelisable, the programmer can choose to create several threads that solve tasks assigned to them. Each thread has private data as well as access to the shared-memory pool, provided by the main application. This entails that data from the main application is not replicated onto the threads, which is why OpenMP is light on resources compared to distributed-memory interfaces like MPI. Since individual threads can be executed concurrently, each CPU core can have assigned threads to work on. For example, a system featuring four CPU cores can work on four threads simultaneously, although it is up to the programmer to avoid race conditions by utilising synchronisation constructs, provided by OpenMP. When the parallel work is done, the created threads can be removed and the process returns to a serial manner of work with only one so-called initial or master thread.

5.1.1.1. Environment variables

In order to control thread behaviour in terms of thread creation and thread pinning, OpenMP offers a number of environment variables that can be set to obtain a desired thread configuration (OpenMP Architecture Review Board, 2015).

The first environment variable of importance is `OMP_NUM_THREADS=N`. It is used to set the number of working threads that can be created by a parallel construct to `N`.

Another important variable is `OMP_PLACES`, which can be used to define places to which threads may be bound. In general, a place is to be understood as one or more hardware threads. The user can either choose to define a list of places or use one of the predefined abstract names, which are `threads`, `cores` or `sockets`. The first implies that each place corresponds to a single hardware thread, the second lets a place correspond to a single core, which might have more than one hardware thread, and the third lets a place correspond to a single socket, which can consist of more than one core. Either way, places are hardware-dependent and the user should investigate how the numbering of hardware threads is handled on the target machine.

To make use of the defined places, the environment variable `OMP_PROC_BIND` is used. It determines whether software threads are pinned to places. If it is set to `false`, the execution environment may freely move the software threads between the places. This may lead to a performance degradation since a move to another hardware thread implies the use of a possibly different cache memory unit, which would increase cache misses. Moving it to a different NUMA section would further impact the performance negatively since the memory latency increases.

To prevent this from happening, threads are bound to their places by setting the variable

to either one of the following values:

<code>true</code>	Software threads are pinned to the defined places and should not be moved by the execution environment.
<code>master</code>	All software threads in a team are pinned to the same place as the master thread.
<code>close</code>	The threads in a team are assigned to places close to the place of the master thread.
<code>spread</code>	Distribute the threads sparsely between the places.

5.1.1.2. Constructs

OpenMP manages parallel execution in a fork-join model implemented as *parallel* regions.

```

1 // variable is shared by all threads of upcoming parallel region
2 int x = 0;
3
4 // opening the parallel region
5 #pragma omp parallel
6 {
7     // synchronising incrementation of variable
8     #pragma omp atomic
9     ++x; // isolated incrementation
10
11     // thread specific print out
12     std::cout << x << std::endl;
13 } // end of parallel region
14
15 // final printout
16 std::cout << "final: " << x;

```

Code 1: Synchronised parallel incrementation of a shared variable.

A parallel region is a construct, opened in Code 1, line 5, that when encountered by the initial thread, creates a team of threads. The number of threads created, when a parallel region is opened up, corresponds to the environment variable `OMP_NUM_THREADS` by default. Each thread then executes the instructions inside the construct in concurrency with the other threads of the team. Threads of a parallel region may read and/or write of/to the same memory location, which can cause errors, specifically for simultaneous read-write or write-write operations. These types of situations can occur in the calculation of advective fluxes, where two threads may read and write data to the same storage vector of a cell. To avoid this situation, thread execution can be synchronised. OpenMP provides multiple

synchronisation methods, one of them being the `atomic` construct. It ensures that a specific memory location is not accessed simultaneously but in a consecutive manner, demonstrated in Code 1, line 8. This averts race conditions between threads, i.e. the computation of indeterminate values by multiple, concurrent read-and-write operations, carried out by multiple threads, is prevented.

The example in Code 1 contains code inside the parallel region that is executed by all threads, however, this not always desired behaviour. For example, the parallelisation of the flux calculation should reduce the workload for each individual thread by dividing it. OpenMP provides many ways to achieve worksharing, a prominent option being the combined construct `omp parallel for`, which specifies that iterations of a for loop will be executed in parallel with each thread taking on a share of iterations. Code 2 demonstrates a for-loop that is parallelised, sharing the iterations of the loop between the threads.

```

1 // OMP_NUM_THREADS=4
2
3 // opening a worksharing parallel for loop with a static schedule
4 #pragma omp parallel for schedule (static)
5 for(int i = 0; i < 16; ++i)
6 {
7     std::cout << "Thread #" << omp_get_thread_num() << " handles
           iteration " << i << std::endl;
8 } // end of parallel region

```

Code 2: Worksharing loop construct.

Loop parallelisation can also be achieved via a single `omp for` construct used inside a parallel region instead of the combined construct of `omp parallel for`.

The threads in Code 2 handle the iterations in contiguous chunks, which is due to a concept called work scheduling. The `schedule`-clause is set to `static`, which ensures a contiguous feed of work for each thread. The default size of the contiguous data chunks for a thread is the iteration space divided by the number threads resulting in an even distribution. Should the division result in a rest, the residual iterations are distributed among the threads. If not specified otherwise, a thread will process its chunk in order of the iterations. This is called a `monotonic` modification of the schedule.

The end of parallelised loops acts as an implicit barrier, i.e. threads stop at this point of code execution and wait for other threads to finish their workload before moving on. If this is unwanted behaviour and threads should rather proceed to their next instruction instead of waiting for the others, a `nowait` clause can be utilised to omit the barrier, signifying threads that finish early to proceed autonomously. Barriers can also

be employed explicitly via the `omp barrier` directive.

Traversing two-dimensional meshes often requires the use of nested loops. If the iterations of these loops are independent from each other, the `collapse(numberOfLoops)` clause may be used to parallelise the execution, as seen in Code 3. The clause is fusing the loops to equally distribute the resulting iterations among the threads.

```

1 #pragma omp parallel for schedule(static) collapse(2)
2 for (i = 0; i < 10; i++)
3   for (j = 0; j < 100; j++)
4
5 // The code above is equal to:
6 #pragma omp parallel for
7 for(int n=0; n<10*100; n++) {
8   int i = n/100;
9   int j = n%100;
10 }

```

Code 3: Parallelisation of nested loops.

Another construct used is `omp sections`, a non-iterative worksharing construct comprising a set of structured blocks, distributed among the threads to be executed concurrently with each thread taking on one section. Code 4 shows an exemplary implementation of two sections in which concurrent threads increment their private variables in a loop. Similar to the `omp for` construct, an implicit barrier is employed at the end of an `omp sections` construct.

```

1 // open the parallel region
2 #pragma omp parallel
3 {
4   // open the sections region
5   #pragma omp sections
6   {
7     // define the first section that is to be executed by one thread
8     #pragma omp section
9     {
10      // first thread does something.
11    }
12    // define second section that is to be executed by another thread
13    #pragma omp section
14    {
15      // second thread does something.
16    }
17  }
18 }

```

Code 4: The `sections` construct comprising two sections that are to be executed in parallel.

Some instructions inside parallel regions may only be executed once by a single thread. For this case, the `omp single` construct can be employed. Every instruction inside the structured block following the directive is executed only once by a single thread. The construct is followed by an implicit barrier that may be omitted via a `nowait` clause.

In `hms++`, each OpenMP directive is encapsulated in conditional preprocessor directives to check if OpenMP is available on the current machine, as seen in Code 5. In case of no support, the OpenMP directives will not be passed to the compiler. In order to improve readability of further code snippets, these conditional preprocessor directives will not be listed.

```
1 #ifndef _OPENMP
2 #pragma omp parallel for
3 #endif
```

Code 5: Conditional preprocessor directive ensuring that OpenMP is available on the current machine.

5.1.2. Eigen

Eigen is an expression template library for linear algebra and is deeply integrated in `hms++`. It provides many data structures, like arrays, matrices and vectors used to store data. Next to its storage components, *Eigen* also offers a wide range of functions to carry out mathematical operations and manipulations on the data structures used. *Eigen* suits the development of the framework, as it is already using a number of optimisation techniques.

It features compile-time mechanisms to enable lazy evaluation. This way, expressions will be evaluated as late as possible by avoiding the evaluation of sub-expressions into temporaries, which can result in large performance improvements.

Eigen also uses a vectorisation system and does not rely on the compiler to vectorise code. The only thing *Eigen* does require from the compiler are some hints for supported instruction sets that are not enabled by default. Among others, the library supports the SIMD instruction sets SSE 2, 3, 4, AVX, AVX2, AVX512, FMA.

Furthermore, fixed-size matrices can be used which are optimised by avoiding dynamic memory allocation and using loop unrolling if it makes sense. Additionally, *Eigen* pays special attention to the cache-friendliness of large matrices (Guennebaud, Jacob, et al., 2010).

5.2. Computational mesh

hms++ supports structured as well as unstructured meshes, although this work focuses solely on structured meshes, which are further described in Sec. 5.2.1. In general, the mesh provides functionality to access topological and geometrical information about the discretised domain. It comprises cells and edges, identifiable by indices. The manners in which these indices are set, the so-called indexing patterns, are described in Sec. 5.2.2 and play an important role in the memory layout of data structures used as well as in the traversal of the mesh.

5.2.1. Structured mesh types

In hms++, structured meshes are divided into the three following sub-types: The **UniMesh**, depicted in Fig. 5.1a, consists of uniform cells that feature a rectangular geometry, which is defined by the edge lengths in x- and y-direction. Cells of a **RectMesh** are rectangular as well but they do not face the requirement to be uniform over the entire mesh. Varying heights and widths for rows and columns, respectively, are allowed in the same mesh, as illustrated in Fig. 5.1b. The rectangular geometry provided by the **UniMesh** and **RectMesh** allows for a simple implementation of normal vectors of edges, as there are only four possible directions, easily addressable via the algebraic sign. The **StructMesh**, shown in Fig. 5.1c, makes use of convex non-orthogonal quadrilateral cells. This allows for an improved representation of complex geometries of a domain while retaining the topological advantages of a conventional structured grid. When looking at the characteristic limitations of the three described structured mesh types, one can observe that they are interchangeable in one direction. This means that a mesh with the characteristics of a **UniMesh** can also be realised as a **RectMesh** or **StructMesh**. Further, a characteristic **RectMesh** can also be created as a **StructMesh** but not as a **UniMesh**. A mesh featuring the qualities of a **StructMesh** is only realisable as such. While all three structured mesh types may vary from one another geometry-wise, they share the same topology, e.g. every mesh topology shown in Fig. 5.1 features eight cells in x-direction and eight cells in y-direction. Every simulation and investigation, associated with this work, has been carried out exclusively using the **UniMesh**-type.

5.2.2. Indexing of cells and edges

The use of quadrilateral cells as control volumes comes results in a mesh that features a matrix-like arrangement of cells. This allows for a relatively simple mesh topology, which

Figure 5.1: Structured mesh types in hms++.

facilitates a straightforward implementation of neighbourhood relations between cells as well as a transparent memory layout. In hms++, the assignment of cell and edge indices is done via one of the two indexing patterns described in this section. These patterns also influence the orientation of normal vectors of edges, as the framework's convention states that they always point from the cell with the lower index to the cell with the higher index.

Simplified indexing Fig. 5.2a illustrates how the cells are indexed when the *simplified indexing* pattern is utilised. It begins with the lower-left ghost cell and indexes the cells in that row from left to right. Indexing continues in the adjacent row above, beginning at the most left cell again.

Figure 5.2: Simplified indexing pattern for cells and edges. Domain cells in blue, ghost cells in green. Blues arrows represent normal vectors of the edges.

The edges of the mesh are indexed in a similar way with a row-wise indexing of horizontal edges, followed by vertical edges, as shown in Fig 5.2b. It is noteworthy that ghost cells only feature edges that border the domain cells. Since there is no flow computation happening between ghost cells, they do not require edges that interface them. As a consequence, ghost cells in the corner of the mesh fulfill no purpose other than keeping the row-wise indexing of the cells consistent, i.e. the amount of cells for each row is the same.

The meshes used throughout this work exclusively use the simplified indexing pattern.

Unified indexing When the *unified indexing* pattern is employed, the indexing begins with the domain cells followed by the ghost cells, as seen in Fig. 5.3a. Similar to the *simplified indexing* pattern, the domain cells are indexed in a row-wise manner, from bottom to top. Afterwards the rows of ghost cells at the bottom and top of the mesh are indexed from left to right, followed by the left and right column of ghost cells, which are indexed from bottom to top. When comparing the patterns, it is noticeable that the *unified indexing* pattern does not feature ghost cells, as the indexing of domain cells is already consistent in itself and it is easy to see that the first ghost cell index starts with the number of domain cells. Including the corner cells would not benefit the consistency of the row-wise indexing as it did for *simplified indexing* pattern. Further, the direction of the normal vectors at the boundaries is consistent with the framework's convention, resulting in outward pointing vectors for the *unified indexing* pattern.

Figure 5.3: Unified indexing pattern for cells and edges.

Fig. 5.3b illustrates the indexing of the edges. The horizontal and vertical edges not located at the boundary are indexed first in a row-wise manner followed by the horizontal

boundary edges at the bottom and top of the mesh. Lastly, the vertical edges at the left and right boundary are indexed, from bottom to top.

5.2.3. Ghost cells

As described in Sec. 3.6, cells at the boundary of a domain are interfacing so-called ghost cells that are required to enforce boundary conditions. Although the ghost cell is a virtual cell, it is also identifiable by index. An essential difference between a ghost and a domain cell is that the former only has edges to domain cells and is not updated through flux, source or friction computations but merely provides its values for the calculation of the flux. Ghost cell values are updated in a separate function, further explained in Sec. 5.4.5.

5.3. Storage components and memory layout

Each primitive variable used in the shallow water equations, namely water depth, flow velocity, bottom elevation, mass sources and sinks, but also friction coefficients as well as the storage vector of state variables is stored in a so-called `field`, a data structure, provided by `hms++`. A field stores values in a one- or multi-dimensional array and provides functions to interface with these values. A field also holds an array containing the boundary conditions that provide set-and-update functionality for values in ghost cells.

The size of the field's storage array depends on the total amount of mesh cells. Each cell is represented by a column of the array and the number of rows is equivalent to the number of components of the respective variable. For example, the water depth is one dimensional, therefore it is stored in just one row, whereas the flow velocity is two-dimensional, hence it is stored in two rows, representing the components in x- and y-direction respectively. This is depicted in detail in Fig. 5.4 and 5.5 for the water depth and flow velocity respectively, based on the mesh seen in Fig. 5.2a.

One should keep in mind that when data is stored in memory, it is always laid out in one dimension. Therefore, the storage array can be a multi-dimensional representation but its data exists in a one-dimensional form in memory. If a one-dimensional variable is stored, the array already resembles the data laid out in memory since the array only has one row. The concept of *storage order* is used to manage the layout of multi-dimensional data. Eigen stores data in *column-major* order by default, i.e. all values of a column are stored, before the next column is stored, as shown in Fig. 5.6.

Figure 5.4: Storage array of a field for a one-dimensional variable.

Figure 5.5: Storage array of a field for a two-dimensional variable.

Two-dimensional array (2 rows, 5 columns):

value (0,0)	value (0,1)	value (0,2)	value (0,3)	value (0,4)	value (0,5)
value (1,0)	value (1,1)	value (1,2)	value (1,3)	value (1,4)	value (1,5)

Two-dimensional array in memory:

value (0,0)	value (1,0)	value (0,1)	value (1,1)	value (0,2)	value (1,2)	value (0,3)	value (1,3)	value (0,4)	value (1,4)	value (0,5)	value (1,5)
----------------	----------------	----------------	----------------	----------------	----------------	----------------	----------------	----------------	----------------	----------------	----------------

Figure 5.6: Memory layout of a two-dimensional array in column-major order.

When data is initially accessed, it is stored in the cache memory unit. Consider the following example how this is done: A field for a one-dimensional variable, e.g. water depth or bottom elevation, on a mesh with 31×32 cells (33×35 , including ghost cells), uses the simplified indexing scheme. Since the field is one-dimensional, it can be visually rearranged into the shape of the mesh, illustrated in Fig. 5.7. Each cell represents an entry in the field, starting at the bottom-left. Values are stored as double-precision floating points (in short: double) with a size of 8 bytes. Since the field's storage array is an Eigen-type, it is ensured that the first entry is 16-byte aligned, i.e. its memory address is divisible by 16. In this example, the memory address of first entry of the storage array, which is assigned to the first ghost cell on the bottom-left, is divisible by 64, making it the first entry in its cache line (although this is not necessarily the case in reality). A cache line is capable of holding 8 doubles, indicated by the red frames around cells in Fig. 5.7. Since the mesh features 33 cells in x-direction, the last cell of the first row coincides with the beginning of a new cache line that is continued in the second row of the mesh, leading to the stair-like pattern for the distribution of cache lines.

Figure 5.7: One-dimensional field for a mesh with $nx = 31$, $ny = 32$. Cells in between black borders are ghost cells. Red frames indicate cache lines.

Now consider a first-time flux calculation utilising a first-order or Central approach. When calculating flux over an edge, field data of the interfacing cells are accessed. Fig. 5.8 illustrates different data accesses and their implications for the cache.

Figure 5.8: First time data accesses for flux calculations using the Fully Upwind Method or HLLC with a first-order accurate reconstruction. Dark blue edge indicates current edge, green cells indicate cache hits, red cells indicate cache misses, purple frames indicate loaded cachelines.

If the data accessed are part of the same cache line, as pictured in Fig. 5.8a, the first data access results in a cache miss but loads the corresponding cache line into cache, which yields a cache hit when accessing the other cell. If the edge interfaces cells on two different cachelines, as in Fig. 5.8b, a cache miss occurs for both data accesses, with both cache lines loaded into cache afterwards. Calculating a flux for horizontal edges always operates on two cache lines, as seen in Fig. 5.8c.

Figure 5.9: First time data accesses for flux calculations using HLLC solver with the MUSCL scheme. Dark blue edge indicates current edge, green cells indicate cache hits, red cells indicate cache misses, purple frames indicate loaded cachelines.

As described in Sec. 3.3.5, the MUSCL reconstruction approach also utilises the second neighbours of the interfacing cells at an edge to limit the slopes. Fig. 5.9a pictures the use of this scheme for an initial calculation across a vertical edge, under the assumption

that the involved cells are part of a single cache line.

The first access results in a cache miss and loads the cache line into cache memory, which is followed by three cache hits for the next three data accesses. Assuming that the data of one of the involved resides on a different cache line, as depicted in Fig. 5.9b, another cache miss occurs, in addition to the first. Using MUSCL for initial flux calculations across horizontal edges results in a cache miss for each initial access of the involved cells, as each is located on a different cache line, as seen in Fig. 5.9c.

It is important to keep in mind that the arrangement of cache lines is probably different for the other variables involved in the calculation.

Exploiting cached data, i.e. performing flux calculations for edges whose involved field data is already in cache memory, is a known optimisation technique to improve performance (Lam et al., 1991). How this can be influenced by the traversal pattern and is a subject of analysis in this work.

5.4. Numerical scheme

The utilisation of the numerical concepts described in Sec. 3 yields the discretised depth-averaged shallow water equations, which can be expressed as in Eq. 3.56. This section covers the implementation of these concepts in `hms++`, with the exception of the exact Riemann solver. Fig. 5.10 broadly covers the process of the simulation and depicts the computational steps that are necessary to compute the primitive and state variables on the new time level. Sec. 5.4.1 covers the calculation of the time step. The advective flux calculation, including the Fully Upwind Method, HLLC approximate Riemann solver as well as the implementation of the different reconstruction schemes, is described in Sec. 5.4.2. This is followed by a description of the mass source/sink term calculation in Sec. 5.4.3, which also includes the friction source term calculation. Afterwards, the implementation of the new state variables calculation is covered in Sec. 5.4.4. Lastly, a brief description of how the boundaries are updated is given in Sec. 5.4.5.

At the start of the simulation, the initial conditions for the primitive variables are used to compute the storage vector \mathbf{q}^n of the current time level, containing the state variables water depth and specific discharges in x- and y-direction, for each cell. Afterwards, the solution is evolved in time until the loop reaches the end of a predefined simulation time.

Figure 5.10: Sequence of instructions to evolve the numerical solution in time.

5.4.1. Calculate time step

After computing the storage vectors, the simulation enters the main computation loop. In a first step, the time step size Δt is computed by solving Eq. 3.6 for each domain cell. In order to ensure numerical stability, the CFL condition has to be fulfilled for every cell of the domain. To achieve this, the overall smallest Δt is chosen as time step for further calculations. The time step calculation itself as well as the reduction to the smallest time step is accelerated through parallelisation by utilising the `omp parallel for` construct. Since the time step is stored in a single variable that is shared by the threads of the construct, the `reduction` clause is attached to prevent data races between threads as they write to the memory location of the variable (OpenMP Architecture Review Board, 2015).

5.4.2. Calculate advective fluxes

At this point, the time step has been successfully determined and the algorithm proceeds to solve the advective flux term of Eq. 3.56. The flux calculation approach depends on how the computational domain is traversed. Sec. 5.5 covers the implemented traversal

patterns in detail. In short, next to a cell-wise traversal, in which the flux calculation is carried out for each cell, `hms++` provides a different approach that traverses the edges of the domain for which the flux is computed. The initial idea for this approach is that the computational steps involved in the solving of the SWEs can be categorised as either edge-based or cell-based. With this notion, the flux calculation can be viewed as an operation belonging to the former while the remaining steps are classified as the latter. The essential difference between the edge-based and cell-based flux calculation lies in the registration of the results. When traversing edges, the resulting flux is added or subtracted to the storage vectors of cells interfacing at the edge. For a mandated cell traversal, on the other hand, the fluxes of all bounding edges of the cell are added or subtracted to its storage vector. The latter approach roughly doubles the total number of flux calculations since each edge, excluding boundary edges, interfaces two cells, which implies that the flux across the edge is computed twice. At the time of writing, only the HLLC approximate Riemann solver is implemented for the cell-wise traversal approach.

`hms++` provides two different flux calculation schemes if the edges of the computational domain are traversed. The first is the Fully Upwind Method and the second is the HLLC Riemann solver, with their numerical concepts described in detail in Sec. 3.3.1 and 3.3.3, respectively. In the following, the implementation of the schemes is presented, which also encompasses the TVD MUSCL extension of the HLLC Riemann solver, detailed in Sec. 3.3.5, as well as a Central approach to reconstruction.

5.4.2.1. Fully Upwind Method The flow chart in Fig. 5.11 depicts the sequence of actions conducted in the Fully Upwind Method. Computation is only carried out if at least one of the interfacing cells is wet, i.e. the water depth must be greater than a threshold value indicating dryness ($d_{min} = 1.0 \times 10^{-8}m$). Otherwise the calculation is skipped and the algorithm moves on to solve potential source/sink terms, as described in Sec. 5.4.3. In case of wetness, the left and right water elevation is computed as

$$h_L = d_L + z_L \quad (5.1)$$

$$h_R = d_R + z_R \quad (5.2)$$

and is used later during the computation of the hydrostatic pressure term. Afterwards, the mean flow velocity $\mathbf{v}_m = (u_m, v_m)^T$ is computed by solving Eq. 3.13 and immediately transformed into the normal/tangential flow velocity \mathbf{v}_{rot} of the edge by applying a

Figure 5.11: Fully Upwind Method for a mandated edge traversal.

rotational matrix to it:

$$\mathbf{v}_{\text{rot}} = \begin{bmatrix} v_{\perp} \\ v_{\parallel} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} n_x & n_y \\ n_y & -n_x \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_m \\ v_m \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.3)$$

This way, the flux scheme can also be easily applied to unstructured meshes. Subsequently, the rotated flow velocity is used to compute the advective flux $\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_k}$ by solving Eq. 3.14, although skipping its pressure term, as it differs for the left and right side. Next, the resulting vector is duplicated in order to obtain the flux terms $\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_{k,L}}$ and $\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_{k,R}}$ for the respective cells. Then, the hydrostatic pressure term that was skipped earlier is computed for both cells using Eq. 3.16, which requires the pressure area at the interface obtained via Eq. 3.15. The results are added to the respective flux vectors. Lastly, the calculated flux is registered in the storage vectors:

$$\mathbf{q}_{\text{adv}_L}^n = \mathbf{q}_L^n - \frac{\Delta t}{A_L} \mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_{k,L}}^n l_k \quad (5.4)$$

$$\mathbf{q}_{\text{adv}_R}^n = \mathbf{q}_R^n + \frac{\Delta t}{A_R} \mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_{k,R}}^n l_k \quad (5.5)$$

5.4.2.2. HLLC Riemann solver When using the approximate Riemann solver instead of the Fully Upwind Method, variables have to be reconstructed at the edge of interest. The user has the choice between a first-order accurate reconstruction or a second-order accurate reconstruction via the MUSCL approach or Central approach, which means that the flux calculation function must know which approach is taken. On a programming level, a simple conditional statement would be an appropriate solution to this issue. However, since the flux calculation is carried out for each edge and time step, unnecessary branching should be avoided, as it can diminish the computational performance through mispredictions (Intel Corporation, 2021). `hms++` solves this problem by adopting conditional statements that are evaluated at compile-time. This is done via an `if constexpr` statement, introduced in C++17 (ISO/IEC, 2017), which discards the false statement and only compiles the true statement. On a compilation level, this results in multiple flux calculation functions, each featuring a different reconstruction approach. On a programming level, however, the only difference is the `constexpr` specifier that is added to the conditional statement. This way the query for the spatial accuracy of the reconstruction is only answered once per time step instead of once per time step and cell. The sequence of instructions and actions for the HLLC Riemann solver is depicted as a flow chart in Fig. 5.12. The approximate solution to the Riemann problem and

Figure 5.12: HLLC Riemann solver for a mandated edge traversal.

reconstruction approaches mentioned in the following descriptions are explained in detail in subsequent paragraphs. After passing an initial dryness check, an empty struct is declared, which will hold the reconstructed values at the edge. A subsequent compile-time conditional statement controls whether the edge values are to be reconstructed with first-order accuracy or not. If a second-order accurate reconstruction approach is chosen, a runtime conditional statement checks if one of the cells is dry or Murillo's condition (Murillo et al., 2006) is not fulfilled, the latter is expressed as:

$$\max(d_{\text{cell},L}, d_{\text{cell},R}) - \min(d_{\text{cell},L}, d_{\text{cell},R}) > \min(d_{\text{cell},L}, d_{\text{cell},R}) \quad (5.6)$$

If so, the algorithm reverts to a first-order accurate reconstruction. Otherwise, another compile-time conditional statement checks if the reconstruction is carried out via the MUSCL scheme or the Central approach. After the successful reconstruction, both reconstructed water depths must be greater than the dryness threshold, otherwise the computation is aborted and the algorithm moves on to calculate the source terms. Subsequently, the reconstructed values are used to calculate the flux by solving the Riemann problem at the edge approximatively, detailed in Sec. 3.3.3, with the result duplicated into the flux vectors $\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_{k,L}}$ and $\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_{k,R}}$ for the left and right cell, respectively. In a next step, the slope source term \mathbf{F}_B is computed for either side, by solving Eqs. 3.49 and 3.52, with the result added on to the advective flux vectors of the left and right cell. Then, the result is multiplied with the time step, divided by cell area and added to the storage vectors of the interfacing cells:

$$\mathbf{q}_{\text{adv+bed}_L}^n = \mathbf{q}_L^n - \frac{\Delta t}{A_L} (\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_{k,L}}^n + \mathbf{F}_{B_L}^n) l_k \quad (5.7)$$

$$\mathbf{q}_{\text{adv+bed}_R}^n = \mathbf{q}_R^n + \frac{\Delta t}{A_R} (\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_{k,R}}^n + \mathbf{F}_{B_R}^n) l_k \quad (5.8)$$

with the storage vectors $\mathbf{q}_{\text{adv+bed}_L}^n$ and $\mathbf{q}_{\text{adv+bed}_R}^n$ now containing the sum of the original storage and the results of the flux and slope source calculation.

First-order accurate reconstruction The procedure of a first-order accurate reconstruction of edge values is illustrated in Fig. 5.13. Reconstructed variables at the edge are denoted by the index k . The water depth and flow velocity at the edge are equal to the respective cell value if the cell is wet, otherwise, they are set to zero. After this dryness check, the edge values of the water depth along with the cell values of the bottom

Figure 5.13: First-order accurate reconstruction in HLLC Riemann solver. Black bars indicate parallel processing.

elevation are used to reconstruct the water elevation at the edge for both sides:

$$h_{k,L} = d_{k,L} + z_L \quad (5.9)$$

$$h_{k,R} = d_{k,R} + z_R \quad (5.10)$$

In a next step, the edge values of the water depth and bottom elevation undergo the hydrostatic reconstruction, described in Sec. 3.3.4. The reconstructed bottom elevation is obtained by solving Eq. 3.32 and is subsequently used to modify the reconstructed water depths at the edge via Eq. 3.33. This concludes the first-order accurate reconstruction and the finalised values are returned to the solver.

MUSCL scheme Next to the variables of the interfacing cells, a second-order accurate reconstruction via the MUSCL scheme also utilises the variables of the second neighbours, which are denoted by the indices *LL* and *RR* for the left and right side, respectively. Since the water elevation and specific discharges are to be reconstructed at the edge as well, their cell values for the interfacing cells and their second neighbours are computed first:

$$h_{\text{cell}} = d_{\text{cell}} + z_{\text{cell}} \quad (5.11)$$

$$\mathbf{q}_{\text{cell}} = \begin{bmatrix} q_{\text{cell},x} \\ q_{\text{cell},y} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} u_{\text{cell}} d_{\text{cell}} \\ v_{\text{cell}} d_{\text{cell}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.12)$$

Next, the edge values for the water depth and water elevation are calculated via Eqs. 3.36 and 3.37. The resulting values are subsequently used to reconstruct the bottom elevation at the edge:

$$z_{k,L} = h_{k,L} - d_{k,L} \quad (5.13)$$

$$z_{k,R} = h_{k,R} - d_{k,R} \quad (5.14)$$

This is followed by a dryness check for the left and right edge value of the water depth. If it is above the threshold value, the edge values for the flow velocity are computed by reconstructing the specific discharges and dividing the result by the reconstructed water

Figure 5.14: Second-order accurate reconstruction in HLLC Riemann solver via the MUSCL scheme. Black bars indicate parallel processing.

depth of the respective side of the edge:

$$\mathbf{v}_{k,L} = \frac{\mathbf{q}_{k,L}}{d_{k,L}} \quad (5.15)$$

$$\mathbf{v}_{k,R} = \frac{\mathbf{q}_{k,R}}{d_{k,R}} \quad (5.16)$$

On the other hand, if the reconstructed water depth is dry, it is set to zero, along with the edge values of the flow velocity. Additionally, the reconstructed water elevation is modified by setting it to the edge value of the bottom elevation.

Finally, the hydrostatic reconstruction of the bottom elevation and water depth is performed in the same way as it is done in the first-order accurate reconstruction. The finalised edge values are returned to the solver.

Central approach The *Central* approach achieves a second-order accurate reconstruction of the variables at the edge by utilising a central differencing scheme. The procedure is detailed in Fig. 5.15. Unlike the MUSCL approach, the Central approach only involves the interfacing cells at the edge. The approach begins by computing the cell values of the water elevation for the left and right cell via Eq. 5.11. Subsequently, the edge values for the water elevation, water depth and bottom elevation are reconstructed by averaging the cell values of the left and right side, which yields a single reconstructed value per variable accomodating both cells at the interface:

$$d_{k,L} = d_{k,R} = d_k = \frac{1}{2}(d_L + d_R) \quad (5.17)$$

$$h_{k,L} = h_{k,R} = h_k = \frac{1}{2}(h_L + h_R) \quad (5.18)$$

$$z_{k,L} = z_{k,R} = z_k = h_k - d_k \quad (5.19)$$

If the reconstructed water depth is dry, it is set to zero, along with the edge value for the flow velocity. In this case, the water elevation is set equal to the bottom elevation. Should the edge value of the water depth be greater than the dryness threshold, the cell values of the specific discharge are computed for both sides. The results are used to reconstruct the edge value of the specific discharge via averaging, followed by a division by the reconstructed water depth to obtain the edge value of the flow velocity. These steps are consolidated into one step, as the reconstructed flow velocity is the only variable

that is required for further computations:

$$\mathbf{v}_{k,L} = \mathbf{v}_{k,R} = \mathbf{v}_k = \frac{0.5(\mathbf{q}_L + \mathbf{q}_R)}{d_k} = \frac{0.5(\mathbf{v}_L d_L + \mathbf{v}_R d_R)}{d_k} \quad (5.20)$$

Figure 5.15: Second-order accurate reconstruction in HLLC Riemann solver via the Central method.

Subsequently, the edge values of the variables are returned to be utilised in the approximate solution to the Riemann problem.

Approximate solution to the Riemann problem The procedure of the flux calculation via the HLLC Riemann solver is illustrated in Fig. 5.16.

Figure 5.16: Solving the Riemann problem approximately.

After the edge values of the variables are obtained via one of the approaches described above, the reconstructed water depths undergo a final dryness check, which leads to a

cancellation of the flux computation if both values are below the threshold. Otherwise, the flux calculation continues. As described in Sec. 3.3, the flux is computed by approximately solving a one-dimensional Riemann problem at the edge. In order to obtain a one-dimensional view on the Riemann problem independent of the edge orientation, the reconstructed flow velocities are transformed into normal/tangential direction of the edge by applying a rotational matrix to them:

$$\mathbf{v}_{\text{rot}} = \begin{bmatrix} v_{\perp} \\ v_{\parallel} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} n_x & n_y \\ -n_y & n_x \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_k \\ v_k \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.21)$$

with n_x and n_y denoting components of the the normal vector and v_{\perp} and v_{\parallel} representing the flow velocities perpendicular and parallel to the edge. In a next step, the wave speeds for the left and right state of the Riemann problem are obtained via Eq. 3.25. Then, the estimations for the normal flow velocity and wave speed in the intermediate state that opens up in between the left and right state are computed by solving Eqs. 3.25 and 3.27. The results are used to obtain the left and right wave speed approximations, connecting the left and right state to the intermediate state, via Eqs. 3.23 and 3.24. It must be noted that the flow velocities involved in the computation of the wave speed approximations are the normal flow velocities obtained of Eq. 5.21. A subsequent conditional statement determines whether the flux is determined from values based on the intermediate state or not. If so, a wave speed approximation for the intermediate state is computed by solving Eq. 3.28 with the sign determining which flux vector of Eq. 3.31 is computed. Otherwise, the sign of the left wave speed approximation determines if the flux is based on the left or right initial state of the Riemann problem, given by 3.29. However, these corresponding flux equations are not applicable on edges with an arbitrary orientation, which can be employed if the **StructMesh**-type, see Fig. 5.1, or an unstructured mesh is used. To change this, the determined flux vector is set up in normal direction of the edge, replacing the involved flow velocities in x- and y-direction with the normal and tangential components of Eq. 5.21, respectively, which yields the following transformed flux vectors for the left and right states:

$$\mathbf{f}_l^{\text{tf}} = \begin{bmatrix} v_{\perp l} d_l \\ v_{\perp l}^2 d_l + \frac{1}{2} g d_l^2 \\ v_{\perp l} v_{\parallel l} d_l \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{f}_r^{\text{tf}} = \begin{bmatrix} v_{\perp r} d_r \\ v_{\perp r}^2 d_r + \frac{1}{2} g d_r^2 \\ v_{\perp r} v_{\parallel r} d_r \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.22)$$

If the flux is based on the values of the intermediate state, it is now computed as

$$\mathbf{f}_m^{\text{tf}} = \frac{S_r \mathbf{f}_l^{\text{tf}} - S_l \mathbf{f}_r^{\text{tf}} + S_r S_l (\mathbf{q}_r^{\text{tf}} - \mathbf{q}_l^{\text{tf}})}{S_r - S_l} \quad (5.23)$$

in which \mathbf{q}_l^{tf} and \mathbf{q}_r^{tf} denote the transformed storage vectors of the left and right cell, respectively:

$$\mathbf{q}^{\text{tf}} = \begin{bmatrix} d \\ v_{\perp} d \\ v_{\parallel} d \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.24)$$

The flux vectors of the left and right parts of the intermediate region are:

$$\mathbf{f}_{ml}^{\text{tf}} = \begin{bmatrix} f_{m,1}^{\text{tf}} \\ f_{m,2}^{\text{tf}} \\ v_{\parallel l} f_{m,1}^{\text{tf}} \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{f}_{mr}^{\text{tf}} = \begin{bmatrix} f_{m,1}^{\text{tf}} \\ f_{m,2}^{\text{tf}} \\ v_{\parallel r} f_{m,1}^{\text{tf}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.25)$$

Furthermore, the resulting flux vector is retransformed into the global coordinate system by applying the inverse of the rotational matrix:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{adv}_k}^n \mathbf{n}_k = \mathbf{T}^{-1} \mathbf{f}_k^{\text{tf,hllc}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & n_x & -n_y \\ 0 & n_y & n_x \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_1^{\text{tf}} \\ f_2^{\text{tf}} \\ f_3^{\text{tf}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_1^{\text{tf}} \\ n_x f_2^{\text{tf}} - n_y f_3^{\text{tf}} \\ n_y f_2^{\text{tf}} + n_x f_3^{\text{tf}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.26)$$

in which $\mathbf{f}_k^{\text{tf,hllc}}$ is the case equation for the flux vectors of Eqs. 5.22 and 5.25, analogous to Eq. 3.22. This completes the computation of the advective flux and the algorithm moves on to the calculation of the source/sink terms.

5.4.3. Calculate sources

Mass sources and sinks A separate field accounts for the mass sources and sinks, holding a storage array sized after the number of domain cells. After the advective flux is calculated and registered, the storage vectors for the left and right cell hold the sum of the initial storage, the advective flux and the transformed slope source term, as written in Eqs. 5.7 and 5.8. In this step, mass source/sink of each cell is multiplied with Δt and

is added to the first component of the storage vector:

$$\mathbf{q}_{\text{adv+bed+src}}^n = \mathbf{q}_{\text{adv+bed}}^n + \begin{bmatrix} (r-i)\Delta t \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.27)$$

with r and i denoting the mass sources and sinks, respectively. As of the time of writing, the momentum sources and sinks are not implemented.

The computation is parallelised by utilising an `omp parallel for` construct, with each thread receiving a workload in form of contiguous rows of cells.

Friction sources The influence of friction is considered as described in Sec. 3.5, whereby only the momentum balance equations are of interest since friction does not influence the mass balance directly. In a first step, the preconditioning factor D of the splitting method is calculated by solving Eq. 3.57. Only the flux, slope source and mass source/sink terms are preconditioned, as seen in Eq. 3.56, however, these terms are already added to the initial storage vector which is why the latter is computed anew:

$$\mathbf{q}^n = \begin{bmatrix} u^n d^n \\ v^n d^n \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.28)$$

and then subtracted from the current momentum storage:

$$\mathbf{q}_{\text{dif}}^n = \mathbf{q}_{\text{adv+bed+src}}^n - \mathbf{q}^n \quad (5.29)$$

which yields the isolated sum of the flux, slope source and mass source terms. Next, the friction term \mathbf{s}_f of Eqs. 2.4 is multiplied with the time step Δt and subtracted from $\mathbf{q}_{\text{dif}}^n$. This is followed by the multiplication with the inverse of Eq. 3.57 to fully perform the splitting method. The result is then added back to \mathbf{q}^n , resulting in a storage vector on the new time level:

$$\mathbf{q}^{n+1} = \mathbf{q}^n + \frac{1}{D}(\mathbf{q}_{\text{dif}}^n - \Delta t \mathbf{s}_f^n) \quad (5.30)$$

The workload is shared via an `omp parallel` construct, identical to the parallelisation employed in the computation of the mass sources.

5.4.4. Calculate new state variables

In this step, the primitive and state variables that are required for the evolution of the solution for the subsequent time step are computed. These include the field of the water depth and flow velocity as well as the storage vector \mathbf{q}^{n+1} of Eq. 5.30, which serves as the initial storage vector for the next loop iteration, after it undergoes some modifications first. The first component of the \mathbf{q}^{n+1} remains untouched and is copied into the storage array of the field that represents the water depth. To update the flow velocity field for the next loop iteration, the specific discharges of \mathbf{q}^{n+1} are divided by the water depth and copied into the field's storage array:

$$u = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } d < d_{\min} \\ q_2/q_1 & \text{if } d \geq d_{\min} \end{cases} \quad v = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } d < d_{\min} \\ q_3/q_1 & \text{if } d \geq d_{\min} \end{cases} \quad (5.31)$$

Afterwards, the specific discharges in \mathbf{q}^{n+1} are reevaluated under the notion of the minimum water depth:

$$q_2 = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } d < d_{\min} \\ q_2 & \text{if } d \geq d_{\min} \end{cases} \quad q_3 = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } d < d_{\min} \\ q_3 & \text{if } d \geq d_{\min} \end{cases} \quad (5.32)$$

with q_1 , q_2 and q_3 denoting the components of \mathbf{q}^{n+1} . The procedure is parallelised in an identical way to the calculation of the mass source/sink terms. This finalises the computation for the domain cells for a single step in the evolution of the solution.

5.4.5. Update boundaries

In order for the boundary conditions to function properly on the next time step of the algorithm, the ghost cell values have to be updated. This is done by calling the update function, provided by each boundary condition, to update the water depth and flow velocity in the ghost cells, as described in Sec. 3.6.

Updating the boundaries is parallelised through the use of an `omp parallel for construct` with a single thread updating all boundary conditions for an assigned patch of cells.

After completing this step, the algorithm has completed a full iteration of the algorithm described in Fig. 5.10.

5.5. Traversal patterns

This section covers the traversal patterns, which dictate the order in which the edges or cells of the computational domain are traversed for the flux calculation. As described in Sec. 5.4.2, traversing the edges of a computational domain results in roughly half as many flux calculations in comparison to a cell traversal, which is why `hms++` focuses on edge traversal patterns, although a cell-traversal approach is implemented as well.

One aspect of the edge-wise traversal of the domain that must not be neglected is the possibility of race conditions that may occur during the registration of the flux calculation results. Since the traversal is parallelised, a situation may arise in which two threads simultaneously write into the same memory location, leading to indeterminate values (OpenMP Architecture Review Board, 2015). Fig. 5.17 illustrates this in an example in which cell 14 is bordered by edges 5 and 9. Both edges calculate a flux for cell 14 and update the latter's storage vector simultaneously, provoking a race condition, if the involved threads are not synchronised accordingly.

Figure 5.17: Possible race condition due to concurrent flux calculation for edges bounding the same cell.

The edge traversal strategies in `hms++` avoid this situation in one of two ways.

Either the traversal strategy itself lets the situation occur but the updating of the storage vector is encapsulated in an `omp atomic update` construct, or the pattern ensures thread-safety on the level of the traversal, i.e. affected edges are only traversed when the other edges that target the same memory location in their flux calculation have already been traversed. The consecutive traversal of these concerned edges resembles the process of

stitching or seaming two disconnected parts together, which is why the words 'seamed' and 'seamless' are used as part of the names of the traversal patterns in Secs. 5.5.2 to 5.5.5.

Since this investigation only covers traversal strategies for flux calculations that aim for second-order accuracy in space, it is noteworthy that if a MUSCL reconstruction approach is taken, not every edge receives the same reconstructive treatment. Consider a cell located at the boundary interfacing a ghost cell. If following a MUSCL approach, the calculation of the smoothness monitor in Eqs. 3.39 to 3.41 uses values from the interfacing cells as well as their second neighbours, as illustrated in Fig. 3.8. However, for cells directly located at the boundary, there is no second neighbour in direction of the interfacing ghost cell. One option would be to reconstruct the edge values with first-order accuracy since it only requires values from the interfacing cells, although this approach leads to an unnatural accumulation of mass in cells where the bed elevation is sloping in proximity of the boundary (Simons, 2020). To avoid this, `hms++` employs the same strategy that is implemented in `hms-java`.

Near the boundary, the flow field and bottom topography is assumed to be smooth so that reconstructed variables at the boundary edge as well as at its neighbouring edge in direction of the domain do not require the intended slope limitation of a complete MUSCL reconstruction. Variables at these edges are reconstructed with second-order accuracy via the Central approach, also described in Sec. 5.4.2, while the MUSCL approach is employed for the remaining edges in the domain, as shown in Fig. 5.18.

Figure 5.18: Utilised reconstruction approaches depending on edge locations with active MUSCL reconstruction.

In `hms-java`, this strategy is implemented by utilising a conditional statement concerning the location of the respective edge. This eases the implementation of the traversal pattern

but it also introduces a conditional statement that is evaluated for each edge and time step. `hms++` solves this issue by simply calling the flux calculation function with the correct reconstruction scheme for the specific edges. This is possible since edges are globally indexed, as seen in Fig. 5.2b, and the mesh representation provides functions to access the necessary topological information.

5.5.1. Ordered edge traversal

```

1 // helpful variables
2 int nx = number of cells in x-direction
3 int ny = number of cells in y-direction
4 int nh = number of horizontal edges
5
6 // open up a parallel region
7 #pragma omp parallel {
8
9     // traverse horizontal edges
10    #pragma omp for schedule (static) nowait
11    for (int edge = 0; edge < 2*nx; edge++ )
12        // central edges, see Fig. 5.19a
13
14    #pragma omp for schedule (static) nowait
15    for(int edge = 2*nx; edge < nh-2*nx; edge++)
16        // MUSCL edges, see Fig. 5.19b
17
18    #pragma omp for schedule (static) nowait
19    for (int edge = nh-2*nx; edge < nh; edge++ )
20        // central edges, see Fig 5.19c
21
22    // traverse vertical edges
23    #pragma omp for schedule (static) nowait
24    for( int row = 0; row < ny; row++ ){
25        // see Fig. 5.19d
26        // 2 central edges on the left
27        // MUSCL edges in the middle
28        // 2 central edges on the right.
29    }
30 }
```

Code 6: Ordered traversal scheme.

Mentioned line numbers in this section are referencing Code 6. In this pattern, the order of the indices defines the traversal of the edges, as illustrated in Fig. 5.2b. As seen in line 7, the traversal begins with the opening of an `omp parallel` region. This creates a team of threads that share the workload of the traversal. Inside the parallel region, the pattern begins with the horizontal edges being traversed in three separate loops, all of them parallelised through the use of `omp for` constructs, as seen in lines 10 to 20. Each

construct is appended by a `nowait` clause allowing finished threads to proceed to the next task. The first loop covers the central edges at the bottom boundary, illustrated in Fig. 5.19a. The second processes the MUSCL edges in the middle, see Fig. 5.19b, while the third loop is taking on the central edges at the top boundary, as seen in Fig. 5.19c. Subsequently, the algorithm proceeds to traverse the vertical edges by looping through the rows of cells. The workload is shared through parallelising the outer loop, therefore distributing the rows among the threads, as seen in lines 23 and 24. As this traversal pattern does not prevent the occurrence of race conditions, the flux registration utilises the `omp atomic` construct, forcing the storage vector to be updated in consecutive fashion.

(a) Horizontal bottom edges in first two rows.

(b) Horizontal edges in middle rows.

(c) Horizontal edges in top row.

(d) Vertical edges in first and last column use Central approach while MUSCL approach is applied in middle columns.

Figure 5.19: Ordered traversal pattern for exemplary mesh with $n_x = 6$ and $n_y = 6$. Red indicates the Central approach, green denotes MUSCL approach. Black edges are already done and dotted edges are still to be traversed.

5.5.2. Seamless row-wise traversal

```

1 // helpful variables
2 int nx = number of cells in x-direction
3 int ny = number of cells in y-direction
4
5 // open up a parallel region
6 #pragma omp parallel
7 {
8     #pragma omp for schedule(static) nowait
9     for (int row = 0; row < 2; row++ ){
10         // first two rows, see Fig. 5.20a
11     }
12
13     #pragma omp for schedule(static) nowait
14     for (int row=2; row<ny-1; row++ ){
15         // middle rows, see Fig. 5.20b
16     }
17
18     #pragma omp single nowait
19     // last row, see Fig. 5.20c
20 }

```

Code 7: Seamless row-wise traversal.

In this section, the mentioned line numbers refer to Code 7 if not stated otherwise. The ordered edge traversal pattern, described in Sec. 5.5.1 may feature suboptimal cache memory exploitation. Since the pattern starts with the traversal of horizontal edges, the corresponding cache lines of the four used cells are loaded into cache, as illustrated in Fig. 5.9c. Then, the traversal moves on into topological x-direction to traverse subsequent horizontal edges. However, for large enough meshes, the four initial cache lines will be evicted from cache memory before the traversal pattern comes around to traverse the vertical edges on these cache lines. So when the time comes to traverse these vertical edges, their cache lines have to be reloaded into cache accompanied by the computational overhead of the memory access.

The seamless row-wise traversal tries to improve the cache exploitation of the ordered edge traversal by reusing a part of the cached memory. Instead of traversing the horizontal edges first and vertical edges second, the seamless row-wise traversal pattern loops through the rows of cells of the domain and traverses their vertical and bottom edges in an alternating fashion.

Worksharing is done via an `omp parallel` region that is opened in the beginning of the traversal, see line 6. The traversal of the rows is split up into three different parts. The first part consists of the first two rows at the bottom that feature central edges at the

bottom, as seen in Fig. 5.20a. An `omp for` construct ensures that each row is processed by a single thread, as seen in line 8. The next part comprises the subsequent rows, except for the last row, as they feature MUSCL edges at the bottom, displayed in Fig. 5.20b. Similar to the first two rows, the parallelisation is handled via an `omp for` construct, see line 13. Since the last row features central bottom and top edges, it is processed in a third part, depicted in Fig. 5.20c. An `omp single` construct is used to ensure that a single thread is handling the workload, as seen in line 18. Every utilised `omp` construct is appended by the `nowait` clause to allow finished or unused threads to move on to the next instruction to handle the three parts of the traversal in parallel. As with the ordered edge traversal, simultaneous write operations on the memory location of the storage vector are prevented by an atomic flux registration, as the traversal pattern does not ensure thread-safety on its own.

Figure 5.20: Seamless row-wise traversal pattern for exemplary mesh with $n_x = 6$ and $n_y = 6$. Red indicates the Central approach, green denotes MUSCL approach. Black edges are already done and dotted edges are still to be traversed.

5.5.3. Seamed row-wise traversal

```

1 // helpful variables
2 int nx = number of cells in x-direction
3 int ny = number of cells in y-direction
4
5 // open up a parallel region
6 #pragma omp parallel
7 {
8     #pragma omp sections
9     {
10        #pragma omp section
11        {
12            // first two rows, see Fig. 5.21a
13        }
14        #pragma omp section
15        {
16            // last row including top boundary, see Fig. 5.21a
17        }
18    }
19    #pragma omp for schedule (static)
20    for ( int row=2; row<ny-1; row+=2 )
21        // every second row, see Fig. 5.21b
22
23    #pragma omp for schedule (static)
24    for ( int row=3; row<ny-1; row+=2 )
25        // every skipped row, see Fig. 5.21c
26 }

```

Code 8: Seamless row-wise traversal pattern.

Mentioned line numbers in this section are referencing Code 8. A modified version of the seamless row-wise traversal pattern is presented, which prevents the race conditions of Fig. 5.17 on the level of the traversal, ensuring thread-safety in the process. This way the computational overhead of the `omp atomic` construct can be avoided (Bull, 2002), however, the approach is not as parallelisable since the concerned edges, whose flux calculation leads to a potential race condition, have to be traversed sequentially. The processing of edges inside a row is identical to the seamless row-wise traversal, described in Sec. 5.5.2.

Line 6 sees the opening of a parallel region via the `omp parallel` construct, creating a team of threads to share the workload.

Similar to the seamless row-wise approach, the traversal is split into three parts. The first part comprises the first two rows and the last row, including the top boundary edges, as illustrated in Fig. 5.21a. An `omp sections` construct is employed to traverse these rows in parallel, as depicted in lines 8 to 18. The next part consists of the rows in between, as

illustrated in Fig. 5.21b, although, only every second row is traversed in order to keep the traversal thread-safe. Afterwards, the skipped rows are traversed, as seen in Fig. 5.21c. This is easily realised via two for-loops, as seen in lines 20 and 24. The iteration variables represent consecutive rows and are incremented by two. The workload of both parts is distributed among the thread via two `omp for` constructs, as seen in lines 19 and 23. The traversal begins by processing the first two rows and the last row of cells, which includes the top boundary of the domain, as seen in Fig. 5.21a. An `omp sections` construct is utilised to distribute the rows between two threads, as seen in lines 8 to 18.

Figure 5.21: Seamed row-wise traversal pattern for exemplary mesh with $n_x = 6$ and $n_y = 6$. Red indicates the Central approach, green denotes MUSCL approach. Black edges are already done and dotted edges are still to be traversed.

5.5.4. Seamless block-wise traversal

```

1 // helpful variables
2 int blocksize = square root of the number of cells per block
3 int nBlocksX  = no. of blocks in x-direction, excl. remainder blocks
4 int nBlocksY  = no. of blocks in y-direction, excl. remainder blocks
5
6 // open up a parallel region
7 #pragma omp parallel {
8   if ( remaining cells in x- and y direction exist ) {
9     #pragma omp single nowait
10    // bottom remainder block on the right, see Fig. 5.23a
11
12    #pragma omp for schedule(static) nowait
13    for(int by = 1; by < nBlocksY; ++by)
14      // remainder blocks on the right after the first one,
15      // see Fig. 5.23b
16
17    #pragma omp single nowait
18    // left remainder block at the top, see Fig. 5.23c
19
20    #pragma omp for schedule(static) nowait
21    for(int bx = 1; bx < nBlocksX; ++bx)
22      // top remainder blocks after the first one, see Fig. 5.23d
23
24    #pragma omp single nowait
25    // remainder block in top right corner, see Fig. 5.23e
26
27    #pragma omp single nowait
28    // lower left block, see Fig. 5.23f
29
30    #pragma omp for schedule(static) nowait
31    for(int bx = 1; bx < nBlocksX; ++bx)
32      // bottom blocks after the first one, see Fig. 5.23g
33
34    #pragma omp for schedule(static) nowait
35    for(int by = 1; by < nBlocksY; ++by)
36      // blocks on the left after the first one, see Fig. 5.23h
37
38    #pragma omp for schedule(static) collapse(2) nowait
39    for(int by = 1; by < nBlocksY; ++by)
40      for(int bx = 1; bx < nBlocksX; ++bx)
41        // blocks in the middle, see Fig. 5.23i
42  }
43 else ... // only one case is presented here.
44 }

```

Code 9: Seamless block-wise traversal.

Any line mentions in this section are referencing Code 9. While the row-wise traversal patterns reuse cached data for the traversal of edges on the same row, they do not fully

Figure 5.22: Distribution of 5×6 blocks among four threads, without remainder blocks. Arrows indicate the monotonic order of processing.

reuse cache lines above and below the current row before these are potentially evicted from cache memory. The seamless block-wise traversal pattern attempts to further improve the reuse of cached data by subdividing the mesh into tiles or blocks of cells and let the algorithm fully traverse the edges of these blocks instead of operating on rows. This way, the edges on cache lines that are above or below the current row are traversed, reusing the cached memory in the process (Lam et al., 1991).

The size of the tile is stated as its square root, e.g. a block size of 10 represents a 10×10 block, consisting of 100 cells in total. Before the traversal begins, the number of blocks in each direction is calculated, with the remaining cells collected in smaller remainder blocks. Afterwards, a conditional statement has to be evaluated, as seen in Code 9, line 8, since the traversal must be adjusted according to the potential existence of remainder blocks, e.g. if there are no remainder blocks at the top boundary, the local blocks there feature central edges and have to be processed differently than a block that fully consists of MUSCL edges. For the sake of readability, a single case in which remainder blocks exist in x- and y-direction is presented here. The traversal begins by opening an `omp parallel` region to create the team of threads sharing the workload. A block is traversed row-wise in a manner similar to the row-wise traversal patterns.

At first the remainder blocks on the right are traversed, as illustrated in Figs. 5.23a and 5.23b. The arrangement of central edges in the lower-right remainder block calls for an isolated processing via an `omp single` construct, as seen in line 9. The other remainder blocks on the right are distributed among the threads through an `omp for` construct, see line 12. The remainder blocks at the top are processed in a similar fashion, as illustrated in Figs. 5.23c and 5.23d. Again, an `omp single` construct is used for the top-left remainder block, as shown in line 17, while the other remainder blocks are distributed via an `omp for` construct, as seen in line 20. This is followed by the traversal of the top right corner block via an `omp single` construct, as seen in Fig. 5.23e. Next, the

lower-left block is processed, also using a `omp single` construct, illustrated in Fig. 5.23f, followed by the traversal of the blocks at the bottom boundary and the left boundary, distributed through `omp for` constructs, as seen in line 30 and 34. At last, the blocks in the middle are traversed, viewed in Fig. 5.23i. The matrix-like arrangement of the blocks calls for a nested for-loop, using the `collapse`-clause on the `omp for` construct, as seen in line 38, to improve the parallelisation.

Every parallelisation construct is appended by the `nowait` clause to allow all blocks to be processed in parallel.

Due to the `collapse(2)` clause and the `static` work schedule, each thread gets to work on contiguous blocks in x-direction, monotonically. This results in a thread traversing the blocks in order of the iterations,. Fig. 5.22 illustrates an exemplary distribution of 5×6 blocks among four threads.

Since the traversal itself does not guarantee thread-safety during the updating of the storage vectors, the approach utilises the atomic flux registration, already employed by the ordered edge traversal.

Figure 5.23: Seamless block-wise traversal pattern for exemplary mesh with $nx = 14$ and $ny = 14$, with a blocksize of 4. Red indicates the Central approach, green denotes MUSCL approach. Black edges are already traversed, dotted edges are still to be traversed. Pink dotted frames indicate blocks.

5.5.5. Seamed block-wise traversal

Mentioned line numbers in this section are referencing Code 10. Similar to the seamless row-wise traversal approach, a modified version of the seamless block-wise traversal pattern is presented in which potential race conditions that can occur during the flux registration are avoided on the level of the traversal.

To keep the blocking implementation as simple as possible, i.e. all blocks should only feature MUSCL edges to avoid the inconvenience of distinguishing between blocks comprised of varying edges, the outer rim, consisting of central edges that frame MUSCL edges in between them, is handled first. Afterwards the remaining MUSCL edges are subdivided into blocks and potential remainder blocks.

Like the other traversal patterns, the traversal begins by opening a parallel region. The vertical central edges in the left and right column of the domain are processed. An `omp single nowait` construct is used for the first and second vertical edge located at the bottom-left, see line 10. Then, an `omp for` construct, also appended by a `nowait` clause, loops through the rows, starting at the second bottom row, to traverse the last two vertical edges of the previous and the first two edges of the current row, as seen in line 13. This way, a single loop iteration features only contiguous data, possibly increasing cache hits. Another `omp single` construct is utilised to traverse the last two vertical edges at the top right. The result is visualised in Fig. 5.24a.

Afterwards, the threads gather at an `omp barrier`, in line 21, to keep thread-safety, before moving on to traverse the horizontal edges in the left and right columns. In similar fashion to the vertical edges, two `omp single` are used to traverse the first MUSCL edge on the bottom left and last MUSCL edge on the top right, respectively, see lines 22 and 35. The horizontal edges in between are traversed in two `omp for` constructs featuring an offset arrangement of rows by skipping every other row in order to prevent race conditions, see lines 25 to 33. The results are illustrated in Figs. 5.24b and 5.24c.

Subsequently, the horizontal central edges in the top and bottom row are traversed in an `omp for` construct, as seen in line 38, and visualised in Fig. 5.24d. This is followed by the traversal of the vertical MUSCL edges in these rows via two `omp for` constructs, again using an offset arrangement, see lines 42 to 50, illustrated in Fig. 5.24f.

Now, the traversal of the blocks and remainder blocks in the center begins. Similar to the seamless block-wise traversal, the scheme begins with the remainder blocks, as seen in lines 56 to 71. These blocks are traversed via `omp for` constructs, appended by a `nowait` clause, although sparing the last blocks adjacent to the corner block since they feature an edge that can provoke a race condition if traversed. This is why these blocks

are handled in `omp single` constructs, as seen in lines 61 and 69. The traversal of these blocks is visualised in Fig. 5.24g.

Another `omp barrier` is used to avoid race conditions, followed by the traversal of the remainder block in the corner in addition to the spared edges of the adjacent remainder blocks, as seen in Fig. 5.24h.

Finally, the inner blocks are traversed via two nested loops inside an `omp for` construct appended by a `collapse(2)` clause, as seen in line 80, with a visual in Fig. 5.24i.

To avoid race conditions between the blocks, their shared edges are spared and traversed afterwards in two `omp for` constructs, as seen in lines 85 to 89. The final results is illustrated in Fig. 5.24k.

```

1 // helpful variables
2 int nx = number of cells in x-direction
3 int ny = number of cells in y-direction
4 int blocksize = square root of the number of cells per block
5 int nBlocksX = number of blocks in x-direction
6 int nBlocksY = number of blocks in y-direction
7
8 // open up a parallel region
9 #pragma omp parallel {
10 #pragma omp single nowait
11     // first two vertical edges at the bottom left, see Fig. 5.24a
12
13 #pragma omp for schedule(static) nowait
14 for(int row = 1; row<ny; row++)
15     // last two edges of previous row, first two edges of curent row,
16     // see Fig. 5.24a
17
18 #pragma omp single nowait
19     // last two vertical edges at the top right, see Fig. 5.24a
20
21 #pragma omp barrier // wait for all threads to finish
22 #pragma omp single
23     // first horizontal MUSCL edge in left column, see Fig. 5.24b
24
25 #pragma omp for schedule(static)
26 for(int row=3; row<ny-1; row += 2)
27     // every second horizontal MUSCL edge in left and right column,
28     // see Fig. 5.24b
29
30 #pragma omp for schedule(static)
31 for(int row=4; row<ny-1; row += 2)
32     // every skipped horizontal MUSCL edge in left and right column,
33     // see Fig. 5.24c
34
35 #pragma omp single
36     // last horizontal MUSCL edge in right column, see Fig. 5.24c
37
38 #pragma omp for schedule(static)
39 for(int col = 0; col<nx; col++)
40     // central edges at top and bottom row, see Fig. 5.24d
41
42 #pragma omp for schedule(static)
43 for(int col = 2; col<nx-1; col += 2)
44     // every second vertical MUSCL edge in top and bottom row,
45     // see Fig. 5.24e
46
47 #pragma omp for schedule(static)
48 for(int col = 3; col<nx-1; col += 2)
49     // every skipped vertical MUSCL edge in top and bottom row,
50     // see Fig. 5.24f
51
52 ...
53 // --> see next Code.

```

Code 10: Seamed block-wise traversal.

```

54 ...
55
56 if( remaining cells in x-direction exist ) {
57     #pragma omp for schedule(static) nowait
58     for(int by = 0; by<nBlocks.y()-1; by++)
59         // remainder blocks on the right, spare the last
60
61     #pragma omp single nowait
62     // last remainder block on the right
63 }
64 if( remaining cells in y-direction exist ) {
65     #pragma omp for schedule(static) nowait
66     for( int bx = 0; bx<nBlocks.x()-1; bx++)
67         // remainder blocks on top, spare the last
68
69     #pragma omp single nowait
70     // last remainder block on the top
71 }
72
73 #pragma omp barrier // wait for all threads to finish
74 #pragma omp single
75     if( remaining cells in x- and y-direction exist )
76         // corner block and spared edges of last vertical and horizontal
77         // remainder blocks.
78
79 #pragma omp for schedule(static) collapse(2)
80 for(int by = 0; by<nBlocksY; ++by)
81     for(int bx = 0; bx<nBlocksX; ++bx)
82         // inner blocks
83
84 #pragma omp for schedule(static)
85 for(int col = 1; col<nBlocksX; col++)
86     // shared vertical edges
87
88 #pragma omp for schedule(static)
89 for(int row = 1; col<nBlocksY; col++)
90     // shared horizontal edges
91
92 } // end of parallel region.

```

Code 10: (Cont.) Seamed block-wise traversal.

(a) Vertical edges and direct neighbours at left and right boundary.

(b) Every other horizontal edge at left and right boundary.

(c) Skipped horizontal edges at left and right boundary.

(d) Horizontal edges and direct neighbours at top and bottom boundary.

(e) Every other vertical edge at top and bottom boundary.

(f) Skipped vertical edges at top and bottom boundary.

(g) Remainder blocks in x-direction.

(h) Remainder block in top-right corner.

(i) Inner blocks.

Figure 5.24: Seamless block-wise traversal pattern for exemplary mesh with $nx = 14$ and $ny = 14$. Red indicates the Central approach, green denotes MUSCL approach. Black edges are already traversed, dotted edges are still to be traversed. Pink dotted frames indicate blocks.

Figure 5.24: (Cont.) Seamless block-wise traversal pattern for exemplary mesh with $nx = 14$ and $ny = 14$. Red indicates the Central approach, green denotes MUSCL approach. Black edges are already traversed, dotted edges are still to be traversed. Pink dotted frames indicate blocks.

5.5.6. Ordered cell traversal

An alternative to the edge-based traversal schemes is presented in which the algorithm traverses cells and issues instructions to compute the flux across each edge of the currently visited cell. Further explanations on the differences between edge-wise and cell-wise traversal schemes are given in Sec. 5.4.2.

In similar fashion to the other patterns, the parallelisation is handled via an `omp parallel` region, creating the thread team to share the workload. The order of the cell traversal is dictated by the indices of the cells, as seen in Fig. 5.25, excluding ghost cells.

Since not all cells share an arrangement of MUSCL and central edges, the traversal is split up into the processing of the first row, the second row, the middle rows, the second to last row and the last row. Furthermore, in each row the first two and last two cells are processed inside an `omp single` construct, as seen in Code 11, lines 11 and 18. The cells in between share an arrangement of edges and can be traversed via an `omp for` construct, sharing the workload in the process, detailed in Code 11, line 14.

Every `omp` construct inside the parallel region is appended with the `nowait` clause, however, unlike in some of the edge-wise traversal patterns, an atomic access to the storage vector is not necessary, since the results of the flux calculations are only registered in the currently visited cell, i.e. the memory locations of the storage vectors are only accessed by a single thread, therefore there is no risk of potential race conditions.

```
1 // helpful variables
2 int nx = number of cells in x-direction
3 int ny = number of cells in y-direction
4
5 // open up a parallel region
6 #pragma omp parallel {
7
8     // Begin with first row, see Fig. 5.25a
9     int begBottom = index of first domain cell
10
11     #pragma omp single nowait
12     // first two cells in first row
13
14     #pragma omp for schedule(static) nowait
15     for( int c = begBottom+2; c < begBottom+nx-2; c++ )
16         // middle cells in first row
17
18     #pragma omp single nowait
19     // last two cells in first row
20
21     // Continue with second row, see Fig. 5.25b
22     begBottom++;
23
24     #pragma omp single nowait
25     // first two cells in second row
26
27     #pragma omp for schedule(static) nowait
28     for( int c = begBottom+2; c < begBottom+nx-2; c++ )
29         // middle cells in second row
30
31     #pragma omp single nowait
32     // last two cells in second row
33
34     // Continue with rows in the middle, see Fig. 5.25c
35     #pragma omp for schedule(static) nowait
36     for (int row=2; row < ny-2; row++)
37         // traverse middle rows
38
39     ... // --> see next Code.
```

Code 11: Ordered cell traversal scheme.

```
1  ...
2
3  // Continue with second to last row, see Fig. 5.25d
4  int begTop = first cell in second to last row
5  #pragma omp single nowait
6      // first two cells in second to last row
7
8  #pragma omp for schedule(static) nowait
9  for(int c = begTop+2; c<begTop+nx-2; c++)
10     // middle cells in second to last row
11
12 #pragma omp single nowait
13     // last two cells in second to last row
14
15 // finish with last row, see Fig. 5.25e
16 begTop++;
17
18 #pragma omp single nowait
19     // first two cells in last row
20
21 #pragma omp for schedule(static) nowait
22 for( int c = begTop+2; c < begTop+nx-2; c++ )
23     // middle cells in last row
24
25 #pragma omp single nowait
26     // last two cells in last row
27 }
```

Code 11: (Cont.) Ordered cell traversal scheme.

Figure 5.25: Ordered cell traversal pattern for exemplary mesh with $nx = 8$ and $ny = 8$. Red indicates the Central approach, green denotes MUSCL approach. Black edges are already done and dotted edges are still to be traversed. Ghost cells are marked in green.

6. Model verification

Before benchmarking the computational performance of `hms++`, the model needs to be verification ensuring that the implementation of the numerical scheme produces correct results and the programmed logic does not contain any errors. The application of the scheme is tested for two cases already used to verify `hms-java` in Simons (2020). The first test case, presented in Sec. 6.1, consists of a one-dimensional dam break scenario and the results are compared to those of an exact Riemann solver, which is implemented in `hms-java`. As a second test case, a two-dimensional rainfall runoff is simulated and compared to an analytical solution, as seen in Sec. 6.2.

6.1. One-dimensional dam break

In order to verify the model’s ability to handle discontinuous initial conditions, two scenarios of a simplified dam break in one dimension are simulated and compared to the results of an exact Riemann solver implemented in `hms-java`. The exact solution has been computed through 50 iterations of the Newton-Raphson-Method. Simulations are carried out in a frictionless domain of 20 m length and 2 m width, discretised into 16000 square cells with an edge length of 0.05 m. It features a flat bottom topography throughout the domain and is bound by slip walls. The initial discontinuity in water depth is located in the middle of the domain, splitting it up into an upstream area with an initial water depth of 4 m and a downstream area, exhibiting 1 m of initial water depth for the wet bed case. There is no initial flow velocity and the simulation is run until an emerging wave reaches the end of the domain. The implemented discretisation schemes for the advective flux are compared, namely the Fully Upwind Method, an HLLC Riemann solver with first-order accurate reconstruction as well as the latter employing a TVD MUSCL approach with the minmod limiter function, described in Eq. 3.42, to achieve second-order accuracy. The time steps are computed in respect to the Courant number, which is set to $Cr = 0.3$. A qualitative comparison of water depth and flow velocities is illustrated in Figs. 6.1 and 6.2. Furthermore, a more quantitative comparison is done between the exact solution and flux schemes by computing the L^1 -norm of the area-weighted mean absolute error (MAE) for the water depth levels, which can be viewed in Tabs. 6.1 and 6.2. The L^1 -norm is useful to discuss the numerical diffusion that is inevitably introduced by the discretisation schemes:

$$L^1(\text{MAE}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (A_i \cdot |d_i^{\text{exact}} - d_i^{\text{simulated}}|)}{\sum_{i=1}^N A_i} \quad (6.1)$$

6.1.1. Case: Wet bed in downstream area

The initial discontinuity, with a downstream water depth of 1 m, resolves into a rarefaction wave and a shock wave, with the former propagating in upstream direction while the latter moves in downstream direction of the domain, as seen in Fig. 6.1a.

A good representation of the upper section of the rarefaction wave is obtained by the Fully Upwind Method and second-order accurate HLLC scheme while the first-order accurate HLLC scheme exhibits some slight smearing of the solution, also visible in the temporal progress of the flow velocity, seen in Fig. 6.1b. The transition from rarefaction wave to constant water level is also slightly smeared by all discretisation schemes, with the second-order accurate scheme showing the best results. When it comes to the representation of the shock wave, the approximate Riemann solver captures the shock well with the second-order accurate approach giving the best results. The Fully Upwind Method, on the other hand, is not able to represent the discontinuity without introducing spurious oscillations, also present in the flow velocity profile.

Tab. 6.1 shows that the second-order accurate HLLC scheme introduces the least amount of numerical diffusion as the error is the smallest of all schemes. The error produced by the Fully Upwind Method is a little less than twice as high as the second-order scheme, whereas the solution of the first-order accurate HLLC solver exhibits the highest amount of numerical diffusion of all implemented schemes.

In conclusion, the second-order accurate HLLC scheme delivers the best representation of the exact solution as it exhibits good shock-capturing capabilities and only introduces small amounts of numerical diffusion.

Time	Fully Upwind	HLLC (1st Order)	HLLC (2nd Order)
0.3 s	$8.09 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m	$1.57 \cdot 10^{-2}$ m	$4.61 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m
0.6 s	$8.70 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m	$1.82 \cdot 10^{-2}$ m	$5.06 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m

Table 6.1: One-dimensional dam break - wet bed scenario: L^1 -errors of water depth for flux schemes Fully Upwind, first-order accurate HLLC solver and second-order accurate HLLC solver.

(a) Temporal change water depth levels.

(b) Temporal change flow velocity.

Figure 6.1: One-dimensional dam break - wet bed case: Water depth levels and flow velocity profiles for the exact solution, Fully Upwind Method, first-order accurate and second-order accurate HLLC solver at $t = 0.3$ s, $t = 0.6$ s.

6.1.2. Case: Dry bed in downstream area

With no initial water depth in the downstream area, the discontinuity resolves to a single rarefaction wave going upstream, as seen in Fig. 6.2a. Observing the temporal progress of the water depth, it is apparent that all discretisation schemes show good agreement with the exact solution. Since shock waves are absent in the solution, the Fully Upwind Method does not introduce spurious oscillations and does in fact obtain better results than the first-order accurate HLLC scheme, exhibiting less smearing at the top and bottom of the rarefaction wave and producing less numerical diffusion. Although both schemes are not able to reproduce the high propagation speeds at the front of the exact solution, visible in Fig. 6.2b, impeding the increase of water depth at the front in the process. The second-order accurate HLLC scheme obtains results that resemble the exact flow velocity profile more closely but also exhibit disparities, which can be traced back to its reduction in the order of spatial accuracy to first-order when reconstructing wet/dry fronts.

Similar to the wet bed case, the second-order accurate approach obtains the best result, as its wave propagation resembles the exact solution the most and introduces the least amount of numerical diffusion, as seen in Tab. 6.2.

Time	Fully Upwind	HLLC (1st Order)	HLLC (2nd Order)
0.3 s	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-2}$ m	$1.69 \cdot 10^{-2}$ m	$7.82 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m
0.6 s	$1.47 \cdot 10^{-2}$ m	$2.05 \cdot 10^{-2}$ m	$7.73 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m

Table 6.2: One-dimensional dam break - dry bed scenario: L^1 -errors of water depth for flux schemes fully upwind, first-order accurate HLLC solver and second-order accurate HLLC solver.

(a) Temporal change of water depth levels.

(b) Temporal change of flow velocity profile.

Figure 6.2: One-dimensional dam break - dry bed case: Water depth levels and flow velocity profiles for the exact solution, Fully Upwind Method, first-order accurate and second-order accurate HLLC solver at $t = 0.3\text{ s}$, $t = 0.6\text{ s}$.

6.2. Rainfall runoff in V-shaped catchment

(a) Catchment overview.

(b) Cross section of upstream channel boundary.

(c) Cross section of downstream channel boundary.

A rainfall runoff scenario is simulated to verify the model's abilities to compute shallow surface water flow on sloped beds and consider bed friction effects. The simulation is carried out for a V-shaped catchment, as illustrated in Fig. 6.3a, and compared to analytical solution for the discharge at one of the hillsides (Overton & Brakensiek, 1970) and another solution for the discharge at the downstream outlet (Giammarco et al., 1996). The domain consists of a 20 m wide channel with a slope of 0.02 that runs down the middle of the catchment, starting at a depth of 1 m and reaching 21 m at the outlet, as seen in Figs. 6.3b and 6.3c, respectively. The channel is bound on either side by hillsides featuring a slope of 0.05 in perpendicular direction and no inclination parallel to the channel. A uniform cell size of 10 m is used to discretise the domain, resulting in a total of 16200 cells. All domain boundaries are closed with the exception of a free outflow boundary condition at the downstream outlet where, in order to prevent an impounding

of water at the outlet, the attached ghost cells continue the sloped bed elevation. To simulate the precipitation event, a constant, 90 min long rainfall with an intensity of 10.8 mm/s is dictated for the hillsides. Friction effects are taken into account by assigning a Manning coefficient of $n = 0.015 \text{ s m}^{-1/3}$ for the hillsides and $n = 0.15 \text{ s m}^{-1/3}$ for the channel bed. The Courant number is set to $Cr = 0.1$. The numerical flux is computed by using the approximate Riemann solver with first-order as well as second-order accurate reconstruction schemes. As in the previous case, second-order accuracy is achieved by employing the TVD minmod limiter function in the MUSCL scheme. The results of both schemes are compared to the analytical solutions, which comprises two hydrographs, the first presents the discharge over the lower end of one hillside and the second depicts the outflow at the channel boundary, although the latter only encompasses the temporal range of the precipitation event. To investigate the total error over time, an L^1 -norm of the normalized, area-weighted MAE from the discharge has been computed for the lower end of the hillside and the channel outflow as

$$L^1(\text{norm. MAE}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (A_i \cdot |\mathbf{q}_i^{\text{exact}} - \mathbf{q}_i^{\text{simulated}}|)}{\sum_{i=1}^N (A_i \cdot \mathbf{q}_i^{\text{exact}})} \cdot 100 (\%) \quad (6.2)$$

with N denoting the number of cells for the observed location.

The results for the L^1 -errors, obtained with Eq. 6.2, are listed in Tab. 6.3. It is apparent that the results obtained with the first-order accurate HLLC scheme are very poor since neither the representation of the discharge at hillside nor at the channel outflow show any agreement with the exact solution, as seen in Figs. 6.4a and 6.4b. For first-order accurate schemes, steep slopes may lead to the artificial drying of cells (see Sec. 3.3.4) which leads to the computation of wrong flow fields and hydrographs. This phenomenon is well recognisable at the two cusps in the outflow hydrograph in Fig. 6.4a. Between these two points in time, the water depth at the outflow is greater than 0.2 m and since the difference in bed elevation between the cells at the boundary and their neighbours is also 0.2 m, computation does not involve the artificial drying of the cells. Before and after this range, the water depth is below 0.2 m, leading to artificially dry cells. It must be noted that better results were achieved in Simons (2020) with `hms-java`, however, tests have been carried out and these results could not be reobtained with the Java version. The second-order accurate scheme on the other hand is showing very good agreement with the exact solution in all phases of the simulation, except for a slight smearing when reaching the peak discharge in the channel outflow hydrograph, and is therefore capable

of computing a sheet-like surface water flow on steep gradients.

	HLLC (1st Order)	HLLC (2nd Order)
Hillside hydrograph	74.95	0.33
Outflow hydrograph	74.11	0.85

Table 6.3: Relative L^1 -errors [%] of the discharge over the simulation time for the first-order accurate and second-order accurate HLLC solver.

(a) Discharge over time at the outflow boundary of the channel.

(b) Discharge over time at the lower end of the hillside.

Figure 6.4: Rainfall runoff: Discharge levels for the exact Riemann solver, first-order accurate and second-order accurate HLLC solver.

7. Performance benchmark

This section discusses the benchmark of the implemented second-order accurate HLLC approximate Riemann solver and the used traversal schemes. All simulations related to the performance benchmark use the *large* and *small* problem sets defined in Sec. 7.1 and are carried out on a node of a supercomputer system, detailed in Sec. 7.2. The parallel performance and scalability of the application is assessed by analysing the performance metrics described in Sec. 7.3. Details about each simulation configuration can be found in Sec. 7.4 followed by a short description of the compilation process and utilised compiler flags in Sec. 7.5.

The following six traversal approaches are benchmarked.

- Ordered edge traversal
- Ordered cell traversal
- Seamless row-wise traversal
- Seamed row-wise traversal
- Seamless block-wise traversal (revised version)
- Seamed blockwise traversal (revised version)

The two block-wise traversal strategies are revised versions of the original formulations, described in Secs. 5.5.4 and 5.5.5. These versions are the product of a preliminary study concerning the block size in block-wise traversal strategies, documented in Sec. 8.

7.1. Problem sets

A *large* and a *small* problem set are created to benchmark the implemented traversal patterns' computational performance for different mesh sizes. Both feature a flat computational domain that is $75 \text{ m} \times 75 \text{ m}$ in size that is represented as a **UniMesh** inside **hms++**. Cell dimensions and numbers are listed in Tab. 7.1. Initially, the water depth is 0.5 m and the flow velocity is 0.1 m/s in x- and y-direction. On the left and lower boundary of the domain, a boundary conditions dictates an orthogonal flow velocity of 0.5 m/s while the top and right boundary allow a free outflow. The employed TVD MUSCL scheme utilises the minmod limiter function, as in Eq. 3.42. Bed friction is uniformly represented by a *Manning* coefficient of $0.025 \text{ s m}^{-1/3}$. All simulations feature a CFL criterion of 0.3.

For the preliminary study investigating the block size of block-wise traversal schemes, a third, *extra small* problem set is created.

The simulation time refers to the amount of time that is simulated. For smaller problem sets the simulation time increases, otherwise, the execution time of the solver is too short to make a reliable statements about the performance.

Problem set	dx, dy	nx, ny	Total cells	Simulation time [s]
<i>large</i>	0.01 m	7500	$56.25 \cdot 10^6$	0.04
<i>small</i>	0.075 m	1000	$1 \cdot 10^6$	10.0
<i>extra small</i>	0.234375 m	320	102400	100.0

Table 7.1: Discretisation metrics of the problem sets.

7.2. Test platform

The compute node is a NUMA system and features two sockets, as illustrated in Fig. 7.1. Each socket is equipped with an Intel Xeon Platinum 9242 processor, which has 48 cores, clocked at 2.3 GHz and evenly distributed over two dies, providing a total of 96 cores on the node. Enabling Hyperthreading doubles the amount of hardware threads, resulting in 192 logical processors.

Each core has a private L1 first-level cache and L2 mid-level cache. The latter has a capacity of 1 MB, whereas the former is split into an instruction cache (L1I) and data cache (L1D), both are 32 KB. The 24 cores per die share the L3 last-level cache, which has a capacity of 35.75 MB. This results in a total of 6072 KB of L1D cache, 96 MB of L2 cache and 143 MB of L3 cache for a single node. The dies and sockets are interconnected via Intel’s *Ultra Path Interconnect*.

Each die has uniform access to its main memory of 93.25 GB of DDR4 RAM and non-uniform access to each other’s RAM, totalling in 362 GB RAM for the complete node (Oertel, 2020).

All simulations were carried out on a single compute node of the supercomputer system operated by the *Norddeutscher Verbund für Hoch- und Höchstleistungsrechnen* — *HLRN* (North German Supercomputing Alliance) (Norddeutscher Verbund für Hoch- und Höchstleistungsrechnen – HLRN, 2021).

Figure 7.1: Processor overview for Intel Xeon Platinum 9200 processors set up in a two-socket configuration (Oertel, 2020).

7.3. Performance metrics

The term scalability refers to the change in the application's execution time as the number of processors is increased for a constant problem size. This type of scaling is known as strong scaling. The obtained speed-up acts as a performance metric and can be expressed as

$$\eta_p = \frac{T_1}{T_p} \quad (7.1)$$

with the execution time denoted by T and the number of used processors p .

Another important performance metric, next to the speed-up function, is the parallel efficiency, which describes how efficient the given number of processors is used. It can be interpreted as the scaling of the speed-up function and is expressed as:

$$e_p = \frac{\eta_p}{p} = \frac{T_1}{p \cdot T_p} \quad (7.2)$$

In an ideal scenario, the execution time decreases proportionally to the increase in processor count, e.g. the execution time should be twice as fast for twice as many processors. However, this is not true for practical applications since parallelising code

always introduces overhead (Hinkelmann, 2006). This leads to the speed-up factor always being below the number of used processors and a parallel efficiency of less than 100% for real applications.

Another limitation that can already be considered in the hypothetical speed-up is the serial fraction of the application that does not benefit from an increase in resources. This implies that the performance improvement to be gained by parallelisation is limited by the proportion of the code that is serial (Hennessy, 2003). Taking this notion into account, the total execution time is formulated as

$$T_p = \alpha T_1 + \frac{(1 - \alpha)T_1}{p} \quad (7.3)$$

with α denoting the serial fraction of the runtime, which is unaffected by an increase in resources. Substituting Eq. 7.3 into Eq. 7.1 yields Amdahl's law for the speed-function:

$$\eta_p = \frac{T_1}{T_p} = \frac{1}{\alpha + \frac{(1-\alpha)}{p}} \quad (7.4)$$

Amdahl's law can be used to predict the maximum hypothetical speed-up, which would be achieved for a 100% parallel efficiency and an infinite amount of processors, as

$$\lim_{p \rightarrow \infty} \eta_p = \frac{1}{\alpha} \quad (7.5)$$

proving that the maximum speed-up of a function converges to the reciprocal value of the serial fraction of the total runtime on one core.

In order to investigate the influence of SMT on the parallel performance, a ratio between the measured times for a specified number of cores p with SMT enabled and disabled is introduced:

$$\eta_{p, \text{SMT}} = \frac{T_{p, \text{SMT on}}}{T_{p, \text{SMT off}}} \quad (7.6)$$

The metric allows measuring the speed-up that is obtained by the utilisation of SMT.

7.4. Simulation configurations

The *large* and *small* problem sets are simulated with each of the six traversal patterns, resulting in 12 different combinations. Each combination is executed on 7 different core configurations, once with the utilisation of SMT as well as once without it, resulting in

a total of 14 different thread configurations. When these configurations are mentioned, the *core configuration* refers to a fixed number of cores, regardless of SMT utilisation. A *thread configuration* always refers to a fixed number of threads and cores, specified in App. C.

Every simulation is repeated three times, with the fastest execution time of the repetitions noted down.

The supercomputer system uses job scheduling software to allocate necessary compute nodes for workloads. All simulations for a thread configuration are organised into a job, resulting in 14 jobs with 36 simulations each. Since some thread configurations use a number of cores smaller than the number available on a single die of a chip, up to four independent simulations can be carried out on single compute node, each running on one of the four available NUMA sections. This way each of these simulations has uniform memory access, L3 cache is not shared and costs can be saved by reducing the number of utilised compute nodes. Larger thread configurations are distributed evenly over two or four NUMA sections, resulting in non-uniform memory access for these simulations.

In order to schedule four simulations on a single node, the `mpirun` command, provided by Intel's MPI implementation, is used. This way each simulation is treated as an MPI process, although no MPI code is necessary on the application side.

7.5. Compilation

The compilation of the source code was done via the *GNU compiler collection* (`gcc`) 9.3.0, which offers several options to control various sorts of optimisations, collectively enabled via the `-O3` flag (Stallman, 2020). This flag also commands the compiler to auto-vectorise code when possible. Furthermore, machine-specific optimisations have been utilised through the `-march=native` flag. The individual flags that are activated by the mentioned flags are listed in App. B. In order to use OpenMP, the flag `-fopenmp` was appended as well.

It must be noted that using `-march=native` diminishes the portability of the performance since not every optimisation flag is available on every machine. For instance, on the test platform, the flag enables AVX-512, a SIMD instruction set currently only available on machines manufactured by Intel.

8. Preliminary study: Block size investigation

In this section, the block size, a parameter in block-wise traversal patterns, is investigated as it is presumed to impact the computational performance, as described in Sec. 5.5.4. Both block-wise patterns are investigated, although only the former's results are analysed in this section. The App. E holds more information about the examination of the seamed version.

Early results of this investigation constituted a revision of both patterns due to their poor load balancing capabilities. The revised and seamless block-wise traversal pattern is described in Sec. 8.1 and underwent the same investigation as the initial version. The results obtained by both versions are plotted in comparative diagrams, accompanied by analyses, in Sec. 8.2 and a subsequent discussion in Sec. 8.3. The approaches were tested using the problem sets described in Sec. 7.1,

Each simulation was run three times and the fastest complete execution time was noted down. All tests were carried out on the test platform, utilising both chips with simultaneous multithreading, resulting 192 threads.

8.1. Revision of seamless block-wise traversal pattern

As mentioned, the preliminary results of original seamless block-wise traversal pattern demonstrated poor load balancing capabilities, which prompted the proposal of a modified seamless block-wise traversal pattern. This revised version features a slightly different traversal order and different work schedules, in an attempt to reduce the load imbalance between the threads, increasing the computational performance in the process.

As seen in Code 12, the modified pattern changes the order of the traversed blocks by beginning with the inner blocks of the domain instead of the blocks at the boundary, as it is done in the original pattern, viewed in Code 9. In order to distribute the blocks in contiguous chunks, the schedule is kept as `static`. Subsequently, blocks at the left and bottom side are distributed with a `dynamic` work schedule, allowing underutilised threads to increase their workload and process additional iterations of the for loop. Then, the blocks at the right and top side are handled, making use of a `dynamic` work schedule once more. Lastly, the four blocks in each corner of the domain are handled. Each construct is appended by `nowait` clause, enabling unutilised threads to proceed to handle subsequent instructions.

```

1 // helpful variables
2 int blocksize = square root of the number of cells per block
3 int nBlocksX = no. of blocks in x-direction, excl. remainder blocks
4 int nBlocksY = no. of blocks in y-direction, excl. remainder blocks
5
6 // open up a parallel region
7 #pragma omp parallel {
8
9     if ( remaining cells in x- and y direction exist ) {
10
11         #pragma omp for schedule(static) collapse(2) nowait
12         for(Index by = 1; by < nBlocksY; ++by)
13             for(Index bx = 1; bx < nBlocksX; ++bx)
14                 // inner blocks
15
16         #pragma omp for schedule(dynamic) nowait
17         for(Index by = 1; by < nBlocksY; ++by)
18             // blocks on left side
19
20         #pragma omp for schedule(dynamic) nowait
21         for(Index bx = 1; bx < nBlocksX; ++bx)
22             // blocks at the bottom
23
24         #pragma omp for schedule(dynamic) nowait
25         for(Index by = 1; by < nBlocksY; ++by)
26             // (remainder) blocks on right side
27
28         #pragma omp for schedule(dynamic) nowait
29         for(Index bx = 1; bx < nBlocksX; ++bx)
30             // (remainder) blocks at the top
31
32         #pragma omp single nowait
33             // (remainder) block in top left corner
34
35         #pragma omp single nowait
36             // (remainder) block in top right corner
37
38         #pragma omp single nowait
39             // block in bottom left corner
40
41         #pragma omp single nowait
42             // (remainder) block in bottom right corner
43     }
44     else ...
45 }
46

```

Code 12: Revised seamless block-wise traversal.

8.2. Analysis

This section is divided into the analysis of the original and revised version for the *large*, *small* and *extra small* problem sets. The structure of the analysis is as follows: First, the execution times of the computational steps, described in Sec. 5.4, beginning with the flux calculation, are plotted in multiple comparative diagrams and are analysed. Then, the complete execution times of the solver, which are the sums of the previous steps, are plotted and analysed as well. The execution time of the solver excludes the solver initialisation and mesh creation. Some of the plots contain a simple moving average (SMA), with a period of five, expressed by superscript, for the *large* problem set and a period of three for the *small* and *extra small* problem set, to visualise trends in data sets. In order to avoid confusion, it should be noted that references to the traversal approaches in this chapter always refer to the original and revised version of the seamless block-wise pattern and not the seamed version.

8.2.1. Large problem set

Figure 8.1: Execution times of the flux calculation for the *large* problem set.

The moving averages of the flux calculation for both traversal approaches decreased for growing tile sizes up to a size of about 60, as seen in Fig. 8.1. While this speed-up

could be observed for both versions, it was more pronounced in the revised pattern. For subsequent block sizes, the average of the original approach rose significantly and the pattern developed increasing fluctuations. This behaviour was not observed for the redesigned approach, although a slight increase of the moving average for block sizes larger than ~ 60 was noticed.

The fastest flux calculation time obtained by revised approach was 11.78 s using a block size of 62 while the original pattern produced its fastest time of 11.95 s with a block size of 27.

Figure 8.2: Execution times for friction source term calculation for the *large* problem set.

The execution times for the friction source term calculation obtained by the original pattern saw no major change for increasing block sizes, as seen in Fig. 8.2, and resulted in an average value of 13.97 s. The modified pattern obtained considerably faster times, averaging 10.05 s, a speed-up of $1.39\times$.

The time step calculation took an average of 0.26 s and 0.29 s for the original and redesigned approach, respectively. Increasing the block size did not have any significant effects on the time step calculation for the range 2 to 70, although the results for

Figure 8.3: Execution times of the calculation of the time step, new state variables and updating of boundaries for the *large* problem set.

subsequent block sizes tended to be a bit more fluctuant, as seen in Fig. 8.3.

The execution times for the calculation of the new state variables, also plotted in Fig. 8.3, fluctuated mildly around slightly increasing moving averages until a block size of ~ 60 , for both traversal patterns. Fluctuations grew for subsequent block sizes and the moving averages developed a somewhat periodic behaviour. For most block sizes the original pattern produced slightly faster times than the revised approach, with the fastest times being 0.74 s using a block size of 8 and 0.85 s with a block size of 7, for the original and revised pattern, respectively.

Execution times of the updating of boundaries were quite similar to one another, with averages of 0.14 s and 0.11 s for the original and redesigned approach, respectively.

Fig. 8.4 displays the execution times for the complete simulation, i.e. the sum of the previously analysed steps. Overall, the modified pattern produced faster execution times than the original traversal approach, as seen in Tab. 8.1, where the fastest time obtained by redesigned pattern is $1.17\times$ faster than the best result achieved by the original approach. The best result produced by the modified pattern is $1.07\times$ faster than its slowest execution time. The moving average of the execution times obtained by

Figure 8.4: Execution times of the complete simulation for the *large* problem set.

	Original pattern	Modified pattern
Slowest exec. time	32.96 s	25.10 s
Block size	194	173
Fastest exec. time	27.36 s	23.45 s
Block size	57	58

Table 8.1: Slowest and fastest complete execution times for *large* problem set.

the redesigned pattern developed a slightly periodic behaviour, that was also observed for the calculation of the new state variables in Fig. 8.3. The moving average stayed below 24 s for block sizes between 18 and 62, with a short dip above for block sizes 36 to 39. For higher block sizes, the average climbed above 24 s with some more or less isolated measurements dipping below the 24 s mark. An execution time of 25.94 s was obtained by the ordered edge traversal scheme. The fastest time obtained with the modified pattern is $1.11\times$ faster when compared to the latter.

8.2.2. Small problem set

Figure 8.5: Execution times of the flux calculation for the *small* problem set.

In the block size range of 2 to 7, both patterns obtained similar execution times for the flux calculation, ranging between 7.79 s and 8.07 s, plotted in Fig. 8.5. Obtained times for the original pattern progressively increased for expanding block sizes. Tiles larger than 20 lead to growing fluctuations. Similar behaviour was already observed for the *large* problem set, however, the moving average in the latter began to rise for the much larger block size of 60, as seen in Fig. 8.1. The modified approach stayed below 8 s until a block size of 20. For subsequent block sizes, the execution times increased slightly as well. Additionally, the obtained times for both patterns were not as fluctuant as in the *large* problem set.

The execution times of the calculation of the new time step, friction source terms, new state variables and the updating of boundaries are plotted Fig. 8.6. Obtained times for the source term calculation were almost identical with 1.40 s and 1.41 s for the original and revised pattern, respectively.

A similar behaviour could be observed for the calculation of the time step, which took 0.19 s with the original pattern and 0.2 s with the redesigned approach, on average.

For the a block size of up to 33, the calculation of the new state variables took 0.15 s on

Figure 8.6: Execution times of the calculation of time step, friction source terms, new state variables and updating of boundaries for the *small* problem set.

average with both traversal patterns. The original scheme developed slight fluctuations for subsequent block sizes.

Updating the boundary conditions was unaffected for growing block sizes. On average it took 0.31 s and 0.32 s for the unmodified and modified traversal pattern, respectively. Similar to the flux calculation, the fluctuations for the friction source term and new state state variables observed in the *large* problem set, seen in Figs. 8.2, and 8.3, are not occurring for the *small* problem set.

The smaller mesh resolution influenced the size of the share that the friction source term and new state variables calculation had of the complete execution time. For the revised traversal pattern, calculating the friction source term made up 42.16% of the *big* problem set's complete time and 13.66% on the *small* mesh. The calculation of the new state variables took 5.16% of the complete execution time on the *large* mesh and 1.54% of the *small* set's time.

The fastest times of the both patterns were almost identical, as seen in Tab. 8.2. When comparing the slowest time obtained by the modified pattern to its fastest time, a speed-up of $1.2\times$ could be observed.

In Fig. 8.7, the complete execution times produced by both versions are plotted along

Figure 8.7: Complete execution times for the *small* problem set.

	Original pattern	Revised pattern
Slowest exec. time	19.10 s	11.79 s
Block size	40	40
Fastest exec. time	9.84 s	9.79 s
Block size	2	4

Table 8.2: Slowest and fastest complete execution times for *small* problem set.

with the execution time obtained by the ordered edge traversal approach. The modified pattern's fastest time is $1.28\times$ faster than the ordered approach, which took 12.49 s.

8.2.3. Extra small problem set

Figure 8.8: Execution times of the flux calculation for the *extra small* problem set.

Concerning the flux calculation, the original traversal pattern obtained its fastest time of 5.53 s with a block size of 3. Afterwards, the produced times increased progressively, also introducing slight fluctuations for a block size upwards of 10 and strong fluctuations for 20 and higher, as seen in Fig. 8.8.

The revised pattern dampened the increase of values with execution times between 4 s and 5.3 s for block sizes up to 16. Then, the obtained times progressively increased for a tile size up to 23. Incrementing the tile size by one resulted in a speed of 2.41 s. For subsequent block sizes, the obtained times progressively increased again.

The execution times of the remaining steps of the algorithm were quite similar to each other, as seen in Fig. 8.9. Both approaches took 0.32 s on average to calculate the time step. Changes in the block size did not affect the calculation. The same behaviour could be observed for the updating of boundaries, both versions averaging an execution time of 0.74 s. Tile size changes had small impacts on the friction source term calculation. While both patterns took 0.73 s on average for block sizes ranging from 2 to 25, the original pattern began to produce increased values up to 2.05 for subsequent block sizes.

The execution times for the calculation of the new state variables were also relatively

Figure 8.9: Execution times of the calculation of time step, friction source term, new state variables and updating of boundaries for the *extra small* problem set.

unaffected by an increase in block sizes up to a block size of 28, with averages of 0.35 s and 0.4 s for the original and revised pattern respectively. Afterwards, times of up to 1.38 s were obtained with the original pattern.

The fastest complete execution time obtained with the original approach was $1.10\times$ faster than the redesigned pattern, as seen in Tab. 8.3. When looking at Fig. 8.10, it becomes apparent that the original pattern performed marginally better for block sizes up to 6, whereas the revised pattern produced faster execution times for the subsequently larger tile sizes. The fastest time obtained with the redesigned approach was $1.89\times$ faster than its slowest result. Both versions produced faster times than the ordered edge traversal, which obtained an execution time of 8.24 s.

	Original pattern	Revised pattern
Slowest exec. time	42.59 s	11.54 s
Block size	40	39
Fastest exec. time	5.53 s	6.11 s
Block size	2	4

Table 8.3: Slowest and fastest complete execution times for *extra small* problem set.

Figure 8.10: Complete execution times for the *extra small* problem set.

8.3. Discussion

The increasing flux calculation times and growing fluctuations obtained by the original pattern for expanding tile sizes can be linked to the uneven distribution of blocks among the threads.

Due to the `static` work schedule of the utilised `omp for` constructs in Code 10, the workload for each thread is the number of loop iterations divided by the number of threads, in this case 192, with the remainder being distributed among the threads, in order of the thread numbers. This implies that each distributed loop that resulted in remainders added further blocks to the first threads, creating a load imbalance between the threads. Growing block sizes increased this imbalance, resulting in longer execution times overall since the algorithm is only as fast as its slowest thread. Additionally, the growing fluctuations were related to the traversal of blocks located at the top and the right boundary of the domain. These blocks could be either actual or remainder blocks, with the latter exhibiting size variations, depending on the number of remaining cells. Faster computation times are achieved for small remainder blocks, which results in growing deviations for increasing block sizes. As an example, consider the *large* problem set's block sizes 178 and 179, which lead to 24 and 161 remaining cells in x-direction,

respectively. With the larger block size, an execution of 16.03 s was obtained while the smaller block size needed 14.07 s, a speed-up of 1.14 \times .

The analysis of the *large* problem set showed that the redesigned pattern successfully dampened the growing fluctuations and produced considerably faster times than the original pattern, especially for larger tile sizes. This can be attributed to the pattern's improved load balancing capabilities. The dampening effects were also observable on the other problem sets, although, in those cases both patterns produced similar times for smaller block sizes.

There was a substantial difference between the execution times obtained by the traversal patterns for the friction source term calculation on the *large* mesh. This was somewhat unexpected since the actual edge traversal pattern itself is not connected to the friction source term calculation in any way. The cause for the speed-up might be the order in which the blocks were traversed. A subsequent test showed that when the traversal order of the modified pattern (inner blocks first, then left, bottom, right and top side, as seen in Code 12) is applied to the original pattern, the same speed-up for the friction source term calculation was obtained. A presumption can be made, that the traversal of blocks dictated by the revised approach leads to more advantageously cached data for the friction source term calculation.

The results obtained by the modified traversal pattern, for the *large* problem set, suggest that expanding the block size only slightly impacts the overall computational performance. However, the flux calculation did seem to marginally profit from the cache blocking principle, highlighted by the slightly decreasing moving averages, ranging from block size 2 to 60, seen in Fig. 8.1. Unfortunately, when summing up the execution times of all computational step, the alluded performance gain was diminished.

The total execution times on the *large* problem set fluctuated around the averages for consecutive block sizes. This makes it difficult to pinpoint a specific block size for best performance. However, fluctuations for tiles ranging between 2 and ~ 60 were not as severe as for subsequent sizes. Furthermore, the revised approach's moving averages were the lowest for tile sizes between ~ 20 and 60, which suggests that, for a mesh of comparable size, the block size should be in the mentioned range.

The *small* and *extra small* problems sets did not seem to profit from any potential cache blocking speed-ups, possibly due to the relatively large amount of available cache memory. The results suggest that every utilised thread was able to fully cache its workload and reuse stored memory before it was evicted, therefore canceling out any cache blocking benefits. This makes smaller tiles the more attractive choice for comparable mesh sizes, since larger sizes tend to introduce a more imbalanced load distribution, even with the

redesigned pattern, diminishing performance in the process. The results obtained by the revised pattern suggest that block sizes larger than ~ 19 should be avoided for meshes with a size comparable to the *small* problem set.

On the *extra small* mesh, the original pattern was able to slightly outperform the redesigned approach. A possible reason for this could be the larger overhead caused by the dynamic work scheduling utilised in the modified pattern. If the redesigned approach is used, tiles should not be larger than ~ 10 in order to obtain good performance on a mesh of comparable size. Analysing the results for *extra small* problem set showcased interesting phenomena regarding the parallelisation of the algorithm. Consider the performance increase that happened for the incrementation of the tile size from 23 to 24. The larger block size divided the mesh into less blocks than available hardware threads. On the one hand, this diminished the parallelisation of the algorithm since not all available threads were utilised, on the other hand, it also led to an even load balance, because each thread processed exactly one block. Results showed that the speed-up gained from the better load balancing was greater than the loss in parallelisation. However, faster flux calculation times were still achieved with significantly smaller block sizes as they lead to a better parallelisation of the algorithm whilst creating negligible load imbalances. For mesh sizes as small as this one, another performance degrading phenomenon might gain importance. Combining the *small* mesh resolution with the relatively large number of threads, as well as choosing tile sizes bigger than 17, increased the risk of false sharing, detailed in Sec. 4.3.4. In this case, the workload of some threads only included a single block, which led to the parallel processing of adjacent blocks. Some cache lines might have been part of both blocks and were operated on simultaneously forcing CPU cores to reload these cache lines and increasing the execution time in the process.

Caution should be practised when it comes to the block size recommendations given in this discussion. The current approach to implement the cache-blocking principles into the traversal of edges requires further work since the increase of the block size only yields non-significant performance improvements or none at all.

9. Parallel performance investigation

This chapter covers the results of the performance benchmark obtained by the six traversal patterns for the *large* and *small* problem set and the defined thread configurations. The analysis of the results is carried out in Sec. 9.1, followed by a discussion in Sec. 9.2. Information related to the simulation setup is given in Sec. 7.

9.1. Analysis

The results obtained for the *large* and *small* problem sets, with and without the utilisation of SMT, were analysed. In order to investigate the scalability of the traversal patterns, parallel speed-up and efficiency graphs were set up, including the ideal speed-up for each pattern, according to Amdahl's law. The performance metrics are based on reference times given in Sec. 9.1.1. In addition to the graphs, efficiency drop-offs between consecutive thread configurations were listed. Since each core configuration was also used with SMT enabled, additional graphs were plotted, representing the obtained speed-ups or slow-downs for each core configuration.

The complete execution times for all patterns and thread configurations can be found in App. D.

9.1.1. Reference times

The performance metrics are based on reference times that were obtained with simulations utilising a single core. Reference times obtained with and without SMT are listed in Tab. 9.1. These times were obtained with the thread configurations #1 and #8 respectively. Amdahl's law, see Eq. 7.4, has been used to compute the speed-ups of the traversal patterns. This study focuses solely on the execution times of the solver, disregarding any overhead due to mesh creation or solver initialisation, which is why Amdahl's law was only computed for the highly parallelised execution of the solver. When measuring the execution times on a single core, the parallel portion of the solver exceeded 99.99% for every traversal pattern, regardless of mesh size and the utilisation of SMT. This is why the number of utilised cores is a good approximation for the ideal speed-up.

Tab. 9.2 lists the block sizes used by the block-wise traversal patterns for this study. The chosen block sizes yielded the best or good results in the preliminary block size study in Sec. 8. It must be noted that those results were obtained using all 192 hardware threads of the test platform. For smaller thread configurations, these sizes might not be optimal, specifically in regards to the load balancing capabilities of the traversal patterns.

Traversal pattern	Problem set			
	SMT disabled		SMT enabled	
	<i>large</i>	<i>small</i>	<i>large</i>	<i>small</i>
Ordered edge	1633.10	1003.10	1250.67	769.59
Ordered cell	2307.27	1415.75	1846.68	1128.87
Seaml. row-wise	1637.48	1006.52	1252.63	770.87
Seamed row-wise	1542.50	949.92	1234.78	757.74
Seaml. block-wise	1672.38	1037.67	1264.94	792.16
Seamed block-wise	1588.67	984.81	1239.68	772.92

Table 9.1: Reference times [s] obtained with thread configuration #1 (SMT disabled) and #8 (SMT enabled).

Traversal pattern	Problem set	
	<i>large</i>	<i>small</i>
Seaml. block-wise	58	15
Seamed block-wise	53	22

Table 9.2: Block sizes used in the parallel performance investigation.

9.1.2. Large problem set

Results without SMT The parallel speed-ups obtained for the traversal patterns are depicted in Fig. 9.1. The displayed speed-ups increased for every 16-core increment, except for the seamless row-wise traversal strategy. Here, the increase from 64 to 80 cores resulted in a decrease from $47.63\times$ to $40.27\times$.

The fastest execution times and highest speed-ups were obtained with the maximum number of cores and are listed in Tab. 9.3. Overall, the fastest time was achieved by the seamed block-wise traversal pattern, although the ordered edge, the seamed row-wise and seamless block-wise traversal strategies obtained quite similar times, all of them being in the range of 25.41 s to 26.13 s. The seamless row-wise pattern performed slightly worse and ordered cell traversal pattern produced significantly slower times, even though the latter approach benefited the most from the increase in core count, achieving a maximum speed-up of $67.11\times$.

For up to 32 cores, each traversal pattern's parallel efficiency is above 90%, as seen in Fig. 9.2. The efficiency drop-offs for consecutive core-configurations are listed in Tab. 9.4.

All traversal patterns sustained a significant drop in parallel efficiency when moving from the 32-core to the 48-core configuration, ranging from 8.70% to 12.22%, as seen in Tab. 9.4.

The speed-up decrease obtained by the seamless row-wise pattern for the 80-core configuration was also reflected in an efficiency loss of 24.08%. The subsequent configuration sped up the simulation again, which is represented as a negative efficiency loss in Tab. 9.4.

	Ordered edge	Ordered cell	Seamless row-wise	Seamed row-wise	Seamless block-wise	Seamed block-wise
Max speed-up	$62.48\times$	$67.41\times$	$57.52\times$	$59.39\times$	$64.10\times$	$62.51\times$
Corresponding efficiency [%]	65.09	70.22	59.92	61.87	66.77	65.12
Exec. time [s]	26.13	34.22	28.46	25.96	26.08	25.41

Table 9.3: Highest speed-ups and corresponding execution times obtained for the *large* problem set. SMT is disabled.

Figure 9.1: Speed-up graphs for the *large* problem set. SMT is disabled.

Figure 9.2: Efficiency graphs for the *large* problem set. SMT is disabled.

Δe_p	Ordered edge	Ordered cell	Seamless row-wise	Seamed row-wise	Seamless block-wise	Seamed block-wise
1 to 16	3.05	2.54	4.64	3.50	2.71	2.89
16 to 32	3.52	2.71	3.65	5.77	3.87	4.29
32 to 48	9.75	8.97	12.22	9.57	8.70	10.31
48 to 64	7.00	6.40	5.04	7.50	5.69	6.79
64 to 80	7.64	4.79	24.08	5.47	7.94	5.83
80 to 96	3.92	4.32	-9.57	6.29	4.29	4.75

Table 9.4: Efficiency drop-off [%] between core configurations for the traversal strategies for the *large* problem set. SMT is disabled.

Results with SMT Utilising SMT resulted in significantly faster reference times but the solutions did not scale as well, as seen in Fig. 9.3. Generally, incrementing the number of cores resulted in progressively higher speed-ups, except for the 80-core configuration of the seamed row-wise traversal approach, as it performed worse than the 64-core configuration. Further, the seamless row-wise strategy did not sustain the significant performance loss for the 80-core configuration that occurred in the non-SMT version. The overall fastest execution time of 24.38 s was obtained with the seamless block-wise traversal pattern using the 96-core configuration. This corresponding speed-up of $51.88\times$ was also the highest speed-up registered, which implies that this approach scaled better than the others. Slightly worse, yet similar results were obtained by the ordered edge and seamed block-wise strategies, as seen in Tab. 9.5. The ordered cell and row-wise strategies performed significantly worse with the former taking exactly twice as long as the seamless block-wise pattern and only obtained a speed-up of $37.86\times$.

It should be noted that not all traversal approaches obtained their fastest times with the maximum number of cores. The seamless row-wise traversal strategy performed best on the 80-core configuration.

Since utilising SMT results in overall worse scalability, the corresponding parallel efficiencies, displayed in Fig. 9.4, were lower as well. The efficiency drop-offs between the consecutive core configurations are listed in Tab. 9.6. Similar to the results obtained without SMT, the highest drop-offs generally happened when moving from the 32-core configuration to the 48-core configuration, with drop-offs ranging from 9.85% to 20.44%.

However, other losses were severe as well, e.g. 14.87% for the ordered traversal pattern when moving from 48 to 64 cores or 14.46% for the seamed row-wise approach when increasing the number cores from 64 to 80.

The graphs in Fig. 9.5 illustrate how much faster or slower the traversal pattern performed when enabling SMT compared to when it is disabled.

For up to 32 cores, all traversal approaches produced faster execution times when SMT was enabled. All patterns benefited the most from SMT when utilising just one core, speed-ups ranged between between 24.92% to 30.72%, which are expected values, further described in Sec. 4.3.3. With the number of cores increasing, the speed-up obtained through SMT diminished and it even began to impact performance in a negative way for ordered cell and row-wise patterns. However, the seamed row-wise approach gained a significant performance boost from SMT for the 80-core configuration. This was due to the considerable performance-loss that occurred in the non-SMT version, illustrated in Fig. 9.1. The ordered edge and seamless block-wise pattern are the only patterns that still benefit from SMT when utilising the maximum number of cores, although it should be noted that these speed-ups are only marginal, with 0.72% and 7.01% for the ordered edge and seamless block-wise traversal strategies, respectively.

	Ordered edge	Ordered cell	Seamless row-wise	Seamed row-wise	Seamless block-wise	Seamed block-wise
Max speed-up	48.19×	37.86×	37.66×	41.57×	51.88×	48.64×
Corresponding efficiency [%]	50.20	39.44	47.08	43.30	54.04	50.66
Exec. time [s]	25.94	48.76	33.25	29.70	24.38	25.48

Table 9.5: Highest speed-ups and corresponding execution times obtained for the *large* problem set. SMT is enabled.

Figure 9.3: Speed-up graphs for the *large* problem set. SMT is enabled.

Figure 9.4: Efficiency graphs for the *large* problem set. SMT is enabled.

Figure 9.5: Speed-ups/Slow-downs obtained by the utilisation of SMT for the *large* problem set.

Δe_p	Ordered edge	Ordered cell	Seamless row-wise	Seamed row-wise	Seamless block-wise	Seamed block-wise
1 to 16	6.48	5.51	7.45	7.17	5.07	5.44
16 to 32	10.63	10.71	11.39	10.92	9.42	10.74
32 to 48	10.95	16.75	20.44	14.05	10.89	9.85
48 to 64	7.00	14.87	5.38	9.58	5.63	7.58
64 to 80	8.50	9.05	8.23	14.46	8.32	7.21
80 to 96	6.21	3.64	7.86	0.48	6.58	8.49

Table 9.6: Efficiency drop-off [%] between core configurations for the traversal strategies for the *large* problem set. SMT is enabled.

9.1.3. Small problem set

Results without SMT Significant parallel speed-ups were obtained for each core configuration when using the ordered edge, ordered cell or block-wise traversal patterns, as seen in Fig. 9.6. Both row-wise patterns did not perform as well as the others, which is noticeable when looking at the maximum speed-ups in Tab. 9.7. The overall fastest time of 12.10 s was achieved with the ordered edge approach, although the block-wise traversal strategies obtained quite similar results with 12.33 s for the seamless block-wise pattern and 12.54 s for the seamed strategy. The ordered cell traversal strategy also benefited considerably from the increased number of cores and obtained a maximum speed-up of $77.52\times$, however, since the corresponding reference time was substantially higher, the pattern’s fastest time was a fair amount longer than those of the mentioned approaches. Corresponding to the speed-ups, the ordered edge, ordered cell and the block-wise traversal approaches keep a relatively high parallel efficiency of over 80% for all core configurations, as seen in Fig. 9.7. The ordered cell traversal strategy even gained some efficiency when moving from the 32-core to the 48-core configuration, as seen in Tab. 9.8. In accordance with the slower speed-ups, the seamless row-wise pattern’s efficiency declined significantly faster. For the 96-core configuration the seamed row-wise approach’s efficiency was 56.92% and the seamless pattern obtained an efficiency of 48.29%. In general, the row-wise patterns sustained the highest efficiency drop-offs of all patterns.

Figure 9.6: Speed-up graphs for the *small* problem set. SMT is disabled.

Figure 9.7: Efficiency graphs for the *small* problem set. SMT is disabled.

	Ordered edge	Ordered cell	Seamless row-wise	Seamed row-wise	Seamless block-wise	Seamed block-wise
Max speed-up	82.86×	77.52×	46.36×	54.64×	84.09×	78.50×
Corresponding efficiency [%]	86.31	80.75	48.29	56.92	87.59	81.77
Exec. time [s]	12.10	18.26	21.70	17.38	12.33	12.54

Table 9.7: Highest speed-ups and corresponding execution times obtained for the *small* problem set. SMT is disabled.

Δe_p	Ordered edge	Ordered cell	Seamless row-wise	Seamed row-wise	Seamless block-wise	Seamed block-wise
1 to 16	3.14	3.14	5.34	5.60	0.94	0.87
16 to 32	1.19	2.57	4.43	3.14	0.15	1.61
32 to 48	1.58	-0.26	8.43	6.15	2.84	3.24
48 to 64	2.64	5.87	11.51	15.80	4.04	5.00
64 to 80	3.71	4.09	13.78	7.84	2.99	3.37
80 to 96	1.39	3.82	8.18	4.51	1.42	4.10

Table 9.8: Efficiency drop-off [%] between core configurations for the traversal strategies for the *small* problem set. SMT is disabled.

Results with SMT The parallel speed-ups obtained with SMT enabled are shown in Fig. 9.8. While the reference times obtained with SMT enabled were 25% to 30% faster, as seen in Tab. 9.1, the speed-ups for an increasing number of cores were lower than those obtained without SMT. Although in general, the increased core count still led to increasing speed-ups, especially for the seamless block-wise pattern. However, the row-wise patterns as well as the seamed block-wise pattern sustained slow-downs for 80-core and 96-core configuration, respectively, when compared to previous configurations. Tab. 9.9 shows that the obtained maximum speed-ups differ significantly between the traversal patterns. The fastest execution time of 10.41 s and corresponding maximum speed-up of $76.05\times$ were obtained with the seamless block-wise approach. This is almost twice as fast as the seamless row-wise pattern, which obtained the lowest maximum speed-up of all patterns. It must be noted that the maximum speed-ups and fastest times for the seamless row-wise and seamed block-wise pattern were obtained with the 80-core configuration. The overall slowest execution time of 28.29 s was achieved by the ordered cell approach. This was $2.71\times$ slower than the fastest time.

In accordance with the obtained speed-up, the seamless block-wise approach obtained the best results for the parallel efficiency, as seen in Fig. 9.9. The seamed block-wise approach achieved similar results to the ordered edge strategy, obtaining 65.29% and 64.15%, respectively. Both block-wise approaches even slightly increased their efficiency by about 1.0% when moving from 48 cores to 64 cores. Since the row-wise and the ordered cell traversal strategies performed worse than the other approaches, they obtained a considerably lower efficiency than the other approaches. For the 96 core configuration efficiencies of 41.55%, 37.98% and 43.55% were obtained by the ordered cell, seamless row-wise and seamed row-wise patterns, respectively. When looking at Tab. 9.10, it becomes clear that the three approaches sustained major efficiency drop-offs when moving from 32 to 48 cores.

The utilisation of SMT had a similar effect on the execution times and speed-ups for the *small* problem set as it did for the *large* problem set. For some core configurations and traversal approaches, enabling SMT even resulted in slow-downs, as seen in Fig. 9.10. For the 1-core configuration, using SMT sped up the solver execution by 25% to 30%. This speed-up rapidly declined for subsequent core configurations if an ordered cell traversal strategy was employed. Upwards of 48 cores, the obtained times were slower than without SMT. The 96-core configuration with SMT enabled resulted in a 35% slower execution than without SMT.

For the 48- and 64-core configurations, the seamless row-wise pattern also achieved faster execution times without SMT while the 80-core and 96-core configurations benefited

from SMT.

The seamed row-wise approach performed worse with SMT for the 80-core and 96-core configuration.

Using 96 cores also slightly diminished the performance of the ordered edge strategy. Block-wise approaches generally performed better with SMT enabled, with the seamless approach even improving performance by 18.46% on the 96-core configuration. The seamed version obtained very similar results to those obtained without SMT, only achieving a speed-up of 1.73%.

	Ordered edge	Ordered cell	Seamless row-wise	Seamed row-wise	Seamless block-wise	Seamed block-wise
Max speed-up	61.58×	39.89×	37.98×	41.80×	76.05×	63.26×
Corresponding efficiency [%]	64.15	41.55	47.48	43.55	79.21	79.08
Exec. time [s]	12.49	28.29	20.29	18.12	10.41	12.21

Table 9.9: Highest speed-ups and corresponding execution times obtained for the *small* problem set. SMT is enabled.

Δe_p	Ordered edge	Ordered cell	Seamless row-wise	Seamed row-wise	Seamless block-wise	Seamed block-wise
1 to 16	5.20	8.00	10.13	8.79	1.53	1.98
16 to 32	2.49	11.34	9.03	4.86	1.33	2.69
32 to 48	6.94	17.41	22.74	15.12	7.07	9.92
48 to 64	2.24	12.31	8.33	9.35	-0.91	-1.14
64 to 80	10.22	6.12	2.25	14.33	4.11	7.45
80 to 96	8.72	3.25	9.50	3.96	7.63	13.78

Table 9.10: Efficiency drop-off [%] between core counts for the traversal strategies for the *small* problem set. SMT is enabled.

Figure 9.8: Speed-up graphs for the *small* problem set. SMT is enabled.

Figure 9.9: Efficiency graphs for the *small* problem set. SMT is enabled.

Figure 9.10: Speed-ups/Slow-downs obtained by the utilisation of SMT for the *small* problem set.

9.2. Discussion

When fully utilising the compute node, the seamless block-wise traversal approach produced the fastest or next to fastest execution times out of all traversal patterns, regardless of mesh size and SMT. The analysis of the *large* problem set showed that all patterns exhibited good scaling behaviour without SMT since all efficiencies stayed above 57.52%. While the block-wise, ordered cell and seamed row-wise traversal patterns obtained similar results ranging between 25.41 s and 26.08 s, the seamless row-wise approach performed slightly worse and ordered cell patterns produced significantly slower execution times. The latter approach was expected to be slower since it utilises a cell-based flux calculation, which involves computing the flux for each edge twice.

Furthermore, the obtained speed-ups did not reach a constant, which indicates that a machine featuring more cores could increase the speed-up even further.

The drop-off in efficiency experienced by every pattern for the *large* problem set when moving from the 32-core to the 48-core configuration could be related to the fact, that the L3 cache is shared by more threads than before. This could lead to a higher communication overhead between the cores as well as an increased memory latency since more cores populate the L3 cache with their cache lines, leading to more evictions and reloads, which degrades performance. The performance from 80 to 96 is not as obvious, since the density of threads per die for the 80-core configuration is higher than for the 32 core-configuration. The latter shares a thread/die ratio with the 64-core configuration. When summing up the efficiency drop-offs from 64 cores to 96 cores, the losses are similar to the jump from 32 to 48 cores.

The seamless row-wise pattern's poor result on the *large* mesh for the 80-core configuration cannot be explained at this point and demands further investigation. The thread configurations #5, #6 and #7 in Tab. C.2 show that the simulations using 64, 80 and 96 cores were all distributed over four NUMA sections, although the utilisation of 64 and 96 cores resulted in significantly higher speed-ups, which rules out a sudden memory latency increase due to non-uniform memory accesses. Furthermore, the 80-core configuration had more cache memory available than the 64-core configuration and less than the 96-core configuration, which renders memory latency and bandwidth problems due to a larger number of threads populating the cache unlikely. Determining the exact reason for the loss in speed-up proves to be difficult.

The analysis of the *small* problem set revealed even better scaling behaviour for all approaches, except for the seamless row-wise traversal patterns. Their speed-ups began to decline sharply when more than 48 cores were utilised. This overhead might be caused

by keeping the cache between cores coherent. When the number of cores increases, read and write operations to the same memory locations also increase, leading to a higher communications overhead and memory latency. Simulations on the *large* mesh might not suffer from this phenomenon as much. There, the workload per core might still be so large that when it comes to a point where a thread is accessing a memory location that was also accessed by another thread, this other thread does not hold the memory in question in its cache anymore. No communication to keep the cache coherent would be necessary.

One has to be careful with the utilisation of SMT as it may slow down the simulation, depending on the used traversal pattern, core count and mesh size. The analysis showed that for up to 32 cores all approaches benefited from SMT, independent of mesh size. The seamless block-wise approach benefited the most from the utilisation of SMT as it obtained speed-ups for every core configuration and mesh size. SMT should not be used in combination with the ordered cell approach and a core count of 48 or higher since it produce slow-downs of up to $\sim 35\%$. The seamed block-wise and ordered edge traversal approaches mostly benefited from SMT as well, although, when utilising the full node, the speed-up and slow-downs were negligible, regardless of mesh size.

It must be noted that there are some indications that the scheduler did not always pin threads and processes in the intended manner since a few simulations exhibited highly varying results between their three repetitions. The obtained execution times of the ordered cell simulation on the *large* mesh utilising 48 cores were 56.05 s, 56.21 s and 121.17s. The third result is more than two times higher than the first two execution times, even though all simulation settings as well as execution configurations were identical. This could be an indication that threads were moved by the execution environment, possibly between NUMA sections, therefore increasing memory latency.

10. Comparison to hms-java

Figure 10.1: Sub-catchments in Heumoeser, Austria. Black dot in creek 3 marks the outlet of the sub-catchment (Simons, 2020).

This section covers the performance comparison of the C++ and Java versions of `hms`. The subject of comparison is a surface runoff simulation for a sub-catchment in the Heumöser area, located in the Vorarlberg Alps, Austria, illustrated in Fig. 10.1 (marked as "creek 3"). An in-depth case study was carried out in Simons (2020) in which the surface runoff was simulated for a corresponding unsteady rainfall event that took place in the area in July 2008. The real-world rain event measured ~ 160 mm in ~ 100 h with a peak discharge of $0.2 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, measured at the outlet of the sub-catchment.

The results presented in Simons (2020) were obtained with `hms-java`, which utilised a different reconstruction scheme than the one implemented in `hms++`, however, the scheme in the latter is also available in the Java version. This is why the simulations with Java version were repeated for this work, utilising the same reconstruction scheme as the C++ version. Due to time constraints, only the first 24 h of the surface runoff event were simulated for both versions.

A rectangular computational domain containing the subcatchment with a size of $670 \text{ m} \times 220 \text{ m}$ was discretised into a UniMesh with a resolution of $1 \text{ m} \times 1 \text{ m}$, resulting in 147400 cells. Bed elevation values were read from a digital elevation model (DEM) with a resolution of $1 \text{ m} \times 1 \text{ m}$. To do this, a basic DEM reader was implemented, capable of reading models in ESRI format. All boundaries allow a free outflow and the initial water

depth and velocity inside the domain were set to zero. The rain was realised as a spatially uniform mass source while the infiltration was considered by utilising a runoff-coefficient of $\Psi = 0.6$. A constant and spatially uniform Strickler coefficient of $30 \text{ m}^{1/3}/\text{s}$ is used to account for bed friction and the Courant number is limited $Cr = 0.3$. The scenario was simulated with each traversal pattern. A tile size of 10 was mandated for the block-wise approaches. Each simulation has been carried out twice, once with SMT enabled and once without it.

The analysis consists of a comparison of the simulated discharges at the outlet of the sub-catchment as well as the comparison and examination of complete execution times.

10.1. Analysis

Figure 10.2: Discharge at the outlet of sub-catchment "creek 3" and rainfall intensity over 24 h.

For the most part, `hms++` exactly reproduced the simulated discharge of the Java version, as seen in Fig. 10.2. On some occasions, e.g. around the 4-hour and 20-hour mark, the C++ version produced local peaks that were not present in the Java version.

The velocity field at 24 h obtained with `hms++`, depicted in Fig. 10.3, shows a stream in direction of the outlet located close to the eastern boundary of the catchment. Here, the

velocities ranged between 0.6 m/s and 1.5 m/s.

The complete execution times of the simulations, including the initialisation of the mesh and solver, were measured and are listed in Tab. 10.1. Overall, the two fastest times of 113 min and 131 min were obtained by the seamless block-wise traversal approach with SMT disabled and enabled, respectively. This is $1.29\times$ and $1.11\times$ faster than the best Java version result, which was obtained with SMT enabled. Looking at the execution times obtained by `hms-java`, the utilisation of SMT sped-up the simulation by a factor of $1.32\times$, resulting in 146 min. This was three minutes slower than the execution time produced by the seamed block-wise approach. However, all other tested combinations of traversal patterns and SMT utilisation performed worse than `hms-java` using all hardware threads. When compared to the fastest result of the ordered cell pattern, which also featured a cell-based flux calculation, the Java version obtained a speed-up of $1.24\times$. The seamless row-wise approach obtained execution times over 210 min, regardless of SMT and the seamed row-wise pattern even exceeded the set maximum job time of 240 min.

To further investigate the seamless block-wise pattern, the time shares of the solver execution time obtained with it are listed in Tab. 10.2. It must be noted that the time shares for the other traversal patterns are similar, except for significantly higher flux calculation times. Enabling SMT sped up the flux calculation by a factor of $1.10\times$. All other computational steps took more or less twice as long when SMT was used. In total, the solver execution without SMT was $1.11\times$ faster than with SMT enabled.

Figure 10.3: Velocity field at $t = 24$ h. Coloured lines represent contour lines and the black line outlines the sub-catchment. The outlet is marked by the pink square.

Traversal patterns	SMT	Execution time [min]
1) Seamless block-wise	X	116
2) Seamless block-wise	✓	131
3) Seamed block-wise	X	143
4) hms-java	✓	146
5) Ordered edge	X	152
6) Ordered edge	✓	166
7) Seamed block-wise	✓	167
8) Ordered cell	X	181
9) Seamed row-wise	X	185
10) hms-java	X	192
11) Seamless row-wise	X	210
12) Ordered cell	✓	221
13) Seamless row-wise	✓	234
14) Seamed row-wise	✓	> 240

Table 10.1: Complete execution times for all traversal approaches of hms++ and hms-java.

Computational step	SMT enabled		SMT disabled	
	Percentual share [%]	Execution time [s]	Percentual share [%]	Execution time [s]
Time step calculation	5.82	448.92	3.53	244.50
Flux calculation (incl. slope source)	56.78	4381.13	69.46	4808.92
Source calculation (incl. friction)	19.33	1491.32	17.59	1217.75
New state calculation	4.97	383.66	2.69	186.27
Updating boundaries	13.09	1010.31	6.72	465.51
Total execution time	100	7715.35	100	6922.94

Table 10.2: Parts of the solver execution time obtained with the seamless block-wise traversal approach.

10.2. Discussion

The results obtained with `hms++` strongly resembled those of the Java version, although the local peaks in the C++ version could be an indication of an error in the code that has not been fixed as of yet.

Overall, the performance of `hms-java` was better than expected. A performance similar to the ordered cell traversal pattern of the C++ version was anticipated since both patterns employ a cell-based flux calculation, however, the Java version was considerably faster. The difference in performance makes an argument for the completely encapsulated approach that is utilised in the Java version. Here, each computational step of the algorithm, illustrated in Fig. 5.10, is carried out for the currently visited cell. This allows for a good reuse of memory before moving on to the next cell. `hms++`, on the other hand, carries out a single computational step for the entire domain in parallel, returns to a single master thread, moves on to the next computational step and creates a new team of threads to complete the calculation. This repeated creation of software threads and the increase in memory read operations can cause additional overhead and slow down the execution. The Java version also benefited from SMT, suggesting that an encapsulated approach saturates of the CPU cores' execution pipelines better, even on small meshes like this.

The performance of the seamless block-wise approach was somewhat contrary to the results of the parallel performance investigation in Sec. 9, where it generally performed better when SMT was enabled. A comparison of the pattern's time shares of the different computational steps showed that the flux calculation was faster with SMT enabled while every other computational step performed worse. The flux calculation seemed to saturate the execution more densely than the other computational steps. Further performance detriments might stem from the resulting communications overhead caused by the increased number of threads, as it was higher than the parallel performance benefit.

Conclusively, the seamless block-wise traversal pattern showed good performance results with room for improvement. One way to possibly improve the performance would be to encapsulate the edge-based flux calculation and the other cell-based computational steps inside the seamless block-wise traversal.

11. Conclusions and future work

The conclusions that are drawn from this work are presented in Sec. 11.1, followed by an outlook to future possibilities concerning the development of `hms++` in Sec. 11.2.

11.1. Conclusions

Hydroinformatics Modeling Systems is a numerical modeling software that allows simulating integrated surface flow and transport processes in natural and urban environments. The Java framework was developed at the Chair of Water Resources Management and Modeling of Hydrosystems at the TU Berlin with a focus on flexibility and expandability to facilitate fast prototyping. However, one aspect that can be improved upon since it is not an expressed goal of the development is computational performance. This is why Steffen et al. (2020) introduced `hms++`, a new open-source framework written in C++ for explicit finite-volume solvers to motivate the exploration of new avenues for optimisation. This work encompasses the verification of the built-in robust solver for the SWEs, the introduction and benchmarking of six new edge traversal schemes for edge-based computational steps, an accompanying preliminary study concerning the tile size of blocked algorithms that were used in a subset of the traversal approaches as well as a comparative study focusing on the performance differences between `hms++` and `hms-java`.

The model was verified by simulating a one-dimensional dam break, featuring a wet and dry bed scenario, in order to test the model's capability of handling discontinuous initial conditions, and by simulating surface runoff in a V-shaped catchment to determine the model's ability to handle sheet-like flow on sloped topography featuring small water depths as well as the wetting and drying of cells. The results showed that the HLLC approximate Riemann solver, extended by a TVD MUSCL scheme, was able to reproduce the analytical solutions of the verification cases with good accuracy.

The verification of the solver was followed by an investigation of the block size, used in block-wise traversal patterns, for possible performance gains due to cache blocking. Early results revealed poor load balancing capabilities of originally designed approaches which led to the subsequent redesign of the patterns. Overall, performance improvements due to cache blocking effects, caused by increasing the block size, were only observable for simulations on the *large* mesh. The absence of benefits on the smaller meshes was attributed to the large amount of available cache memory, ruling out any cache blocking

benefits since the workload is completely stored in cache anyway. Rough estimations for block sizes were given with the remark that further research on the topic is necessary.

In the subsequent parallel performance investigation, the redesigned block-wise traversal approaches as well as the other traversal patterns, described in Sec. 5.5, were put to the test. The problem sets in Sec. 7.1 were simulated with each traversal pattern and varying numbers of CPU cores. Simulations were carried out a second time using simultaneous multithreading. Without SMT, all traversal approaches obtained maximum speed-up factors between $57.52\times$ and $67.41\times$ for the *large* problem set, which suggested good scaling behaviour. Observing the absolute execution times, the patterns obtained similar results, except for the ordered cell approach, which was anticipated since it employs a cell-based flux calculation scheme.

The block-wise, ordered cell and ordered edge traversal patterns scaled even better on the *small* mesh, with maximum speed-ups between $77.52\times$ and $84.09\times$, whereas the row-wise patterns performed considerably worse. This indicated that the latter caused a higher communications overhead than the other patterns. As mentioned, the ordered cell approach scaled well, however, its obtained execution times were still considerably slower.

Overall, the obtained speed-up factors did not reach a constant plateau on the test platform, which indicates that a machine with more cores could improve the performance for the tested problem sets further.

The utilisation of simultaneous multithreading proved to be beneficial for all patterns and problem sets when a small amount of cores was utilised in which cases speed-ups of up to $\sim 30\%$ were obtained. However, some thread configurations actually lead to slow-downs compared to results that were obtained without SMT. Exploiting all 192 hardware threads of the compute node rarely resulted in any speed-ups regardless of mesh size. The only exception to this was the seamless block-wise pattern, which performed 7% faster on the *large* mesh and 18.46% faster on the *small* mesh.

In general, the seamless block-wise pattern consistently obtained the best or next to best results of all patterns.

In order to compare the performance of `hms++` to `hms-java`, a surface runoff scenario in a sub-catchment, based on a real 4-day rainfall event that occurred in 2008 in the Heumöser area, located in the Vorarlberg Alps, Austria, was simulated by both frameworks. Due to time constraints, only the first 24 hours of the event were simulated. A more complete simulation, although with a slightly different reconstruction scheme, was carried out in

Simons (2020). Both version produced very similar results, although several irregularities in the results of `hms++` might indicate a small error in the code, possibly related to some threshold values. Looking at the complete execution times, `hms-java` performed better than anticipated, which was attributed to its encapsulated computation approach, allowing the reuse of cached memory for each step of the computational cycle. The Java version also performed faster with SMT enabled. However, the seamless pattern of `hms++` obtained overall faster computation times with and without the use of SMT, obtaining a maximum speed-up of $1.26\times$ in comparison to the Java version. Unexpectedly, using SMT slightly worsened the performance of all patterns, even of the seamless block-wise approach. Looking at the execution times for the single computational steps of the seamless block-wise pattern showed that the flux calculation was actually faster with SMT. However, the other steps were not, ultimately leading to a longer execution time in total when using SMT.

Conclusively, of all introduced patterns, the block-wise traversal approach showed the best results.

11.2. Future work

While the seamless block-wise pattern proved to be slightly faster than `hms-java`, the surprising performance of the latter made an argument for an encapsulated approach. Combining the faster edge-based flux calculation of `hms++` with the advantages of an encapsulated approach, specifically the reuse of cached memory for every computational step and the smaller overhead due to the thread team only being created once, could further improve the performance of the model. In order to do this in the `hms++` framework, the mesh would still be traversed in a block-wise manner, as described in Sec. 5.5.4 but instead of only doing the flux calculation this way, all computational steps would be carried out sequentially for the currently traversed block by the thread that is assigned to it. A more elaborate synchronisation between threads would be necessary, e.g. for the time step calculation as well as for the calculation of the new state variables. As a result, already cached memory could be reused before it is evicted, costly reloads from main memory and the repeated creation of threads would be avoided.

Since cache memory units read and write data in the shape of cache lines, the arrangement of these lines in the data structures can have a great impact on performance (see Sec. 5.3), especially for block-wise traversal patterns. The simplified indexing scheme does not provide an optimal arrangement since ghost cells are also indexed as part of a row. This

always leads to cachelines overlapping into adjacent blocks, which can be detrimental to the performance since the caches need to be coherent. More control over the arrangement of cache lines could be gained by padding array entries. This is possible with the simplified as well as the unified indexing scheme. Consider the following example using the latter. Since the unified approach indexes the domain cells first and ghost cells last, as seen in Fig. 5.3a, it is possible to avoid overlapping cache lines. If the last data entries in a row do not fill out their cache line and the latter does overlap into the next row, the array could be padded with entries in order to restore the more controllable arrangement, illustrated in Fig. 11.1

Figure 11.1: Exemplary cache lines for one-dimensional variable for a 21×16 mesh with unified indexing. Left and right figures depict cache line arrangement without and with padding, respectively.

Regarding SIMD optimisations, the model only considered auto-vectorisation through the use of specific compiler flags. Additionally, Eigen also supports prominent SIMD instruction sets for which it performs explicit vectorisation. However, vectorisation reports should be checked and guided vectorisation directives should be tested for possible performance gains. The manual use of vector intrinsics is not recommended since they are highly machine-dependent, which is detrimental to the portability of the code. Furthermore, it is unclear how the data structures of Eigen and would cope with the manual use of intrinsics since Eigen already utilises vectorisation.

Another optimisation avenue worth exploring are distributed-memory systems, also known as *Massive Parallel Processing* (MPP). The concept of a global address space

that is shared across all nodes, like in *Symmetric Multiprocessing*, does not exist for MPP systems. Here, each compute node only has its own local memory, which entails that memory access times are always fast since each processor can only access its local memory. In order for the nodes to communicate with one another, they are connected via a communication network, used to transfer the data. Additionally, this kind of isolation results in data independence for each processor, i.e. updating the local memory has no effect on the memory partitions of other nodes, it is not required to keep the caches between nodes coherent. Distributed-memory systems also work well with larger node configurations as they are more easily upscalable than shared-memory systems by simply adding more nodes to the network. Scalability is also more cost-efficient when compared to shared-memory systems, as the nodes and network components can be common retail products. Programming for such systems requires the programmer to write code that explicitly states how and when the communication between the nodes takes place, often referred to as message passing. In addition, the code for the issue at hand has to be written on a local instead of a global scale, e.g. the domain of a flow simulation is decomposed into multiple parts distributed to multiple nodes in the system (Barney & Frederick, 2021). The application then runs on each node and handles a single part of the decomposed domain. This circumstance often requires laborious rewrites of data structures and traversal subroutines already existing for a the global consideration of the scale. However, subroutines for the time-marching algorithm can be reused without any major changes.

The most prominent standard addressing this model is the *Message-Passing Interface* (MPI), enabling different processes to communicate and cooperate on parallel tasks. The standard has been implemented commercially as well as in the open-source community, (Pacheco, 2011).

A great deal of work has already been done to implement MPI into `hms++` and development continues.

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A. Supplemental material

Access to the source code of `hms++` is granted by the Chair of Water Resources Management and Modeling of Hydrosystems, Technische Universität Berlin. The full GIT repository is available at <https://git.tu-berlin.de/wahyd/hmspp>.

The branch associated with this work is called `finn-master`.

Further supplemental material, including the full simulation results, is available at <https://git.tu-berlin.de/finn.amann2011/finn-amann-master-thesis-digital-appendix>. Please contact the author for access (finn.amann@wahyd.tu-berlin.de).

A.1. Remarks on function names

The following list contains the actual function names of the traversal patterns as they exist in the source code. The list only contains traversal patterns for the second-order accurate HLLC approximate Riemann solver that were used in this work.

Pattern name in this work	Pattern name in source code
Traversing edges	
Ordered edge	<code>orderedSecondOrder</code>
Seaml. row-wise	<code>rowwiseSecondOrder</code>
Seamed row-wise	<code>rowwiseSecondOrderThreadsafe</code>
Seaml. block-wise	<code>blockwiseSecondOrderAtomic</code>
Seamed block-wise	<code>blockwiseSecondOrderThreadsafe</code>
Seaml. block-wise (revised)	<code>blockwiseSecondOrderAtomicDynamic</code>
Seamed block-wise (revised)	<code>blockwiseSecondOrderThreadsafeDynamic</code>
Traversing cells	
Ordered cell	<code>orderedSecondOrder</code>

Table A.1: Function names for traversal patterns found in the source code.

B. Compiler flags

The following optimisation flags are provided by gcc and are activated with the `-O3` flag.

<code>-faggressive-loop-optimizations</code>	<code>-finline-functions-called-once</code>	<code>-fsched-last-insn-heuristic</code>
<code>-falign-functions</code>	<code>-finline-small-functions</code>	<code>-fsched-rank-heuristic</code>
<code>-falign-jumps</code>	<code>-fipa-cp</code>	<code>-fsched-spec</code>
<code>-falign-labels</code>	<code>-fipa-cp-clone</code>	<code>-fsched-spec-insn-heuristic</code>
<code>-falign-loops</code>	<code>-fipa-profile</code>	<code>-fsched-stalled-insns-dep</code>
<code>-fasynchronous-unwind-tables</code>	<code>-fipa-pure-const</code>	<code>-fschedule-insns2</code>
<code>-fbranch-count-reg</code>	<code>-fipa-reference</code>	<code>-fshort-enums</code>
<code>-fcaller-saves</code>	<code>-fipa-sra</code>	<code>-fshrink-wrap</code>
<code>-fcombine-stack-adjustments</code>	<code>-fira-hoist-pressure</code>	<code>-fsigned-zeros</code>
<code>-fcommon</code>	<code>-fivopts</code>	<code>-fsplit-ivs-in-unroller</code>
<code>-fcompare-elim</code>	<code>-fjump-tables</code>	<code>-fsplit-wide-types</code>
<code>-fcprop-registers</code>	<code>-fmath-errno</code>	<code>-fstrict-aliasing</code>
<code>-fcrossjumping</code>	<code>-fmerge-constants</code>	<code>-fthread-jumps</code>
<code>-fcse-follow-jumps</code>	<code>-fmove-loop-invariants</code>	<code>-fno-threadsafe-statics</code>
<code>-fdce</code>	<code>-foptimize-register-move</code>	<code>-ftoplevel-reorder</code>
<code>-fdefer-pop</code>	<code>-foptimize-sibling-calls</code>	<code>-ftrapping-math</code>
<code>-fdelete-null-pointer-checks</code>	<code>-foptimize-strlen</code>	<code>-ftree-bit-ccp</code>
<code>-fdevirtualize</code>	<code>-fpeephole</code>	<code>-ftree-builtin-call-dce</code>
<code>-fdse</code>	<code>-fpeephole2</code>	<code>-ftree-ccp</code>
<code>-fearly-inlining</code>	<code>-fpredictive-commoning</code>	<code>-ftree-ch</code>
<code>-fexpensive-optimizations</code>	<code>-fprefetch-loop-arrays</code>	<code>-ftree-coalesce-vars</code>
<code>-fforward-propagate</code>	<code>-fregmove</code>	<code>-ftree-copy-prop</code>
<code>-fgcse</code>	<code>-frename-registers</code>	<code>-ftree-copyrename</code>
<code>-fgcse-after-reload</code>	<code>-freorder-blocks</code>	<code>-ftree-cselim</code>
<code>-fgcse-lm</code>	<code>-freorder-functions</code>	<code>-ftree-dce</code>
<code>-fguess-branch-probability</code>	<code>-frerun-cse-after-loop</code>	<code>-ftree-dominator-opts</code>
<code>-fhoist-adjacent-loads</code>	<code>-frtti</code>	<code>-ftree-dse</code>
<code>-fif-conversion</code>	<code>-fsched-critical-path-heuristic</code>	<code>-ftree-forwprop</code>
<code>-fif-conversion2</code>	<code>-fsched-dep-count-heuristic</code>	<code>-ftree-fre</code>
<code>-finline</code>	<code>-fsched-group-heuristic</code>	<code>-ftree-loop-distribute-patterns</code>
<code>-finline-atomics</code>	<code>-fsched-interblock</code>	<code>-ftree-loop-if-convert</code>
<code>-finline-functions</code>		<code>-ftree-loop-im</code>

<code>-ftree-loop-ivcanon</code>	<code>-ftree-slp-vectorize</code>	<code>-ftree-vectorize</code>
<code>-ftree-loop-optimize</code>	<code>-ftree-slsr</code>	<code>-ftree-vrp</code>
<code>-ftree-partial-pre</code>	<code>-ftree-sra</code>	<code>-funit-at-a-time</code>
<code>-ftree-phi-prop</code>	<code>-ftree-switch-</code>	<code>-funswitch-loops</code>
<code>-ftree-pre</code>	<code>conversion</code>	<code>-fvar-tracking</code>
<code>-ftree-pta</code>	<code>-ftree-tail-merge</code>	<code>-fvar-tracking-</code>
<code>-ftree-reassoc</code>	<code>-ftree-ter</code>	<code>assignments</code>
<code>-ftree-scev-cprop</code>	<code>-ftree-vect-loop-</code>	<code>-fvect-cost-model</code>
<code>-ftree-sink</code>	<code>version</code>	<code>-fweb</code>

Listing 1: Optimisation flags activated by `-O3`

Furthermore, the machine specific flag `-march=native` was used. On the test platform described in Sec. 7.2, the following flags are activated by `-march=native`.

<code>-m128bit-long-double</code>	<code>-mfancy-math-387</code>	<code>-mrdseed</code>
<code>-m64</code>	<code>-mfma</code>	<code>-mred-zone</code>
<code>-m80387</code>	<code>-mfp-ret-in-387</code>	<code>-msahf</code>
<code>-madx</code>	<code>-mfsgsbase</code>	<code>-msgx</code>
<code>-maes</code>	<code>-mfixsr</code>	<code>-msse</code>
<code>-malign-stringops</code>	<code>-mglibc</code>	<code>-msse2</code>
<code>-mavx</code>	<code>-mhard-float</code>	<code>-msse3</code>
<code>-mavx2</code>	<code>-mhle</code>	<code>-msse4</code>
<code>-mavx512bw</code>	<code>-mieee-fp</code>	<code>-msse4.1</code>
<code>-mavx512cd</code>	<code>-mlong-double-80</code>	<code>-msse4.2</code>
<code>-mavx512dq</code>	<code>-mlzcnt</code>	<code>-mssse3</code>
<code>-mavx512f</code>	<code>-mmmx</code>	<code>-mstv</code>
<code>-mavx512vl</code>	<code>-mmovbe</code>	<code>-mtls-direct-seg-refs</code>
<code>-mbmi</code>	<code>-mpclmul</code>	<code>-mvzeroupper</code>
<code>-mbmi2</code>	<code>-mpku</code>	<code>-mxsave</code>
<code>-mclflushopt</code>	<code>-mpopcnt</code>	<code>-mxsavec</code>
<code>-mclwb</code>	<code>-mprfchw</code>	<code>-mxsaveopt</code>
<code>-mcx16</code>	<code>-mpush-args</code>	<code>-mxsaves</code>
<code>-mf16c</code>	<code>-mrdrnd</code>	

Listing 2: Optimisation flags activated by `-march=native`

C. Execution configurations

An exemplary command to execute four processes via `mpirun` may look like

```
mpirun -ppn 2 \  
    -np 2 ./binary.bin args1 \  
    : -np 1 ./anotherBinary.bin args : -np 1 ./yetAnotherbinary.bin args
```

The the number of MPI processes per node is controlled via the `-ppn <#processes-per-node>` switch for the `mpirun` command. The next lines command how many processes are to be started with the executable binary that follows. In order to allocate the necessary compute nodes, the `--nodes=<#number-of-nodes>` variables has to be given in the job script.

Thread configurations, including OpenMP environment variables and MPI switches are listed below.

Thread configuration #1 — 1 core/process		
OMP_NUM_THREADS=1 OMP_PROC_BIND=spread	--nodes=9 -ppn 4	Four processes/node with one thread each. One thread/die (UMA). 1 thread/core.
Thread configuration #2 — 16 cores/process		
OMP_NUM_THREADS=16 OMP_PROC_BIND=close OMP_PLACES="cores(16)"	--nodes=9 -ppn 4	Four processes/node with 16 threads each. 16 threads/die (UMA). 1 thread/core.
Thread configuration #3 — 32 cores/process		
OMP_NUM_THREADS=32 OMP_PROC_BIND=spread	--nodes=18 -ppn 2	Two processes/node with 32 threads each. 16 threads/die (NUMA). 1 thread/core.
Thread configuration #4 — 48 cores/process		
OMP_NUM_THREADS=48 OMP_PROC_BIND=spread	--nodes=18 -ppn 2	Two processes/node with 48 threads each. 24 threads/die (NUMA). 1 thread/core.
Thread configuration #5 — 64 cores/process		
OMP_NUM_THREADS=64 OMP_PROC_BIND=spread	--nodes=36 -ppn 1	One process/node with 64 threads each. 16 threads/die (NUMA). 1 thread/core.
Thread configuration #6 — 80 cores/process		
OMP_NUM_THREADS=80 OMP_PROC_BIND=spread	--nodes=36 -ppn 1	One process/node with 80 threads each. 20 threads/die (NUMA). 1 thread/core.
Thread configuration #7 — 96 cores/process		
OMP_NUM_THREADS=96 OMP_PROC_BIND=spread	--nodes=36 -ppn 1	One process/node with 96 threads each. 24 threads/die (NUMA). 1 thread/core.

Table C.1: Thread configurations without SMT for the scalability study.

Thread configuration #8 — 1 core/process		
OMP_NUM_THREADS=2 OMP_PROC_BIND=close OMP_PLACES="cores(1)"	--nodes=9 -ppn 4	Four processes/node with two threads each. Two threads/die (UMA). 2 threads/core.
Thread configuration #9 — 16 cores/process		
OMP_NUM_THREADS=32 OMP_PROC_BIND=close OMP_PLACES="cores(16)"	--nodes=9 -ppn 4	Four processes/node with 32 threads each. 32 thread/die (UMA). 2 threads/core.
Thread configuration #10 — 32 cores/process		
OMP_NUM_THREADS=64 OMP_PROC_BIND=spread	--nodes=18 -ppn 2	Two processes/node with 64 threads each. 32 threads/die (NUMA). 2 threads/core.
Thread configuration #11 — 48 cores/process		
OMP_NUM_THREADS=96 OMP_PROC_BIND=spread	--nodes=18 -ppn 2	Two processes/node with 96 threads each. 48 threads/die (NUMA). 2 threads/core.
Thread configuration #12 — 64 cores/process		
OMP_NUM_THREADS=128 OMP_PROC_BIND=spread	--nodes=36 -ppn 1	One processes/node with 128 threads each. 32 threads/die (NUMA). 2 threads/core.
Thread configuration #13 — 80 cores/process		
OMP_NUM_THREADS=160 OMP_PROC_BIND=spread	--nodes=36 -ppn 1	One processes/node with 160 threads each. 40 threads/die (NUMA). 2 threads/core.
Thread configuration #14 — 96 cores/process		
OMP_NUM_THREADS=192 OMP_PROC_BIND=spread	--nodes=36 -ppn 1	One processes/node with 192 threads each. 48 threads/die (NUMA). 2 threads/core.

Table C.2: Thread configurations with SMT for the scalability study.

D. Execution times of parallel performance investigation

The following tables contain the fastest execution times obtained by the investigated traversal patterns and thread configurations.

Thread con-fig. #	Ordered edge	Ordered cell	Seamless row-wise	Seamed row-wise	Seamless block-wise	Seamed block-wise
1 (1-core)	1633.10	2307.27	1637.48	1542.50	1672.38	1588.67
2 (16-core)	105.28	147.96	107.32	99.91	107.43	102.25
3 (32-core)	54.63	76.10	55.80	53.13	55.94	53.48
4 (48-core)	40.66	56.04	42.92	39.60	41.12	40.11
5 (64-core)	33.28	45.43	34.37	32.72	33.07	32.78
6 (80-core)	29.57	38.68	40.65	28.28	29.41	28.41
7 (96-core)	26.13	34.22	28.46	25.96	26.08	25.41

Table D.1: Fastest execution times [s] for the *large* problem set. SMT is disabled.

Thread con-fig. #	Ordered edge	Ordered cell	Seamless row-wise	Seamed row-wise	Seamless block-wise	Seamed block-wise
8 (1-core)	1250.67	1846.68	1252.63	1234.78	1264.94	1239.68
9 (16-core)	83.58	122.15	84.59	83.14	83.28	81.94
10 (32-core)	47.15	68.88	48.23	47.11	46.23	46.22
11 (48-core)	36.22	57.40	42.98	37.92	35.32	34.92
12 (64-core)	30.09	55.33	35.38	33.12	28.66	29.18
13 (80-core)	27.70	53.56	33.25	35.25	26.07	26.19
14 (96-core)	25.94	48.76	33.27	29.70	24.38	25.48

Table D.2: Fastest execution times [s] for the *large* problem set. SMT is enabled.

D. Execution times of parallel performance investigation

Thread con- fig. #	Ordered edge	Ordered cell	Seamless row-wise	Seamed row-wise	Seamless block-wise	Seamed block-wise
1 (1-core)	1003.10	1415.75	1006.52	949.92	1037.67	984.81
2 (16-core)	64.72	91.35	66.46	62.89	65.47	62.09
3 (32-core)	32.76	46.92	34.86	32.53	32.78	31.56
4 (48-core)	22.21	31.19	25.63	23.25	22.50	21.76
5 (64-core)	17.14	24.94	22.38	21.42	17.62	17.23
6 (80-core)	14.29	20.92	22.27	19.32	14.57	14.33
7 (96-core)	12.10	18.26	21.70	17.38	12.33	12.54

Table D.3: Fastest execution times [s] for the *small* problem set. SMT is disabled.

Thread con- fig. #	Ordered edge	Ordered cell	Seamless row-wise	Seamed row-wise	Seamless block-wise	Seamed block-wise
8 (1-core)	769.59	1128.87	770.87	757.74	792.16	772.92
9 (16-core)	50.74	76.69	53.61	51.92	50.28	49.28
10 (32-core)	26.05	43.73	29.80	27.42	25.48	25.33
11 (48-core)	18.78	37.18	27.64	22.16	18.32	18.85
12 (64-core)	14.46	34.63	24.21	19.14	13.60	13.95
13 (80-core)	13.19	31.49	20.29	19.93	11.40	12.21
14 (96-core)	12.49	28.29	21.13	18.12	10.41	12.33

Table D.4: Fastest execution times [s] for the *small* problem set. SMT is enabled.

E. Revision of seamed block-wise traversal pattern

In Sec. 8, the poor load balancing capabilities of the seamless block-wise traversal approach have been revealed. Since the seamed block-wise traversal strategy distributes the workload in similar fashion, the approach had to be revised as well. In App. E.1, the modified code is documented. A short analysis of the code can be found in App. E.2.

E.1. Modified code

Changes to the original code, documented in Code 10, include the reordering of the traversal and changes to the work schedule. The revised traversal approach is processing the inner blocks first on a `static` work schedule and allows finished threads to move on to handle remainder blocks on the right and top side via a `nowait` clause, as listed in Code 13, lines 11 to 25. These remainder blocks are distributed through a `dynamic` work schedule, enabling better load balancing.

```

1 // helpful variables
2 int nx = number of cells in x-direction
3 int ny = number of cells in y-direction
4 int blocksize = square root of the number of cells per block
5 int nBlocksX = number of blocks in x-direction
6 int nBlocksY = number of blocks in y-direction
7
8 // open up a parallel region
9 #pragma omp parallel {
10
11 #pragma omp for schedule(static) collapse(2) nowait
12 for(int by = 0; by<nBlocksY; ++by)
13     for(int bx = 0; bx<nBlocksX; ++bx)
14         // inner blocks
15
16 if( remaining cells in x-direction exist ) {
17     #pragma omp for schedule(dynamic) nowait
18     for(int by = 0; by<nBlocksY; by++)
19         // remainder blocks on the right
20 }
21 if( remaining cells in y-direction exist ) {
22     #pragma omp for schedule(dynamic) nowait
23     for( int bx = 0; bx<nBlocksX; bx++)
24         // remainder blocks on top
25 }
26 #pragma omp single
27 if( remaining cells in x- and y-direction exist )
28     // corner block
29     // implicit barrier
30
31 #pragma omp single nowait
32     // first two vertical edges at the bottom left
33
34 #pragma omp for schedule(static) nowait
35 for(int row = 1; row<ny; row++)
36     // last two edges of previous row, first two edges of curent row
37
38 #pragma omp single nowait
39     // last two vertical edges at the top right
40
41 ...
42 // --> see next Code.

```

Code 13: Revised seamed block-wise traversal.

```

1  ...
2  #pragma omp for schedule(static) collapse(2)
3  for(int col = 1; col<((rem.x() > 0) ? nBlocksX+1 : nBlocksX ) ; col
4      ++)
5      for(int row = 0; row<ny-2; row++)
6          // shared vertical MUSCL edges
7
8  #pragma omp single
9  // first horizontal MUSCL edge in left column
10
11 #pragma omp for schedule(static)
12 for(int row=3; row<ny-1; row += 2)
13     // every second horizontal MUSCL edge in left and right column
14
15 #pragma omp for schedule(static)
16 for(int row=4; row<ny-1; row += 2)
17     // every skipped horizontal MUSCL edge in left and right column
18
19 #pragma omp single
20 // last horizontal MUSCL edge in right column
21
22 #pragma omp for schedule(static)
23 for(int col = 0; col<nx; col++)
24     // central edges at top and bottom row
25
26 #pragma omp for schedule(static) collapse(2)
27 for(int row = 1; col<((rem.y() > 0) ? nBlocksY+1 : nBlocksY ) ; col++)
28     for(int col = 0; col<nx-2; col++)
29         // shared horizontal edges
30
31 #pragma omp for schedule(static)
32 for(int col = 2; col<nx-1; col += 2)
33     // every second vertical MUSCL edge in top and bottom row
34
35 #pragma omp for schedule(static)
36 for(int col = 3; col<nx-1; col += 2)
37     // every skipped vertical MUSCL edge in top and bottom row
38 } // end of parallel region.

```

Code 13: (Cont.) Revised seamed block-wise traversal.

E.2. Analysis

The revised pattern was only tested on the *large* problem set.

Figure E.1: Execution times of the flux calculation for the *large* problem set.

The flux execution times for the flux calculation are plotted in Fig. E.1 and showcased the improved load balancing capabilities of the revised approach. Both patterns obtained decreasing flux calculation times for expanding block sizes with the more pronounced speed-up obtained by the modified approach, evidenced by the moving averages of the curves. However, the fastest times obtained are very similar to one another, with 11.95 s and 11.77 s for the original and revised strategy, respectively. Similar to the seamless approach analysed in Sec. 8.2, the original pattern's execution times begin to increase for block sizes larger than ~ 65 , accompanied by increasing fluctuations as well. Due to the improved load balancing, the revised approach dampened the increase in execution times and fluctuations successfully.

The execution times of the friction source term calculations, plotted in Fig. E.2, are quite similar to one another, averaging 10.17 s and 10.18 s for the original and modified strategy, respectively.

Both patterns obtained similar times for the time step calculation and the updating of

Figure E.2: Execution times for friction source term calculation for the *large* problem set.

boundaries. The former averaged 0.11 s for both approaches and the latter averaged 0.29 s using the original strategy and 0.30 s when employing the revised approach. Similar to the calculation of the new state variables using the seamless block-wise patterns, the execution times begin to fluctuate increasingly for block sizes larger than ~ 70 .

	Original pattern	Modified pattern
Slowest exec. time	33.19 s	28.00 s
Block size	199	3
Fastest exec. time	23.60 s	23.67 s
Block size	70	85

Table E.1: Slowest and fastest complete execution times for *large* problem set.

For both versions, the updating of the boundaries as well as the time step calculation are not impacted by a change in the block size, as seen in Fig. E.3. The calculation of the new state variables of both version is very much alike as well. When reaching a tile size of ~ 70 , the fluctuations start to increase.

Fig. E.4 depicts the complete execution times for the original and revised approach.

Figure E.3: Execution times of the calculation of the time step, new state variables and updating of boundaries for the *large* problem set.

Figure E.4: Complete execution times for the *large* problem set.

Looking at the moving averages, the revised traversal strategy was mostly faster than the original pattern, although the latter obtained faster times for block sizes 42 to 46. However, the fastest execution time was achieved by the original pattern, although not by much, as seen in Tab. E.1. When comparing the slowest and fastest times within the patterns, the original pattern obtained a speed-up of $1.41\times$, whereas the modified approach was $1.18\times$ faster.

In conclusion, the revision of the original strategy resulted in improved load balancing capabilities, although it did not improve on the fastest complete execution time.